

UNIVERSITÀ DEGLI STUDI DI NAPOLI
FEDERICO II

University of Naples Federico II

Department of Industrial Engineering
PhD in Industrial Engineering

THESIS FOR THE DEGREE OF DOCTOR OF PHILOSOPHY

Intelligence Onboard Satellites: Deep Learning techniques for effective onboard data processing

Thesis Advisor
Prof. Alfredo Renga
Prof. Maria Daniela Graziano

Candidate
Roberto Del Prete

Academic Year 2023-2024 (XXXVII cycle)

*“ Dovunque sono andato nel mondo ho
visto che c'era bisogno di un poco di
Napoli ”*

- Luciano De Crescenzo

Acknowledgements

First and foremost, I would like to express my deepest gratitude to Prof. Alfredo Renga and Prof. Maria Daniela Graziano, my PhD advisors. Your consistent support and invaluable guidance have been crucial throughout my academic journey. You allowed me the freedom to explore my ideas while providing thoughtful direction, offering both wisdom and motivation. Beyond your roles as advisors, you have been like an older brother and sister to me—mentors whose trust and camaraderie made this journey truly memorable. For that, I will always be profoundly grateful. Your insights have not only shaped my research but also helped me grow as a scientist and as a person. The many discussions we had, the challenges we overcame together, and the knowledge you imparted are all things that I will carry with me throughout my career and life. I cannot thank you enough for the balance of autonomy and guidance that allowed me to develop my skills and pursue my passions without hesitation. Your belief in me has been a beacon of encouragement during difficult times, and for that, I am forever thankful.

I would also like to extend my sincere thanks to the Φ -lab team at ESA, especially to Gabriele and Nicolas. Your support, encouragement, and collaboration over these years have significantly enriched my research. Working alongside you has been an honor, and your friendship has been an incredible source of strength. The Φ -lab has been like a second home, providing an environment where creativity and “disruptive” innovation flourished. The countless brainstorming sessions, shared projects, and even the moments of trial and error have been crucial in refining my work and driving it forward. Gabriele and Nicolas, you both have been my machine learning brothers, offering not only technical insights but also emotional support when things seemed overwhelming. I will cherish those moments always, and I look forward to continuing our friendships and professional collaborations in the future.

To my family, who have stood by me with unwavering love and belief, I owe everything. Your encouragement has been the foundation upon which I have built this journey. To my girlfriend Alessandra, thank you for your patience, warmth, and for being my anchor during challenging times. You have celebrated my successes, comforted me in my failures, and always reminded me of what truly matters in life. I cannot imagine having undertaken this journey without you by my side.

Finally, I want to thank my dad. Though he is no longer with us, his enduring belief in me and the lessons he taught have always been my guiding light. I dedicate this work to him. His influence on my life is immeasurable, and his memory continues to drive me to be the best version of myself. I think of him often, especially during moments of accomplishment and challenge. I hope that this work, in some small way, continues his legacy. I carry his spirit with me, and this thesis is as much a testament to his dreams as it is to mine.

Roberto Del Prete, Napoli, 10-2024

Abstract

The timely and efficient onboard processing of vast quantities of data is crucial for the effective exploitation of current and future space sensing capabilities. Space missions generate enormous quantity of data which require rapid and tailored analysis to support real-time decision-making and enhance operational efficiency. In very recent times, the deployment of Artificial Intelligence (AI) onboard space missions has attracted considerable interest from the scientific community due to its substantial benefits, including reduced latency, minimized bandwidth, and improved system autonomy. By processing data directly on-the-fly, AI can significantly curtail the need for extensive data transmission to ground stations, thereby optimizing bandwidth utilization, expediting response times, and enhancing overall mission autonomy. This technology holds transformative potential for reshaping emergency response mechanisms and advancing space exploration, ultimately delivering significant benefits to humankind.

Nonetheless, significant challenges persist in the implementation of machine learning for onboard space systems. A primary challenge lies in the considerable cost associated with data acquisition from space environments, which hinders the adoption of data-driven machine learning algorithms. Additionally, the unique physical and operational complexities inherent to the space environment—such as the impact of solar radiation on sensor performance, stringent constraints on spacecraft size, weight, and power, as well as restricted communication bandwidth for telemetry and data transfer—present challenges that are largely absent in terrestrial applications. Moreover, the domain gap problem, resulting from the inherent difficulty in generating datasets that comprehensively represent operational space scenarios, continues to impose substantial limitations on the effective automation of machine learning models for space applications.

To address these challenges, this thesis explores the application of deep learning methodologies for onboard satellite data processing across three critical domains: wildfire response, autonomous spacecraft navigation, and maritime situational awareness. Each of these domains presents distinct challenges, such as the need for rapid detection and localization of wildfires from sparse data, the precise navigation of spacecraft in dynamic and unpredictable environments, and the monitoring of vast maritime regions for potential threats. Addressing these challenges requires the development of innovative AI-driven solutions that can enhance the efficiency, robustness, and autonomy of satellite operations, ultimately pushing the boundaries of what can be achieved with current space technology.

By integrating AI capabilities directly into spaceborne systems, this research aims to substantiate the advantages of onboard intelligence, and the findings presented herein contribute to the advancement of AI-driven space sensing, providing a foundational framework for more autonomous and efficient satellite operations. This work not only underscores the technical feasibility of onboard AI but also highlights its transformative potential for future space missions, capable of independent operation in complex and evolving environments.

Keywords: onboard processing, deep learning, wildfire response, visual-based navigation, maritime situational awareness.

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Acronyms

AI Artificial Intelligence

AIS Automatic Identification System

AN Autonomous Navigation

AOI Area Of Interest

B2B Band-to-Band

BRISK Binary Robust Invariant Scalable Keypoints

CAM Channel Attention Module

CCD Charge-Coupled Device

CDA Crater Detection Algorithm

CET Central European Time

CFAR Constant False Alarm Rate

CG Coarse Georeferencing

CLAHE Contrast Limited Adaptive Histogram Equalization

CM-vessel curved-moving vessel

CMA Crater Matching Algorithm

CNN Convolutional Neural Network

COG Speed Over Ground

CPU Central Processing Unit

CSC Coarse Spatial Coregistration

CSK COSMO-SkyMed

CV Cross-Validation

CV Computer Vision

DEM Digital Elevation Map

DL Deep Learning

DN Digital Number

DSN Deep Space Network

E2E End-to-End

ED Euclidean Distance

EKF Extended Kalman Filter

EO Earth Observation

EPnP Efficient Perspective-n-Point

ESA European Space Agency

ESTRACK European Space Tracking network

FC Fully-Connected

FFT Fast Fourier Transform

FLOAT16 16-bit Floating Point

FOV Field Of View

FPGA Field Programmable Gate Array

FPN Feature Pyramid Network

FPS Frames Per Second

GNN Graph Neural Network

GPU Graphics Processing Unit

GRD Ground Range Detected

HH Horizontal transmit-Horizontal receive

HOG Histogram of Oriented Gradients

IMO International Maritime Organization

IoU Intersection over Union

ISA Israeli Space Agency

IW Interferometric Wide

IW Interferometric Wide

L0 Level-0

L1A Level-1A

L1B Level-1B

L1C Level-1C

L2A Level-2A

LCLF Lunar Centered Lunar Fixed

LEO Low Earth Orbit

LOLA Lunar Orbiter Laser Altimeter

LRO Lunar Reconnaissance Orbiter

LROC Lunar Reconnaissance Orbiter Camera

MCC Matthew Correlation Coefficient

ML Machine Learning

MMD Multi-Mission Dataset

MMSI Maritime Mobile Service Identity

MPA Marine Protected Areas

MSA Maritime Situational Awareness

MSI MultiSpectral Instrument

MSSWD Multi-Spectral Ship Wake Dataset

MTF Modulation Transfer Function

NCS Neural Comput Stick

NCS2 Neural Comput Stick 2

NMS Non Maximum Suppression

OD Object Detection

OPNAV Optical Navigation

ORB Oriented FAST and Rotated BRIEF

PCC Pearson Correlation Coefficient

PEA Position Estimation Algorithm

PMA Product Matching Algorithm

PSF Point Spread Function

PyRawS Python for RAW Sentinel-2 data

RADC Residual-Attention-Dilated-Convolution

RANSAC Random Sample Consensus

RMSE Root Mean Square Error

ROI Region of Interest

RT Radon Transform

S-2 Sentinel-2

SAHI Slicing Aided Hyper Inference

SAR Synthetic Aperture Radar

SD Ship Detection

SGD Stochastic Gradient Descent

SHAVE Streaming Hybrid Architecture Vector Engine

SIFT Scale-Invariant Feature Transform

SLC Single-Look Complex

SNR Signal-to-Noise Ratio

SOG Course Over Ground

SRTM Shuttle Radar Topography Mission

SSWD SAR Ship Wake Dataset

SURF Speeded-Up Robust Features

SWIM Ship Wake Imagery Mass

T&C Tip & Cue

TDI Time Delay Integration

THRaws Thermal Hotspots in Raw Sentinel-2 images

TOA top-of-atmosphere

TSX TerraSAR-X

UTC Coordinated Universal Time

VCN Vision-Based Navigation

VEI Volcanic Explosive Index

VH Vertical transmit-Horizontal receive

VPU Vision Processing Unit

VSSC VEN μ S SuperSpectral Camera

VV Vertical transmit-Vertical receive

WAC Wide Angle Camera

WR Wildfire Response

XE1 CogniSAT-XE1

Chapter 1

Introduction

This chapter introduces the significance of this research, presenting the core structure of the thesis in its chapters.

1.1 Artificial Intelligence Onboard Satellites

The heritage of past AI-enabled satellite missions plays a pivotal role in shaping the landscape of current research. Over the years, numerous studies have delved into the integration of Machine Learning (ML) models for onboard data processing, a trend initiated by missions such as EO-1 and Φ -Sat-1 [13–15]. These missions paved the way for a new era in Earth Observation (EO) by demonstrating the significant benefits of onboard AI, including data reduction, enhanced decision-making capabilities, and real-time actionable insights. One of the key advantages of AI onboard satellites is the ability to downlink only relevant data, thus reducing bandwidth consumption by filtering out images with limited information content [16, 17]. Furthermore, AI-driven decision-making facilitates near real-time responses to natural disasters, enhancing the satellite’s ability to deliver crucial information when timing is critical [1, 18–20]. Other benefits include the fast retrieval of localized information, such as identifying changes or targets in specific areas [21], as well as the execution of onboard data correction techniques like atmospheric correction and compression [22–24]. Within the framework of remote sensing, the ongoing evolution of AI in space is best exemplified by Φ Sat-2, which continues to push the boundaries of onboard processing with advanced multispectral and panchromatic data workflows [25].

If we look outside the EO framework, benefits coming from the onboard application of AI include the enhanced real-time decision-making, and autonomy from ground-based systems. For instance, GPU@SAT [26], a radiation-hardened Field Programmable Gate Array (FPGA)-based IP-core, demonstrates how AI algorithms can be implemented onboard satellites using OpenCL programming to deliver enhanced computational performance in space environments. AI is now being used for real-time in-orbit navigation of planetary orbiters to effectively process visual information in space, improving navigation accuracy and autonomy [27]. The SpIRIT nanosatellite’s Loris payload represents another milestone in the use of AI for onboard computing. It has been designed to carry out computer vision experiments in space, tackling common space challenges such as cosmic radiation and the limited computational resources available on small platforms [28]. This demonstrates the potential for AI-driven solutions to not only process data efficiently but also to operate

autonomously in harsh space environments, making satellites more resilient and capable of functioning with minimal ground intervention. Similarly, the LetSat-1 project aims to demonstrate the use of Graphics Processing Unit (GPU)-based AI hardware for satellite navigation, employing machine vision to determine orbital parameters autonomously [29]. This project highlights how AI-enhanced hardware can support more sophisticated satellite navigation systems, reducing the dependency on ground-based tracking and enabling spacecraft to operate with greater independence.

These developments collectively illustrate the transformative potential of AI in space. By leveraging its parallel computing paradigm, particularly through advanced hardware platforms, the adaptability and scalability of such systems is not only improving data processing efficiency but also enabling higher levels of autonomy. This shift is particularly significant for current and future space missions, where real-time responses, enhanced autonomy capabilities, and reduced communication delays will be crucial to mission success.

1.2 Research Objectives

The research aims to demonstrate the application and effectiveness of AI in resource-constrained environments, such as those encountered on spacecraft. The primary objective is to design and implement AI-driven systems capable of processing data and making autonomous decisions in real time, utilizing the limited computational resources available onboard spacecraft. This research encompasses the development of tailored pre-processing techniques, Deep Learning (DL) models, and the testing of edge-computing hardware currently in use or proposed for space missions.

To achieve this overarching goal, the research focuses on three distinct application domains: Maritime Situational Awareness (MSA), Wildfire Response (WR), and Autonomous Navigation (AN) for planetary mission. These three domains were selected based on their relevance to both Earth-based and space-exploration missions, as well as their demand for real-time processing, decision-making, and autonomy.

The goal within MSA is to enhance the accuracy and response time of vessel identification systems, thereby improving the monitoring of marine protected areas, enabling more effective border control, and addressing illegal fishing activities. This objective seeks to demonstrate how AI and DL algorithms can be used to classify and track vessels from satellite imagery or other remote sensing data. By improving vessel detection and classification, this research could aid in better monitoring of human activities at sea, providing actionable information for national security and environmental protection. This topic has been explored in [20, 30–34].

For WR, the objective is to enhance the detection and real-time monitoring of wildfires. By leveraging satellite imagery, thermal sensors, and other remote sensing tools, AI algorithms aim to detect the early signs of wildfires and provide timely alerts to local authorities. This would enable faster and more coordinated disaster responses, potentially mitigating the impact of wildfires on human life, property, and the environment. Additionally, AI could assist in predicting fire spread and providing real-time situational awareness to firefighters on the ground. The research concerning WR has been further elaborated in [1].

The AN domain focuses on developing autonomous navigation systems for space missions, particularly for lunar and planetary exploration. The goal is to create systems capable of independent operation, reducing reliance on ground-based control systems. These AI-powered systems must

process sensor data in real-time, navigating the spacecraft or rover through complex and dynamic extraterrestrial environments while avoiding hazards and optimizing routes. The AN has been investigated in [35–38]

In summary, this thesis investigates the application of AI techniques in each of these three domains using existing spacecraft hardware and software frameworks. The scope of the research includes the following:

- Developing and testing pre-processing algorithms optimized for edge computing.
- Implementing DL-based models tailored for specific domain tasks.
- Evaluating the performance of these models on the developed datasets, mainly consisting of raw, unprocessed data. Within this context, the usage of raw data is exploited to simplify the traditional data handling chain encompassing geometrical and radiometrical corrections.
- Testing the deployment of these models on hardware currently available on space missions.

Through this studies, the intention is to bridge the gap between the theoretical capabilities of DL methods and the practical constraints imposed by space-based environments, demonstrating the feasibility of deploying such systems on current and future space missions.

1.3 Overview of the Thesis Structure

This thesis is structured to investigate the application of AI and DL techniques in resource-constrained environments, particularly in space missions. Each chapter addresses a specific domain of application, contributing to the overall goal of showcasing how AI systems can be implemented onboard spacecraft for autonomous decision-making and real-time processing. As stated above, the chapters focus on different domains, including maritime monitoring, emergency response to wildfires, and autonomous optical navigation for lunar exploration, with an emphasis on developing models that are optimized for edge computing hardware. Below is a detailed overview of the chapters and their contributions to the overarching research objectives.

Chapter 2 focuses on emergency response to wildfires, presenting a novel pre-processing technique designed to exploit multiple spectral bands without the need for computationally expensive co-registration techniques. Wildfire detection and monitoring typically rely on multispectral data, where multiple spectral bands are used to identify fire signatures. However, co-registration—the alignment of these bands—is a computationally demanding step and impractical for space-based systems with limited processing power. This chapter introduces a new approach to pre-processing multispectral data that lightens the classical co-registration, while still maintaining high detection accuracy. The wildfire detection model developed here is optimized for deployment on edge devices, ensuring that it can run in real-time with the limited computational resources available onboard spacecraft. Benchmarks of the model demonstrate its performance under various conditions, including diverse terrains and atmospheric conditions, validating its effectiveness for real-time disaster response. The chapter also presents the deployment of the model on representative hardware with flight heritage, showcasing its feasibility for space missions tasked with monitoring natural disasters such as wildfires.

Chapter 3 shifts the focus to AN in lunar exploration scenarios, presenting the development of

an optical navigation system based on lunar landmarks. AN is critical for lunar missions, where communication with ground control is often delayed or unavailable. The system developed in this chapter uses lunar landmarks to provide position and orientation data for spacecrafts. To track landmarks onboard, an DL-based model is trained on a custom developed dataset of real lunar optical images. The chapter traces the evolution of this navigation system, from initial algorithmic development to its optimization for edge computing and eventual deployment on hardware suitable for space missions. The system is designed to function autonomously, without relying on ground-based navigation support, which is crucial for long-term extraterrestrial missions. Various lunar terrains and lighting conditions were simulated to test the robustness of the system, and the results demonstrate its reliability and accuracy in providing navigation information. The chapter concludes with a discussion of the system’s deployment on spacecraft hardware, showing its potential for future lunar missions.

Chapter 4 presents research on MSA with a focus on the processing of SAR and optical data for vessel detection, wake detection, wake component identification, and ship classification. The chapter begins by introducing the datasets developed for these purposes and the techniques designed to process large-scale SAR and multi-spectral imagery. The primary aim of this chapter is to enhance vessel detection accuracy and reduce response time in real-time maritime monitoring systems. The vessel detection and classification algorithms developed in this chapter are optimized for edge computing, ensuring that they can operate on the limited hardware available on current spacecraft. Additionally, wake detection and classification techniques are presented to further improve the system’s ability to monitor vessel movement and behavior. The chapter concludes with a study on synergical exploitation of more than one satellite, showing that in the foreseeable future swarm of spacecrafts can improve maritime monitoring.

Each chapter in this thesis, drawn in Figure 1.1, contributes to the overall research objectives by demonstrating the feasibility of deploying AI-driven systems on edge hardware in space missions. Together, these chapters form a cohesive investigation into how DL can be leveraged in resource-constrained environments available onboard satellites, pushing the boundaries of what is currently possible in terms of autonomy, real-time processing, and decision-making in space-based systems.

Figure 1.1: Overview of the thesis structure, illustrating the key contributions across three chapters: wildfire detection, lunar exploration navigation, and maritime domain awareness. Each chapter highlights the deployment of AI-driven systems on edge hardware for space-based applications.

1.4 Thesis Contribution

This research makes a significant contribution to the scientific community by tackling critical challenges in maritime monitoring, wildfire response, and autonomous navigation, while also pioneering the transferability of these solutions to space exploration missions.

By advancing the operational capabilities of AI, this work pushes the frontiers of what is possible in integrating sophisticated algorithms into spacecraft systems, directly improving efficiency, autonomy, and mission success rates. The research delivers concrete outputs that were previously unavailable, including raw datasets, benchmarks on edge AI devices, proof-of-concept implementations, and system models. These contributions provide a solid foundation for developing AI-driven autonomous systems, enabling robust, real-time decision-making in remote and resource-constrained environments.

The breakthroughs in edge computing and AI techniques presented in this thesis have significant implications beyond space missions, offering robust, real-time solutions for diverse applications that require efficient, autonomous systems in remote or inaccessible environments. These advancements will drive future developments in both space and ground-based AI-driven technologies.

Chapter 2

Wildfire Reponse

This chapter discusses the role of AI onboard satellites in enhancing wildfire response, focusing on a novel real-time data processing chain for onboard deployment, raw dataset developed and deployment on representative hardware. The capabilities demonstrated can improve detection, monitoring, and mitigation of wildfires.

2.1 Introduction

2.1.1 Overview

As already stated, implementing onboard AI offers distinct advantages for disaster response, such as: reducing downlink data by discarding low-value images [16, 17]; enabling near real-time decision-making for natural disasters [1, 18–20]; and providing faster retrieval of actionable information like changes or hotspots in local areas [21]. It is worth noting that early warnings can protect critical infrastructure like power lines and oil pipelines [20, 39] from fires spreading. Additional benefits include applying data correction steps (e.g., atmospheric correction) [22] and onboard data compression [23, 24].

However, most missions still require pre-processing schemes that increase hardware complexity, as current workflows replicate ground-based processing (e.g., radiometric and geometric corrections) [20, 21, 40]. These steps, detailed in the following Section 2.1.2, are computationally expensive, and thus challenging to implement on small satellite platforms. Additionally, due to the lack of raw datasets, many works rely still on highly processed, high-level satellite products like L1C images [18, 20, 23, 24, 41]. As a result, the lack of raw datasets and the absence of methods to process them unintentionally facilitate onboard processing for higher-level products. However, this approach significantly increases computational costs in the processing workflow and introduces delays. In fact, after empirically evaluating the inference times on different hardware accelerators, including the NVIDIA Jetson Nano, Google Coral, and Myriad X.

Mateo-Garcia et al. [42] highlighted that the time overhead in the initial stages of Sentinel-2 processing—specifically Band-to-Band (B2B) alignment, radiometric calibration, and detailed coregistration—requires careful consideration. Therefore, for applications where delays in detection and communication are a crucial issue, as preventing fires from spreading, the ground-based workflow is not well-aligned with the constraints of onboard processing. To realise an efficient early-detection system, the computational complexity of the traditional processing chain must be addressed.

2.1.2 Multispectral Processing Chains for EO Missions

In missions like S-2 [43] and Landsat-8 [44], extensive post-processing is applied to multispectral pushbroom imagery to prepare the data for high-end applications. These steps typically include radiometric, geometric, and orthorectification corrections, most of which are executed at the ground segment level [45]. Given the focus of our methodology on S-2 data, this section emphasizes its processing chain. Although specific processing solutions and product nomenclature vary across missions, fundamental operations such as band coregistration, image georeferencing, and conversion of radiance to top-of-atmosphere (TOA) reflectance are common across many data processing chains [46, 47]. In the Sentinel-2 workflow, images are acquired and organized into granules, representing data collected by all sensors in a 3.6-second interval [46]. As the Figure 2.1 displays, the granules are equalized and compressed onboard before being downlinked [46]. Once on the ground, the data, defined as L0, are processed to include metadata such as geographical information and quick-look images. At this stage, the data are decompressed, and for the purposes of this paper, these decompressed granules are referred to as “raw data”.

Next, Level-1A (L1A) products are generated by applying coarse spatial coregistration of the bands. Radiometric corrections, including the reversal of onboard equalization, are then applied to produce Level-1B (L1B) products. From L1B, the L1C data are derived through geometric corrections, including sub-pixel multispectral registration and ortho-rectification, with TOA reflectance calculations. At this stage, cloud and land masks are also generated, and periodic calibration ensures the high quality of L1C products, as described in [48]. L1C products are delivered in predefined 100x100 km² tiles, and a single acquisition may partially or fully cover a specific area of interest (AOI) within a granule. As a result, multiple L1C tiles may need to be mosaicked to represent the entire AOI.

Figure 2.1: Illustration of the Sentinel-2 processing chain from satellite data to L1C data. The images in the raw and L1C format show an eruption of the Etna volcano, Italy, for the two processing levels as RGB-like images. (Source: Meoni et. al [1])

The effects of onboard equalization remain in raw data, as the inversion is only performed at the L1A level. Moreover, the lossy compression scheme used onboard [43] introduces unavoidable distortions that differentiate raw data from sensor-produced data. The products from L0 to L1B are not publicly available, while L1C and higher-level products, such as Level-2A (L2A) atmospheric-corrected and domain-specific datasets (e.g., marine ecosystem monitoring¹ and land cover assessment²), are accessible through Copernicus and European Space Agency (ESA) projects. ESA’s plans are underway to release additional raw S-2 products to the public in the upcoming years.

2.1.3 Chapter Structure

The Section 2.2 of this thesis present the developed solution employing a lightweight pre-processing scheme [1], tailored for ensuring low-latency, energy-efficient operations onboard satellites.

Building on these findings, to demonstrate the effectiveness of our proposed methodology in a real-world scenario, a dataset of raw S-2 imagery has been constructed with a focus on thermal hotspots. The Thermal Hotspots in Raw Sentinel-2 images (THRawS) dataset is reported in Section 2.3. This target application was chosen for its potential to improve early warning systems and help prevent the spread of wildfires [20, 39], thereby enhancing the safety of people in high-risk areas and protecting critical infrastructure, such as power lines and oil pipelines.

Following, in the Section 2.4 the capability of DL models to detect thermal hotspots in raw S-2 data using minimal pre-processing is examined on the developed dataset of thermal hotspots. A coarse-grained segmentation model is implemented and deployed on representative hardware. Specifically, we demonstrate real-time execution of the proposed method further demonstrating its applicability for disaster applications and emergency response.

In line with this, a software tool, Python for RAW Sentinel-2 data (PyRawS)³ has been developed. This open-source Python package streamlines the dataset creation process from raw Sentinel-2 data. This approach ensures reproducibility and extending this methodology to other multispectral raw data. Through our proposed framework, wildfire monitoring systems can be enhanced, promoting efficient onboard detection and early intervention capabilities that are essential for mitigating fire-related disasters.

2.2 Lightweight Onboard Data Handling

2.2.1 Band-to-Band Registration

In multi-spectral and hyperspectral imaging, B2B registration (or co-registration) refers to the precise alignment of different spectral bands so that each pixel across the bands corresponds to the same spatial location; this process is critical when analyzing satellite imagery. Co-registration allows avoid chromatic aberrations that can mislead or degrade models’ performance. It enables accurate pixel-by-pixel comparisons, allowing models to capture subtle spectral variations that are crucial for tasks like land use classification, vegetation monitoring, or anomaly detection of thermal hotspots. The absence of co-registration can pose significant challenges for DL-based approaches, which rely on spatial and spectral coherence to extract meaningful patterns and predictions. A Convolutional

¹<https://shorturl.at/jvGR6>; last accessed on 2023-12-19.

²https://seom.esa.int/page_project025.php; last accessed on 2023-12-19.

³PyRawS. Available online at: <https://github.com/ESA-PhiLab/PyRawS>. Last accessed on 2024-06-22.

Neural Network (CNN) extract hierarchical spatial features from images, assuming that corresponding features in multi-band data occupy the same location across bands. If the data is not properly co-registered, the learned filters may become confused, leading to suboptimal feature extraction and, consequently, poor performance in downstream tasks.

Given two generic bands B_n and B_m , the band B_n is generally shifted of a certain number of pixels $S_{B_n_{-}B_m}$ with respect to B_m . In general, it is possible assume that $S_{B_n_{-}B_m}$ is made of two components as shown in Eq. 2.1:

$$S_{B_n_{-}B_m} = \overline{S_{B_n_{-}B_m}} + \Delta S_{B_n_{-}B_m} \quad (2.1)$$

where $\overline{S_{B_n_{-}B_m}}$ is the systematic shift due to pushbroom acquisition mode and additional offset [46], whilst $\Delta S_{B_n_{-}B_m}$ is an aleatory component due to mechanical vibrations and other non-ideal effects. Spatial coregistration algorithms are generally designed to eliminate both the components of $S_{B_n_{-}B_m}$ so that the spatial displacement between B_n and B_m can be minimized [49, 50] in addition to errors in skewness, rotation, and warping [51].

Registration Techniques

Even though spectral band displacements are generally available, spacecraft dynamics and attitude compromise the accuracy of such information. A plethora of image registration techniques exist in the literature, each one exhibiting its distinct advantages and use cases. This efficacy is profoundly contingent upon the characteristics of the data under analysis. The survey of [52] recollects various methods for image registration. We can distinguish the techniques into region-based [53], moment-based [54], region and feature based [55], Fast Fourier Transform (FFT)-based [56], cross-correlation and FFT-based [49].

The first band registration system was proposed in [49] while hase correlation later became widely adopted for its robustness against noise. Nandy et al. [50] introduced EdgeReg, an edge-based algorithm with an initial filtering stage, but resulted sensitive to threshold settings. The work of [57] enhanced phase correlation to achieve sub-pixel accuracy without interpolation, reaching accuracies near 0.1 pixels. Nonetheless, these methods suffer from being susceptible to the threshold used. The paper [58] addresses this by introducing a novel gradient-based phase correlation method (GradPC), enhanced by a sub-pixel extension stage. Additionally, the paper presents an automatic scheme to determine the validity of the registration. Despite the robustness of gradient-image-based phase correlation, it faces limitations in homogenous regions that primarily consist of noise and lack helpful features. However, there has not been a sufficient assessment of the processing time needed to co-register an image, as this approach focuses on individual patches.

Due to the properties of multi-spectral imagery, feature-based methods are more suitable for registration. These techniques are superior in terms of accuracy at the expense of more demanding processing, directly depending on the number of control points used. In general, high-resolution imaging for registration demands an extensive set of control points [59]. A variety of feature identification algorithms, such as Scale-Invariant Feature Transform (SIFT) [60], Speeded-Up Robust Features (SURF) [61], Binary Robust Invariant Scalable Keypoints (BRISK) [62], and Oriented FAST and Rotated BRIEF (ORB) [63], have been scrutinized for their efficacy in the realm of image registration. SIFT stands out for its performance in control point matching [64], whereas SURF

shows efficiency in computational time [64]. Notably, ORB stands out for its quick processing and low computational overhead. These diverse methods serve as the basis for control points in experimental registration frameworks. The spectral reflectance properties of surface materials can result in significant non-linear intensity differences between satellite images of the exact location acquired at different spectral bands. Though robust to intensity changes, this non-linearity can degrade the performance of SIFT features, which are typically invariant to linear intensity changes. Notwithstanding, these methods are computationally intensive and energy-demanding. It is worth recalling that in the realm of onboard data processing, optimizing energy-efficient resources is imperative. The study titled [65] explores the trade-offs between area-based and feature-based approaches for efficient implementation on multi-GPU systems. The authors evaluate HYFM and HSI-KAZE as exemplars of area-based and feature-based methods, respectively. While HSI-KAZE outperforms HYFM in terms of registration quality across the datasets examined, it does so at the expense of being $\times 50$ times more computationally demanding in terms of GPU execution time [65].

2.2.2 Proposed Coarse Approach

To facilitate onboard processing, a lightweight and energy-efficient pre-processing algorithm was developed to compensate only the systematic shift error component $\overline{S_{B_n}_{B_m}}$ by shifting B_m of a fixed value equal to $\overline{S_{B_n}_{B_m}}$.

The technique termed as Coarse Spatial Coregistration (CSC) has been validated on S-2 raw data. As for [66], CSC uses one-time pre-calculated spatial shift values to compensate for the average spatial displacements both along and across the satellite track due to the sensor's pushbroom nature and additional sensor offsets. Thus, the developed approach does not require using ground control points nor other ancillary data. In addition, it does not require to perform keypoints extraction and matching, typical of features-based technique [60, 60–63, 65]. Besides, these shift values offer the advantages of being insusceptible from effects due to noise, attitude disturbances, or depending on the surface characteristics. However, as shown later in Table 2.1, for Sentinel-2 data $\overline{S_{B_n}_{B_m}} \gg \Delta S_{B_n}_{B_m}$, especially for the along-track component (*along-track shift*).

The statistical analysis conducted to estimate the shift values is described as follow. Let us define I the vector of band indices as:

$$I \triangleq \{02, 08, 03, 10, 04, 05, 11, 06, 07, 8A, 12, 01, 09\} \quad (2.2)$$

I is sorted according to the time delays of the various bands compared to the band B_{02} [67]. Let us consider two bands $B_{I(n)}$ and $B_{I(m)}$, with $B_{I(n)}, B_{I(m)} \in B_S$ where $B_S \triangleq [B_x, B_y, \dots, B_z]$ is the band collection of a granule that we want to register spatially. To perform the CSC, we apply a shift along and across the satellite-track $\overline{S_{B_{I(n)}}_{B_{I(m)}}}$ to the band $B_{I(n)}$ measured with respect to the resolution of $B_{I(n)}$. $\overline{S_{B_{I(n)}}_{B_{I(m)}}}$ depends only on the couple of bands $(B_{I(n)}, B_{I(m)})$, the satellite and the detector number producing that raw data.

For any coupling of satellite, detector number, and couple of bands, the value of $\overline{S_{B_{I(n)}}_{B_{I(m)}}}$ can be calculated by using the relations in Eq. 2.3:

$$\begin{cases} \overline{S_{B_{I(n)}-B_{I(m)}}} = \sum_{k=m}^n N_{I(k+1)-I(k)} \cdot \frac{R_{B_{I(k+1)}}}{R_{B_{I(n)}}}, & n > m \\ \overline{S_{B_{I(n)}-B_{I(m)}}} = -\overline{S_{B_{I(m)}-B_{I(n)}}} \cdot \frac{R_{B_{I(n)}}}{R_{B_{I(m)}}}, & n < m \end{cases} \quad (2.3)$$

where $R_{B_{I(k+1)}}$ is the resolution in m of the band $B_{I(k+1)}$, and $N_{I(k+1)-I(k)}$ is the shift to apply to the band $B_{I(k)}$ to match the band $B_{I(k+1)}$ measured with respect to the resolution of the band $B_{I(k)}$.

Given a specific coupling, the shift values $N_{I(k+1)-I(k)}$ are fixed coefficients that we estimated for each of the band couples $(B_{I(k)}, B_{I(k+1)})$ by performing a statistical analysis on raw data granules. To this aim, we ran a feature-matching method, SuperGlue [68], to extract and match keypoints in a pair of bands $(B_{I(k)}, B_{I(k+1)})$ having the same detector number and used the along-track and across-track distance between the couples of matched key-points to provide an estimation of $N_{I(k+1)-I(k)}$. More specifically, for a couple of bands $(B_{I(k)}, B_{I(k+1)})$ we proceeded as follows.

To ensure successful keypoint matching between adjacent granules, all granules that could be stacked along the satellite track have been coupled. For each along-track-stacked granule g , the band pair $(B_{I(k)-g}, B_{I(k+1)-g})$ is selected. Next, the CLAHE algorithm [69] is applied to the stacked bands $(B_{I(k)-g}, B_{I(k+1)-g})$ to enhance feature distinctiveness without introducing noise. SuperGlue was then used to extract and match keypoints in the enhanced bands, and the average along-track and across-track distance for each pair of matched keypoints was calculated. Outliers were removed ($\pm 2\sigma$), and the values were averaged to obtain $N_{I(k+1)-I(k)-g}$ for each band pair in the stacked granule g . Finally, $N_{I(k+1)-I(k)}$ was derived by averaging $N_{I(k+1)-I(k)-g}$ across all stacked granules g . This process was repeated for all the band pairs. An example of this pre-computed calculation is reported in Table 2.1, presenting the mean and standard deviation of across- and along-track offsets for the $B_{8A} - B_{11}$ spectral bands.

Table 2.1: Mean and standard deviation (along- and across-track) of offsets values for each detector of Sentinel-2 optical imagers when performing the registration of $B_{8A} - B_{11}$ spectral bands. The offset is provided in pixel values.

D	Sentinel-2A		Sentinel-2B	
	μ	σ	μ	σ
1	[-174.8, -1.93]	[1.01, 0.26]	[-178.33, -12.78]	[1.12, 0.44]
2	[188.0, -6.0]	[0.76, 0.0]	[186.83, -16.5]	[1.47, 0.55]
3	[-173.08, -2.0]	[0.79, 0.0]	[-174.77, -13.0]	[1.42, 0.0]
4	[186.0, -3.2]	[0.94, 0.42]	[183.22, -14.06]	[0.94, 0.24]
5	[-170.5, -1.88]	[0.53, 0.35]	[-172.5, -13.0]	[0.62, 0.0]
6	[184.0, -2.0]	[0.0, 0.0]	[183.0, -12.75]	[0.82, 0.5]
7	[-170.0, -1.0]	[0.0, 0.0]	[-173.0, -11.67]	[0.0, 0.58]
8	[185.56, -0.64]	[1.12, 0.49]	[184.12, -10.96]	[0.83, 0.2]
9	[-170.55, -1.73]	[1.04, 0.47]	[-172.6, -11.0]	[0.82, 0.0]
10	[187.0, 1.5]	[0.0, 0.58]	[185.13, -9.33]	[0.83, 0.49]
11	[-176.0, -0.5]	[0.0, 0.71]	[-174.88, -11.88]	[1.13, 0.35]
12	[193.0, 4.0]	[0.0, 0.0]	[189.17, -7.33]	[0.41, 0.52]

Notably, band B_{10} was found difficult to correlate with the bands B_{03} and B_{04} because of the significant difference in the spectral content. This makes the estimated values of N_{04-10} and N_{10-03} unreliable. To solve this problem, two additional coefficients N_{10-09} and N_{10-03} have been extracted

and used to invert Eq. 2.3 and provide better estimates for N_{04_10} and N_{10_03} . In this context, the extraction of N_{10_09} was possible because of the higher correlation of the spectral contents of the bands B_{10} and B_{09} . Regarding the feature matching settings, we used the Superpoint Neural Network as a feature extractor with outdoor weights as in the original implementation [68]. To increase the detection and matching capabilities, the hyper-parameters were tuned for the task, and the best ones have been reported in Pyraws source code⁴.

In particular, the matching threshold values were raised to increase the number of strongly matched keypoints, i.e., those having higher probabilities of being the same in both bands.

2.2.3 Evaluation of Coarse Co-Registration

Accuracy Performance

Regarding the accuracy of the proposed method, since the shift values are averaged from SuperGlue results, their standard deviation provides a reliable estimate of the error in the CSC proposed method. Referring to Table 2.1, 17 of 24 cases feature a subpixel error both along and across-track compared to the. In 3 cases, the coregistration error is null. The maximum along-track and across-track errors are 1.47 px and 0.71 px, respectively

The standard deviation remaining below one pixel for both directions is a trend observed consistently across all Sentinel-2 band pairs, not just $B_{8A} - B_{11}$. Additionally, the results are differentiated based on the satellite and detector number, as the offsets show a dependence on the satellite. An interesting pattern is a change in sign when transitioning from odd to even detectors, due to their inverted orientation on the satellite, resulting in opposite offset signs. The reported errors are based on shift values $N_{I(k+1)_I(k)}$, averaged from data on volcanic events acquired between 2017 and 2022. In a practical scenario, $N_{I(k+1)_I(k)}$ should be recalculated periodically for specific calibration or sensor configurations. However, in a hypothetical mission scenario, it is possible to recalculate $N_{I(k+1)_I(k)}$ periodically to optimize them towards specific calibration settings or other possible temporary sensor set-ups.

Timing Performance

This subsection compares the proposed CSC technique in terms of timing performance to SuperGlue, and other coregistration solutions including the traditional SIFT implementation [60], LightGlue [70] method, covering different feature descriptors, including Superpoint, ALIKED [71], and DISK [72]. Differently from the described CSC, these techniques are feature-based, i.e., they extract and match keypoints from the bands to be aligned enabling a fine B2B alignment. Results shown in Table 2.2 showcase the profiling of these methods. This comparison was conducted across the granules of the THRawS dataset, highlighting the practical advantages of CSC in onboard satellite processing contexts. More specifically, an experiment was set to compare the time to register 10 raw data granules. For all the aforementioned methods, the time to register the bands B_{8A}, B_{11}, B_{12} was measured. Both the methods were profiled by using PyTorch Profiler [73] both on an Intel® Xeon® Gold 6248 CPU @ 2.50GHz Central Processing Unit (CPU) and an NVIDIA A40-48C GPU to test the dependency on the time performance on the hardware device. Each test case was run three times, and time performance was measured by averaging the results on the three tests. All

⁴Pyraws matching config: <https://shortur1.at/k1JL7>; last accessed on 2023-12-19.

Table 2.2: Evaluation of timing performance for SuperGlue, LightGlue (ALIKED, DISK, SIFT, Superpoint), and traditional SIFT-based method in spatial coregistration compared to the developed CSC approach, executed on CPU (Intel® Xeon® Gold 6248 CPU @ 2.50GHz) and GPU (NVIDIA A40-48C with Driver Version 525.105.17 and CUDA Version 12.0).

Method	Average CPU [ms]	Average GPU [ms]
SuperGlue (Superpoint)	5167.45	1706.30
Lightglue (ALIKED)	5651.29	N/A
Lightglue (DISK)	7169.25	536.51
Lightglue (SIFT)	1916.15	1225.58
Lightglue (Superpoint)	6660.91	458.92
SIFT	23849.50	2189.06
CSC	16.63	1.65

the tests were performed continuously with 15 warm-up cycles at the beginning of the test series with one raw data granule.

Concerning the CSC, precalculated shifts were stored in memory before running the tests to reduce the overhead time due to the storage memory access. On both devices, all the methods show a linear increment of the time to perform the band registration with the number of images. In general, on both CPU and GPU, our method outperforms the other feature-matching techniques. In particular, for a single granule with bands B_{8A}, B_{11}, B_{12} our methodology requires 17ms and 1.65 ms on CPU and GPU, respectively.

2.2.4 Coarse Geo-Referencing

A Coarse Georeferencing (CG) scheme optimized for onboard satellite applications has been developed in this study. It is based on the fixed band-to-band values used for the CSC, which are applied to the granule corner coordinates to determine the coordinates of each bands corners. This approach allows for the efficient georeferencing of each point within a band, balancing efficiency and accuracy.

Although the following methodology was applied only to band B_{8A} , it is general. Therefore, a description is provided for a generic band $B_k \in B_S$.

The process is initiated by extracting the coordinates of the four corners of a granule, which constitute essential ancillary information provided in the metadata of the Sentinel-2 raw product. Referring to the Figure 2.2, we define two key variables for our methodology. The first, Prior Coordinates (PC), represents the initial two corner coordinates scanned by the pushbroom system. The second, Afterward Coordinates (AC), denotes the final two corner coordinates scanned. Given the known location of Prior Coordinates for band B02 (PC_{B02}), the method we have devised utilises the coarsely estimated offsets $S_{B_k_{-}B02}$ from this reference band to determine the Prior Coordinates PC_{B_k} for any arbitrary band B_k .

For a band B_k , we can estimate the offsets from the reference band using the following equation:

$$PC_{B_k} = PC_{B02} + |S_{B_k_{-}B02}| \cdot \frac{R_{B_k}}{R_{B02}} \cdot \frac{AC_{B09}}{G_L} \quad (2.4)$$

Here, $S_{B_k_{-}B02}$ represents the shift value between band B_k and the reference band B02, AC_{B09} is the Afterward Coordinate of band B09, G_L is the granule length. Essential to note is that, given the variations in spatial resolution between bands, the shift values are scaled specifically for each

Figure 2.2: Pictorial view of a granule with Prior and Afterwards coordinates

band with the resolution scale factor $\frac{R_{B_k}}{R_{B_{02}}}$, where R_{B_k} and $R_{B_{02}}$ are the spatial resolutions of band B_k and B_{02} , respectively. This equation allows us to calculate the Prior Coordinates for each band, facilitating the process of band georeferencing.

The Afterward coordinates are, instead, prompted using ancillary information by applying the following linear proportion:

$$G_L : B_{l_k} = G_a : \Delta_{B_k} \quad (2.5)$$

where

- G_a is the granule length expressed in arc of latitude/longitude, prompted from the polygon coordinates at positions 0 and 1 of the granule (Figure 2.2);
- B_{l_k} is the length of the k band expressed in px;

Solving the proportion in Equation 2.5 gives the offset Δ_{B_k} referred to a generic k band as:

$$\Delta_{B_k} = \frac{B_{l_k} \cdot G_a}{G_l} \quad (2.6)$$

In the end, the AC can be calculated as:

$$AC_{B_k} = PC_{B_k} + \Delta_{B_k} \quad (2.7)$$

The set of AC and PC enables the coarse georeferencing of each pixel within the k spectral band.

2.3 The THRAWS Dataset

2.3.1 Data Acquisition

The THRawS dataset was meticulously designed to advance the detection of volcanic eruptions and wildfire events using raw Sentinel-2 data [1]. The dataset’s development process began by identifying event timeframes and locations through established databases and sources. Specifically, for volcanic eruptions, the Smithsonian Institution’s Global Volcanism Program database [74] was used to select significant eruptions with a Volcanic Explosive Index (VEI) greater than 1, focusing on events that occurred between the launch of Sentinel-2A in 2016 and 2022. To ensure a geographically diverse dataset, we sampled eruptions from various latitudes and seasons, and up to three events were chosen for each eruption. In cases where the raw data granules contained previously unidentified volcanic hotspots, additional data points were included beyond the initial selection, highlighting the dataset’s robustness and flexibility. For shorter-duration eruptions (lasting days to months), data acquisitions were timed as close as possible to the eruption’s onset to evaluate the system’s early detection capabilities.

Wildfire detection, a more complex task due to the rapid and unpredictable nature of fires, was approached differently. Fire events were identified using data from the Copernicus Emergency Management System and real-time detection services, such as NASA’s FIRMS platform, which tracks active fires globally. These events were further supplemented by information from environmental agencies and satellite observations. As with volcanic eruptions, each fire event was visually inspected at the L1C level to verify the presence of a visible fire front or smoke plume. A balanced approach was maintained in the dataset by ensuring that the number of wildfire and volcanic eruption events was approximately equal, making THRawS a comprehensive resource for detecting thermal anomalies in both types of natural disasters.

The THRawS dataset also emphasizes the importance of hard negatives—granules that do not contain thermal hotspots—introduced to optimize model performance and reduce false positives. These not-event granules were carefully selected through manual inspection to ensure the absence of any thermal anomalies, such as volcanic hotspots or firefronts, thus providing a stronger foundation for training machine learning models to differentiate between real and false signals.

The dataset includes both raw and L1C Sentinel-2 data, which were processed using spatial coregistration techniques to account for sensor misalignments inherent in satellite pushbroom acquisition. This coregistration step was crucial for aligning multispectral bands like B_{8A} , B_{11} , and B_{12} , which are instrumental in detecting thermal hotspots. By using *PyRawS*, the simplified coarse coregistration technique was systematically applied, compensating only for systematic shift errors, making the process more lightweight and feasible for onboard satellite applications, where computational resources are often limited. The use of these bands follows the thermal anomaly detection algorithm proposed by Massimetti et al. [75], which applies logical conditions to identify thermal anomalies based on band reflectance ratios.

THRawS stands out as an invaluable resource for advancing onboard satellite processing of natural disaster events, particularly wildfires and volcanic eruptions. By providing both raw and processed data, the dataset fosters research into energy-efficient, real-time detection systems that could be implemented directly on satellite platforms. This capability is critical for improving the timeliness of disaster response, helping to mitigate the impact of events like wildfires and volcanic eruptions on

vulnerable populations and critical infrastructure, such as power lines and pipelines. The integration of real-time event detection with minimal pre-processing makes THRawS a pioneering dataset that pushes the boundaries of satellite-based Earth observation.

2.3.2 Dataset Composition

As detailed in the Table 2.3, the dataset includes 88 thermal hotspot events, divided into 58 volcanic eruptions, 20 wildfire events, and 10 “not-event” instances. These events correspond to 146 granules covering the Area Of Interest (AOI) of an event: 135 of which contain thermal anomalies, while the remaining 11 serve as negative samples (granules depicting volcanic regions without thermal hotspots). In total, THRawS consists of 905 granules, with 707 granules discarded after rigorous screening. This balance of positive and negative samples allows researchers to test machine learning models’ ability to distinguish between events and non-events, enhancing model generalization.

Each granule in THRawS spans a spatial resolution of 1152×1296 pixels for the three primary bands (B_{8A} , B_{11} , B_{12}). To fit the requirements of edge devices, THRawS implements a patchification process, which divides the granules into smaller patches. However, patch decomposition introduces an inherent class imbalance between thermal hotspots and non-hotspots. Techniques such as upsampling of the thermal hotspot class or downsampling of non-events can mitigate this issue, improving the model’s ability to detect rare but significant events.

Geographic and Temporal Coverage THRawS boasts a geographically diverse dataset, with volcanic eruptions primarily located in regions like Central and South America, Africa, Southeast Asia (including Indonesia and the Philippines), and European islands (e.g., Sicily and Iceland). Wildfire events are concentrated in Europe, Australia, Africa, and the Americas. The thermal anomalies span almost every continent, providing near-global coverage, except for North America, continental Asia, and Antarctica. The dataset is particularly relevant for remote areas prone to wildfires and volcanic activity, though additional data might be needed for urban applications.

The temporal coverage of THRawS ranges from January 2017 to June 2022, capturing a broad spectrum of events from the early years of the Sentinel-2 mission. Volcanic events are represented across various stages of eruption, from initial to advanced phases, offering valuable data for early detection studies. Wildfire events, typically occurring in the afternoon during the dry season, are captured when fires are at their most severe, providing a representative sample of high-intensity fire events.

Data Labeling and Validation The dataset underwent a rigorous validation process, ensuring the quality and accuracy of thermal hotspot annotations. Each event was initially identified using

Table 2.3: Number of events, useful granules, and discarded granules in the dataset.

Product/event	Eruptions	Fire	Not-event
raw products	58	20	10
raw useful granules	135		11
Total raw useful granules		146	
Discarded granules		707	
Total number of raw granules		905	

existing databases, such as the Smithsonian Institution’s volcano database for eruptions [74] and the Copernicus Emergency Management System for wildfires. These events were visually inspected at the L1C level, followed by manual cross-validation by two independent experts to confirm the presence of thermal anomalies.

The dataset employs a well-established detection algorithm by Massimetti et al. [75], which uses reflectance ratios from the B_{8A} , B_{11} , and B_{12} bands to identify thermal hotspots. This algorithm does not distinguish between different types of thermal anomalies (e.g., volcanic eruptions vs. wildfires), but for the purposes of THRawS, this lack of differentiation was not considered a limitation, as the goal is to provide a general dataset for thermal anomaly detection. To spot thermal hotspots on L1C data, as for the original implementation of Massimetti et al. [75], we derived a hotmap containing candidate anomalies fulfilling four logical conditions that are calculated by applying fixed thresholds on the ratios of TOA reflectance of the different bands. More specifically, as in the original work [75], the logical equation to activate a pixel p in the hotmap is:

$$p = \alpha \oplus \beta \oplus S \oplus \gamma \quad (2.8)$$

where \oplus is the logical sum between the logical conditions α , β , S , and γ . The latter are calculated as a function of the TOA reflectance values of the bands B_{8A} , B_{11} , B_{12} (ρ_{8A} , ρ_{11} , ρ_{12}) as follows:

$$\begin{cases} \alpha = (\frac{\rho_{12}}{\rho_{11}} \geq 1.4) \otimes (\frac{\rho_{12}}{\rho_{8A}} \geq 1.2) \otimes (\rho_{12} \geq 0.15) \\ \beta = (\frac{\rho_{11}}{\rho_{8A}} \geq 2) \otimes (\rho_{11} \geq 0.5) \otimes (\rho_{12} \geq 0.5) \\ SR \triangleq SUR\{\alpha \oplus \beta\} \\ S = (\rho_{12} \geq 1.2) \otimes (\rho_{8A} \leq 1) \oplus (\rho_{11} \geq 1.5) \otimes (\rho_{8A} \geq 1) \\ \gamma = (\rho_{12} \geq 1) \otimes (\rho_{11} \geq 1) \otimes (\rho_{8A} \geq 0.5) \otimes SR \end{cases} \quad (2.9)$$

where $SUR\{\}$ and \otimes are respectively the surrounding and the logical and operation.

Then, a bounding box was extracted for every cluster of pixels in the hotmap using *scikit-image* [76]. Finally, to minimize the false detection rate, we filtered those bounding boxes surrounding a number of active pixels in the hotmap lower than 9 to discard small clusters of pixels as suggested in [75]. After extracting the bounding boxes on the mosaicked and cropped L1C tiles, we reprojected them on the raw products using an affine transformation and manual tuning. Indeed, it is essential to note that the bounding boxes extracted from the L1C products cannot be straightforwardly used for the raw data due to their different projections. While the raw products are represented in azimuth-range coordinates (*EPSG* : 4326), L1C products are in latitude-longitude projected in the *WGS84* system. A further issue is added by the geometrical correction applied to the L1C images, in which a resampling using a 90m DEM (PlanetDEM 90)⁵ is employed. In order to exploit the L1C bounding boxes, we warped the points from the L1C to the raw coordinates with an affine transformation. We defined the transformation matrix from L1C to raw coordinates using the coordinates of three corner points. After applying the correction, our results showed that there still exists a discrepancy between the bounding box and the actual event in several cases. In order to rectify the issue, we manually tuned the bounding boxes for eruptions and created a buffer for fire events. Finally, we performed a visual inspection. An example of applications of the different methodology steps by

⁵Reference Document: GMES-GSEG-EOPG-TN-09-0029 (v2.3)

Figure 2.3: Each row shows all the processing steps for the bands B_{8A} , B_{11} , B_{12} of the various raw data granules: the first image from left of each row displays the raw data granule, the second image shows a spatially registered granule, the third image shows the correspondent L1C tiles cropped on the coordinates of first band of the raw data granule band collection with the detected bounding boxes, and the rightmost image showcases the bounding boxes warped on the raw data granules.

using *PyRawS* on raw granules and L1C data of THRawS are depicted in Figure 2.3.

Errors in bounding box warping between L1C and raw granules were manually corrected to ensure high accuracy. This ensures that the dataset is reliable and ready for deployment in machine learning models, with minimal risk of false positives or labeling errors.

In summary, THRawS represents the first effort of realising a raw dataset marking a significant leap forward in creating datasets tailored for onboard satellite processing. With its diverse geographical and temporal coverage, careful balance of event and not-event samples, and emphasis on lightweight processing techniques, THRawS is an ideal resource for researchers aiming to develop and test ML models for real-time thermal anomaly detection onboard. Whether applied to volcanic eruptions, wildfires, or other high-risk thermal hotspots, THRawS provides a solid foundation for improving disaster response capabilities through advanced satellite-based Earth observation technologies.

2.4 Onboard Proof-of-Concept

As stated above, the method is demonstrated on the THRawS dataset. Specifically, the pipeline takes as input Sentinel-2 raw granules, selecting the B_{8A} , B_{11} , and B_{12} bands—the standard bands utilised by numerous previous works to detect thermal anomalies [1, 75, 77–81].

2.4.1 End-to-End Processing Chain

As suggested by the name “end-to-end”, the proposed concept is a payload data processing chain that leverages a CNN model to create a thermal hotspot event binary classification map (event/non-event) of multispectral or hyperspectral pushbroom data acquisitions directly with minimal pre-processing steps. The idea behind this approach is minimising the pre-processing steps applied on board a satellite by training CNN models on minimally processed raw data. This way, it is possible to speed up the processing and reduce the energy consumption significantly.

The proposed E2E processing chain is depicted in Fig 2.4 and comprises three main components: a CSC module, a raster-tiling engine, and a sequential patch inference module.

Figure 2.4: Developed E2E pipeline for onboard thermal hotspot heatmap classification of Sentinel-2’s raw data.

In the following, each module will be examined in detail to elucidate the rationale behind its incorporation into the processing pipeline.

1. **Coarse Coregistration Module:** Given the pushbroom nature of Sentinel-2 or other pushbroom detectors, spectral bands are not natively overlapped, namely spatially registered. Non-coregistered bands can lead to inaccuracies in techniques that rely on pixel-wise information from multiple spectral bands. Therefore, in the context of thermal hotspot detection, it is essential to coregister these bands accurately for precise and reliable interpretation of the data. Generally speaking, the process of coregistration can be divided into two distinct stages: a coarse coregistration, aiming for an accuracy of approximately 1 pixel, and a fine coregistration applied to determine any residual transformation that might be needed. The first stage sets the foundational alignment of the bands. In contrast, the second one involves formulating and applying transformation equations, representing the most intensive computational part of the registration process. In our study, we concentrate only on the first kind of coregistration, prioritizing achieving a general approximate level of alignment. This approach is based on the generalizability of Deep Learning in addressing small misalignment errors [82]. For these reasons, we adopt the CSC technique proposed in our previous work [1] that consists of applying a set of precalculated along-track and across-track shifts $\overline{S_{B_{11}_B_{8A}}}$ and $\overline{S_{B_{12}_B_{8A}}}$ to respectively align the B_{11} and B_{12} bands to the reference band B_{8A} . Such shifts $\overline{S_{B_x_B_y}}$ were calculated by measuring the average along-track and across-track displacements

between the bands B_x and B_y of raw granules of the THRawS dataset. In each granule, such displacements were measured as the average distance in pixels of the keypoints extracted and matched through the SuperGlue neural network [68].

2. **Raster tiling Engine:** After selecting the B_{8A}, B_{11}, B_{12} bands, the Sentinel-2 granule—which is $1152px \times 1296px$ wide—is tiled into $256px \times 256px$ patches. This is needed to match onboard hardware’s memory requirements and distinguish between local features [16, 83, 84]. Notably, the raster tiling operation is performed with no overlap between consecutive patches.
3. **Sequential Patch Inference Module:** The sequential patch inference module operates by taking the tiles created by the patch engine module as input. Each tile is singularly classified by the CNN into thermal-hotspot event/non-event. The outputs for different patches are sequentially collected in a binary classification map, a matrix whose elements contain the assigned labels for each analysed patch. This targeted approach is particularly advantageous for maintaining significant dimensions of each tile. It is worth noting that the ability to preserve tile dimensions ensures that these small yet critical events are not overlooked or inadequately processed, thereby improving the overall accuracy and robustness of the model. This enhancement is especially convenient when dealing with small-scale fires. The adopted CNN model is an EfficientNet-lite0, which represents an optimized version of the original EfficientNet model [85] for implementations on embedded systems. The choice of the CNN model was driven by the need to reach high classification performance while keeping the number of floating point operations and model size limited because of the need to reach a real-time implementation. The efficacy of EfficientNet models for classification purposes on Sentinel-2 images was already demonstrated in our previous work MSMatch [86] work. The latter also shows a comparison in performances of the different EfficientNet models (i.e., EfficientNet-B0 - EfficientNet-B7), demonstrating how the use of more computationally expensive models compared to EfficientNet-B0 leads to a slight increase in classification accuracy at the expenses of a significantly higher number of operations. Because of that, we selected the correspondent lite version of EfficientNet-B0, i.e., EfficientNet-lite0, to minimize the number of floating-point operations. Notably, the effectiveness of EfficientNet-lite0 models for onboard satellite classification was already demonstrated in the scope of “The OPS-SAT case” challenge in-orbit test campaign [84].

2.4.2 Dataset Compiled

In order to train our classification model, we needed a dataset specifically designed for thermal hotspot classification. Mainly for this reason, we modified the data from THRawS [1] to suit the requirements of patch classification. THRawS is made of Sentinel-2 raw granules containing volcanic eruptions and wildfires. In each raw granule, thermal hotspots are marked through a bounding box that allows for their localisation inside the granule.

To create our patch classification dataset, we first selected the bands $B_{8A}, B_{11},$ and B_{12} of each raw granule as proposed for the THRawS dataset. Subsequently, to train a model with the same input as for the E2E pipeline, we applied the CSC technique and tiled the registered bands into $256px \times 256px$ patches. This tiling was performed with a deliberate overlap of 10%, ensuring that contiguous areas are not missed and allowing for a more comprehensive analysis of the granules.

Upon completion, the dataset was substantial, comprising over 5000 samples, resulting in a wide-ranging and extensive collection of data. Concerning data labelling, we implemented a categorization system for the analyzed patches based on thermal hotspots, whose bounding boxes are provided in THRawS, on the cropped patches. Specifically, we designated any patch encompassing a minimum of 9 pixels exhibiting these hotspots as an “event” class. The threshold was set empirically to identify areas with significant thermal irregularities. Conversely, patches that did not meet this criterion, lacking the specified extent of thermal hotspots, were systematically marked as “non-events”. This distinction allowed us to differentiate between areas of potential interest and those with normal thermal patterns, facilitating a more focused analysis of thermal irregularities in our data. After tiling, patches were visually inspected to avoid errors in the labeling procedure.

As compiled in this manner, the dataset demonstrates a significant imbalance in its composition, reflecting a notable disproportion in the representation of its classes. Out of the total number of patches analyzed, 4,636 were categorized as “non-events”, overshadowing the mere 394 patches identified as “events”. This latter group constitutes only 7.83% of the entire dataset. Such a disparity in distribution between event and non-event patches highlights a significant imbalance, indicating a predominant prevalence of non-event occurrences within the dataset. This skewness in data could have implications for further analysis, affecting our choices in terms of the training strategy adopted and metrics used to evaluate the classification performance of our CNN model.

After creating our patch classification dataset, we statically split it into train and test by using 90% and 10% splits. We used stratified sampling to keep the exact percentages of the event and non-event classes in the train and test datasets. However, during the stratification sampling process, we split the dataset using a geographical split criterion instead of performing random sampling. This means that all the patches related to a specific dataset location were placed exclusively in the train or the test partition. The idea of such a choice is to avoid data leakages between train and test due to possible spatial similarities of patches with the exact locations that could lead to overestimating the model performances [84]. After tiling, patches were visually inspected to avoid errors in the labeling procedure. The total number of patches in the train and test partitions is 4502 and 531, respectively. During the model training, the train partition is split at runtime into Train and Cross-Validation (CV) with 90% and 10% split ratio by using a random geographically split logic. In particular, we first selected a desired Cross-split ratio (δ_{sr}) (e.g., 10%), which fixes the maximum number of CV patches and a value to be used as an initial seed for the next random assignment operations. Then, we create a dictionary containing the name of a location (key) and the corresponding number of patches (value) for partitioning all the volcano, fire, and non-event patches in the training dataset. After randomly shuffling the location names in the dictionaries, we pick the following location for volcano events and assign all the corresponding patches to the CV split. If the number of patches assigned to the CV partition is lower than the maximum, we perform the same step for fire events. In this way, both the CV and the Train partitions will have wildfire and volcanic eruption events. We continue iteratively until the number of CV patches is greater or equal to the maximum; the remainder is assigned to the Train partition. The total number in the CV split is generally overestimated by proceeding this way. Therefore, we calculate the actual split ratio (α_{sr}) and compare it to the desired one. If $|\alpha_{sr} - \delta_{sr}| < 0.01 \cdot \delta_{sr}$, we accept the performed split. On the contrary, if that condition is not met, we choose another seed so that the random shuffling of the locations will lead to different results, and the split will be performed again. Using a runtime

random assignment of the locations, it is possible to test the effect of the different splits in the Train/CV partitions on the final model performance while keeping the advantages of geographical splitting. Table 2.4 shows the number of patches for the different sets and classes.

Table 2.4: Thermal hotspots dataset overview

Description	Count	% of Total Dataset
Event Patches	394	7.83%
Non-Event Patches	4636	92.17%
Total Patches	5033	100%
Train-Validation	Event (360), Non-Event (4142)	89.45%
Test	Event (34), Non-Event (497)	10%

2.4.3 Training Strategies

Since both the train and the test datasets are unbalanced, using accuracy as a classification metric is not advisable [87]. Therefore, we opted for MCC as the metric to evaluate and compare our trained models, which already found numerous applications for assessing binary classification problems on unbalanced datasets [87–89]. The MCC can be calculated as shown in Eq. 2.10 [89]:

$$MCC \triangleq \frac{T_N \cdot T_P - F_P \cdot F_N}{\sqrt{(T_P + F_P)(T_P + F_N)(T_N + F_N)(T_N + F_P)}} \quad (2.10)$$

where T_P , T_N , F_P , and F_N are, respectively, the total number of True Positives, the total number of True Negatives, the total number of False Positives, and the total number of False Negatives. Since in our dataset, the total number of events is much smaller than the number of non-events, one model predicting all the patches as non-event would have an accuracy roughly of 93.6% on the test set but an MCC of 0, which represents a random prediction. Because of that, MCC represents a valid alternative to scoring the capability of a trained model to predict both event and non-event patches correctly.

However, to partially fix the problem of class unbalance, during training, we upsampled the “event” class of a factor N_{UPS} by presenting the same patch multiple times after applying a random light augmentation. This allowed us to balance the dataset classes partially. In particular, we tested different values of $N_{UPS} \in \{2, 3, 4, 6, 7\}$. We repeated the training for five seeds (i.e., 0, 9, 14, 18, 19) for each value to make a robust performance assessment.

After training, we picked the model featuring the best MCC value on the cross-validation dataset for each of these sets of hyperparameters.

We trained our model using different training strategies, i.e., supervised and MSMatch. We used an EfficientNet-lite0 model pre-trained on ImageNet [90] for both training strategies. To train the models with supervised learning, we applied the weak augmentations included in the MSMatch pipeline [86], i.e., image translations by up to 12.5% and horizontal flips.

The training was performed using stochastic gradient descent with a momentum of 0.9 and weight decay of 0.00075, with an initial learning rate of 0.03. Furthermore, we used a batch size of 8 patches. During training, the CV dataset was evaluated with an exponential moving average with a momentum of 0.999. We noticed that the training process failed for specific combinations of N_{UPS} and seeds, leading the model under training to predict *non-event* for all the possible inputs. We

supposed this problem to be linked to the significant imbalances in the training class. Therefore, we added the following weighting factors to the loss function for each class:

$$\begin{cases} W_E = \frac{4636}{N_{UPS} \cdot 5033} \\ W_{NE} = \frac{397 \cdot N_{UPS}}{5033} \end{cases} \quad (2.11)$$

where w_E and w_{NE} are, respectively, the weighting factors for the event and non-event class. As one can see, when $N_{UPS} = 1$, w_E and w_{NE} weight errors in the loss function proportionally to the inverse of their population percentages in the dataset. When $N_{UPS} \neq 1$, w_E and w_{NE} are scaled to compensate for the effect of the event class upsampling.

Compared to the original work [86], as for supervised learning, we modified the pipeline by adding the ‘‘event’’ class upsampling. After the upsampling, we used 400 samples per class as labelled examples, while the rest were used as unlabelled ones. In addition, compared to the MSMatch pipeline, we did not apply channel normalization. As stated, we used the same setup for the hyperparameters shared with supervised learning. Furthermore, for each of the eight labelled examples in the batch, we used four unlabelled examples (i.e., unlabeled-ratio of 4) and a pseudo-label cutoff threshold of 0.95.

2.4.4 Training Results

The current overview of Table 2.5 aims to illustrate the model’s performance across various training strategies, thereby providing a comprehensive demonstration of its general capabilities.

Indeed, under the previously outlined methodology, we conduct a rigorous benchmarking analysis on the model trained to utilize three distinct approaches, namely MSMatch, Supervised Unweighted and Supervised Weighted. Based on the observations depicted in Table 2.5, each graph illustrates the outcomes obtained from five distinct seeds (0, 9, 14, 18, 19), signifying various model initializations across a range of five distinct upsampling factors (2, 3, 4, 6, 7). Such results were obtained by testing the trained models on the test dataset.

Concerning the MSMatch training (Table 2.5), the range of MCC values spans from -0.2121 to 0.8864. Predominantly, the results showcase positive values, suggesting a reasonable prediction accuracy across most of the setups. However, a significant outlier is observed with the negative MCC value of -0.2121 for the combination of seed 14 and an upsampling factor of 2. This particular result is concerning as it indicates a lack of predictive accuracy and a possible inversion in prediction,

Table 2.5: Comprehensive evaluation of MCC across different training techniques: MSMatch training, weighted supervised training, and unweighted supervised training, calculated for different upsampling factor values (2,3,4,6,7) and seeds (0,9,14,18,19).

	MSMatch Training					Weighted Supervised Training					Unweighted Supervised Training				
	2	3	4	6	7	2	3	4	6	7	2	3	4	6	7
0	0.836	0.788	0.839	0.812	0.750	0.795	0.750	0.805	0.793	0.793	0.830	0.788	0.756	0.825	0.812
9	0.886	0.851	0.858	0.526	0.868	0.722	0.869	0.886	0.807	0.871	0.000	0.833	0.774	0.821	0.795
14	-0.212	0.705	0.504	0.812	0.843	0.716	0.817	0.716	0.857	0.902	0.786	0.832	0.871	0.871	0.832
18	0.869	0.839	0.664	0.871	0.805	0.812	0.886	0.830	0.857	0.819	0.000	0.902	0.807	0.854	0.854
19	0.758	0.836	0.793	0.812	0.825	0.000	0.774	0.756	0.830	0.815	0.750	0.851	0.805	0.768	0.833

where the model may be consistently incorrect. This could point to a potential issue in the model’s training process or a specific anomaly in the data for this configuration.

The MCC values in the unweighted supervised training (Table 2.5) vary from 0.0 to 0.902. There are predominantly positive values, indicating effective model performance in most scenarios. However, for both seed 18 and seed 9 with $N_{UPS} = 2$, the trained model predicts *non-event* for any input patch, which leads to an MCC of 0.0. Nevertheless, as shown in 2.5, the proposed weighting strategy is effective in removing such for seeds 9 and 18, leading to positive MCC values. A null MCC is found for seed 19 for $N_{UPS} = 2$ when using the weighted training strategy. It is interesting that negative or null MCC values are found only for $N_{UPS} = 2$ for all the different training strategies. That remarks the need for upsampling the underrepresented *event* class during training.

Since our goal is to train the model for any seed successfully and not to compare different training techniques to characterize our models’ performance, we picked the best model obtained for each combination of (N_{UPS} , seed) listed in Table 2.5 among the three training strategies, and we averaged them among the seed values. The obtained results, listed for different N_{UPS} values, are displayed in Table 2.6. Such results, displayed in Table 2.6, range from 0.780 to 0.854 for N_{UPS} and show an increasing trend for growing values of N_{UPS} .

The Figure 2.5 showcases the classification masks produced by the E2E pipeline on three different raw granules when the best model is used (MCC = 0.902). The classification mask produced for the first granule, correspondent to a wildfire acquired in Australia (coordinates (lat= -29.92° , lon= 152.34°) in 2019, underlines the capability of the trained to detect events much smaller than the patch size and partially affected by registration errors due to the coarse spatial registration technique used. This fact seems to remark on the findings by Fanizze et al. [82], which states that the robustness of the model to registration errors can be increased by including misregistered patches during training.

Table 2.6: Average MCC results over different training seeds for different upsampling factor values (2, 3, 4, 6, 7). The results were achieved by averaging, over the seeds, the best value for each (N_{UPS} , seed) combination among the three training strategies.

	N_{UPS}				
	2	3	4	6	7
MCC	0.780	0.848	0.839	0.841	0.854

2.4.5 Power consumption and latency results

Experimental Set-Up

We created a breadboard implementation on target edge computing hardware to measure the timing and energy performance that E2E can attain. In particular, we compared three test setups leveraging different hardware chains:

- **E2E pipeline on Raspberry Pi 4 only.** The full E2E pipeline is performed on a Raspberry PI device, which was chosen due to its broad use in CubeSat missions [91–93]. Specifically, we used a Raspberry PI 4 equipped with 4 GB of Random Access Memory.

Figure 2.5: Classification masks for three different raw granules produced by the E2E pipeline when the best model ($MCC = 0.902$) is used. Patches classified as *event* are marked in red.

- **E2E pipeline on Raspberry Pi 4 and a NCS 2⁶.** In this setup, the CSC and raster-tiling operations are implemented on the Raspberry Pi 4 CPU, while the inference of the CNN is offloaded to a NCS 2, which is connected to the Raspberry PI CPU through a USB cable. Differently from a Raspberry PI4, which is a general-purpose CPU, the NCS 2 is a processing device specifically tailored for ML applications. Specifically, it is equipped with an Intel[®] Movidius[™] Myriad[™] X Vision Processing Unit (VPU), a 16 nm AI processor featuring 16 Very Long Instruction Word Streaming Hybrid Architecture Vector Engine (SHAVE) processors, 2 Neural Compute Engines specific for neural network executions and high throughput intelligent memory fabric to reach up to 4 Trillion Operations per second with a maximum power consumption of 1.5 W [94]⁷. Because of that, this setup is supposed to outperform the first scenario in terms of timing and energy-performance at the expenses of an increased hardware complexity. The NCS2 enables quick iterations and is readily available to consumers but is not space grade. This benchmark shows the relevance of testing on NCS 2 for space

⁶Intel[®] Neural Compute Stick 2 (Intel[®] NCS2): <https://www.intel.com/content/www/us/en/developer/articles/tool/neural-compute-stick.html>. Last accessed on 21/03/2024.

⁷Intel[®] Movidius[™] Myriad[™] X Vision Processing Unit: <https://www.intel.com/content/www/us/en/products/details/processors/movidius-vpu/movidius-myriad-x/products.html>. Last accessed on 21/03/2024.

applications and characterises the delta between actual space hardware and this Commercial Off-The-Shelf NCS2.

- **E2E pipeline on Raspberry Pi 4 and a Ubotica CogniSat-XE2 board.** In this experimental configuration, the CNN model is inferred on the CogniSat-XE2⁸. Similar to the NCS 2, the CogniSAT-XE2 board incorporates a Myriad X VPU. However, differently from the NCS 2, it is specifically designed to accelerate the inference of ML models on CubeSat payloads. It has been successfully deployed in the context of the CogniSat-6 mission [95]. Consequently, this setup provides a lower reality gap solution than the setup using the NCS2.

For all the configurations, we utilised the CNN model with $seed = 18$ and $N_{UPS} = 18$, which showcases the best MCC performance on the test set $MCC = 0.902$. Specifically, to comply with the Myriad X-supported arithmetics, we quantized the trained model via post-training quantization using 16-bit Floating Point (FLOAT16). Indeed, although the INT8 arithmetic could have further improved energy and timing performance, we opted for a floating point format to minimize the implementation loss due to quantization. This choice is also supported by the fact that FLOAT16 is sufficient to achieve real-time performance with no need for further optimization in terms of energy and timing performance. To make a fair comparison, the FLOAT16 quantized model was also used for the setup relying only on Raspberry PI.

For the setups using the NCS2 and CogniSat-XE2 board, the quantized model was then compiled by using *OpenVINO v2022.1* before deployment.

The Siglent SPD3303X Programmable DC Power Supply was used to measure the power consumption during the inference. Timing measurements were performed using *time* Python libraries and recorded on the Raspberry Pi. The full test setup leveraging the CogniSat-XE2 board is shown in Figure 2.6.

Benchmarks

The experiments were conducted using three granules for 256 iterations, particularly examining a Raspberry Pi + CogniSat-XE2 setup with 1 and 2 executors. An executor is a firmware mechanism that interacts with SHAVE processors to parallelize neural network inferences, either by running two instances of the same model or two different models. This setup typically enhances execution time but introduces minor synchronization overhead.

Raspberry Pi 4 The execution of the Raspberry Pi 4 was carried out to establish a baseline and investigate the possibility of running the proposed E2E chain in real time on satellite hardware.

The whole execution took 16.2 s per granule on average, while the execution had a peak power consumption of 6.2 W and a mean power consumption of 5.3 W. Notably, this configuration does not enable the execution of our pipeline in real-time since the processing time is significantly higher than the acquisition time.

Figure 2.7 depicts the power consumption evolution during the whole process (in yellow) and compares it with the consumption of the system in idle mode in similar circumstances.

⁸Cognisat-XE2 : <https://ubotica.com/product/cognisat-xe2-product-overview/>. Last accessed on 21/03/2024.

Figure 2.6: Test setup. Shown are the Siglent SPD3303X Programmable DC Power Supply, the Raspberry Pi 4, and the CogniSat-XE2 board. (The monitor, keyboard and mouse attached to the Raspberry Pi are not shown)

Raspberry Pi 4 & NCS2 Adding the NCS2 to the setup allows reducing the computational time to 1.6 s per granule, allowing real-time execution. Moreover, the execution had a peak power consumption of 6.6 W and a mean power consumption of 5.5 W.

Figure 2.8 depicts the power consumption evolution during the whole process (in yellow) and compares it with the consumption of the system in idle mode in similar circumstances. It is worth noting that the initial low consumption of the system is due to the initial steps to set up and run the NCS2 device without performing inference.

Raspberry Pi + CogniSat-XE2 The setup with CogniSat-XE2 tested two configurations using 1 and 2 executors. Pre-processing on the Raspberry Pi took 0.7 s, and with one executor, inference time per granule was 2.0 s, allowing real-time execution. Average and peak power consumption for the whole system were 5.8 W and 6.4 W, respectively, as shown in Figure 2.9.

Comparisons The Table 2.7 compares the performance of several hardware setups in terms of power consumption (average and peak power) and computational efficiency (mean running time per

Figure 2.7: Graph displaying the Raspberry Pi 4 power consumption over time, with blue indicating idle and yellow for execution consumption. Horizontal lines represent average values, showing 5.27W during execution and 2.73W in idle state.

Figure 2.8: Graph displaying the Raspberry Pi 4 + NCS2’s power consumption over time, with blue indicating idle and yellow for execution consumption. Horizontal lines represent average values, showing 5.46W during execution and 3.49W in idle state.

Figure 2.9: Graphs illustrating power consumption over time for the Raspberry Pi 4 + CogniSat-XE2 are presented: the top plot shows usage with a single executor and the bottom with dual executors. Blue marks the pre-processing phase, while red denotes the inference stage. This assessment was conducted using three granules, limited to a singular iteration each.

granule), specifically focusing on average power, peak power, and time per granule. The Raspberry Pi 4 consumes the least power (5.3W on average), but this comes at the expense of speed, with a time per granule of 16.2s, making it the slowest among the configurations.

When the NCS2 is integrated with the Raspberry Pi 4, the average power increases slightly to 5.5W, but the processing speed drastically improves, with the time per granule reduced to 1.6s, enabling real-time processing with a per-granule time below 3.6 seconds. This significant performance enhancement is due to the dedicated inference hardware provided by the NCS2, which accelerates computation by offloading neural network tasks.

The CogniSat-XE2 configurations show similar enhancements in computational speed while keeping power consumption within a comparable range. In the setup with one executor, the Raspberry Pi + CogniSat-XE2 consumes 5.8W and processes each granule in 2.0 seconds, already achieving performance similar to the NCS2. By increasing the number of executors to two, the system’s power consumption decreases to 5.5W, and the processing time further improves to 1.8 seconds. This brings the CogniSat-XE2 (2 executors) configuration to a performance level that is nearly equivalent to the Raspberry Pi 4 + NCS2.

Table 2.7: Results - Power and Timing Benchmark Measurements

Deployment Device	Average power	Peak power	Time per granule
Raspberry Pi 4	5.3W	6.2W	16.2s
Raspberry Pi 4 & NCS2	5.5W	6.6W	1.6s
Raspberry Pi + CogniSat-XE2 (1 executor)	5.8W	6.4W	2.0s
Raspberry Pi + CogniSat-XE2 (2 executors)	5.5W	6.4W	1.8s

In conclusion, in terms of both power efficiency and speed, the CogniSat-XE2 (2 executors) is closely aligned with the NCS2 setup, allowing real-time execution onboard.

2.5 Discussion and Conclusion

2.5.1 Discussion

Previous works have suggested using AI to pre-filter data directly on spacecraft, moving away from the traditional ‘first-in-first-out’ bent-pipe model [94, 96]. However, studies by Furano et al. [94] and Giuffrida et al. [16] propose a file storage system where data is stored, optionally pre-processed, and then pulled for AI interpretation. While this approach has its merits, the lightweight method proposed here differs by operating on raw data. This makes the pipeline both simpler and faster, without sacrificing accuracy. Since the system processes data faster than it is produced, there is no need for intermediate storage, allowing data to be sent directly to the AI accelerator for inference. Processing in real-time significantly reduces the delay in generating alert maps compared to other on-board AI methods that rely on storage or pre-processing before inference.

This is crucial for applications like thermal hotspot detection, where processing delays directly impact the alert notification time. One limitation of our analysis is the assumption that the image is immediately available after its creation, which overlooks potential delays in transferring data from the camera to payload memory and from memory to RAM. However, high-speed communication protocols like SpaceFibre [97], with data rates up to 2.5 Gb/s [98], reduce the transfer delay for a 0.38 Gb raw image to under 0.2 s. Thus, this assumption has minimal impact on our findings.

A key outcome is the notably reduced energy and peak power consumption during model inference. Lower energy consumption affects orbit power availability, and thus the maximum duty cycle and coverage area. Since the pipeline assumes the imager and data handling unit operate simultaneously, reducing peak power is vital to ensure proper heat dissipation. Low energy and peak power consumption are critical for scalable, miniaturized payload designs, which can reduce mission costs. Our results show that real-time processing and energy efficiency are achieved due to two main factors. First, the inclusion of an AI hardware accelerator is essential; without it, the system fails to meet the required throughput and consumes significantly more energy. Space system designs should balance complexity, throughput, energy consumption, and hardware size. For smallsats with ARM-based processors, an accelerator is likely necessary. Second, the lightweight pre-processing, particularly the CSC discussed in our previous work [1], ensures sufficient accuracy, even when small events are included in the patch size. However, exceptions exist where registration errors cause significant displacement of thermal hotspots, which are critical for early alert systems. Future work will aim to refine the timing/quality trade-off in registration accuracy, potentially exploring

ML-based models.

It is also important to note that the onboard equalization coefficients applied to each granule are not recoverable, the equalization was not reversed. If needed for performance, onboard equalization could be integrated into the pipeline without affecting real-time processing, as it is a lightweight step (i.e., double-step piecewise linear function). Thus, we believe the differences between our data and real raw sensory data do not compromise the validity of our results.

2.5.2 Conclusions

The study [1] introduces a novel classification dataset for thermal hotspots in raw Sentinel-2 imagery, marking the first dataset of its kind. This unique dataset highlights the characteristics of raw, unprocessed multi-spectral data, further contributing to advancements in the field of AI at the edge for spaceborne remote sensing applications.

Based on this dataset, the work [99] presents a payload data processing concept designed to generate a thermal anomaly classification map by processing multispectral raw data in an end-to-end fashion. Data undergo a custom lightweight pre-processing step—termed CSC—before being input into an EfficientNet-lite0 model. Extensive benchmarks were performed using various training strategies, including MSMatch, Supervised Unweighted, and Supervised Weighted. The model’s performance, measured through MCC values, highlights the effectiveness of this patch-based detection approach. A breadboard prototype of the end-to-end pipeline was also implemented, leveraging different hardware configurations, including the CogniSat-XE2 board, a space-targeted device with flight heritage [95]. Real-time performance, with a peak power consumption of 6.4 W, was demonstrated through the inclusion of this and other hardware like Neural Comput Stick 2 (NCS2), in contrast to the baseline Raspberry Pi 4. The analysis of power consumption and latency across these configurations showed the efficiency of the system in reducing computational time while balancing power consumption, crucial for optimizing real-time data processing in space systems.

In conclusion, the study demonstrates the successful training of deep learning models on Sentinel-2 raw data for thermal hotspot detection, confirming the feasibility of the proposed raw-to-insight processing chain. These findings represent a significant advancement in real-time onboard data processing and in the application of AI in space.

Chapter 3

Autonomous Navigation

3.1 Introduction

3.1.1 Overview

The autonomous VBN is a crucial challenge for scheduled and future exploration missions. Taking the lunar scenario as an example, scientists have observed that the gravity field on the Moon deviates significantly from a spherically symmetric distribution [2, 100, 101]. This irregular gravitational field, often referred to as a “lumpy” field (Figure 3.1), causes localized gravitational anomalies that push and pull on the spacecraft. These perturbations lead to deviations from the predicted orbit, thus making orbit propagation more complex and computationally demanding. The Lunar exploration venture has garnered significant attention in recent years. The scientific interest in lunar exploration, especially in the polar regions with confirmed ice deposits, is driving efforts to establish bases and conduct sample extraction missions [5]. On February 22, 2024, the Nova-C lander, named *Odysseus* and developed by Intuitive Machines, successfully completed a seven-day orbital transit to the Moon. It achieved a soft landing near the Malapert A crater, located within the Moon’s South Pole region, at 18:24 Eastern Standard Time¹.

The resurgence in manned lunar missions introduces new challenges for navigation systems, as space missions are constrained by high costs and operational limitations with networks like Deep Space

Figure 3.1: Lunar gravity model (LGM2011). Gravity acceleration at the surface of the Moon in m/s^2 . (Source: Mazarico et al. [2])

¹<https://www.nasa.gov/missions/lro/nasas-lro-images-intuitive-machines-odysseus-lander/>

Network (DSN) or European Space Tracking network (ESTRACK). Furthermore, satellite links can be unreliable, and ground stations are often inaccessible, making real-time command transmission difficult. However, knowing the spacecraft's position and orientation is essential for navigating around a planetary body or conducting In-Orbit Servicing and Active Debris Removal operations. In these challenging scenarios, Optical Navigation (OPNAV) methods become a valuable tool for determining the spacecraft's spatial orientation and position, as extensively documented in the literature [102]. VBN strategies, leveraging image data, are divided into two categories based on the proximity of the spacecraft to the celestial body [103]. Horizon-based navigation is employed when a substantial portion of the celestial body is visible in the captured imagery. As the spacecraft approaches the surface, landmark-based navigation becomes essential, using distinct topographical features like craters or boulders for accurate positional determination [104]. VBN systems employ various sensor options, including monocular stereo cameras, thermal sensors, RGB/greyscale cameras, RADARs, and LIDARs. Monocular cameras are often preferred due to their simplicity, compact size, lightweight nature, minimal power requirements, and ease of integration into spacecraft configurations. Over the past decade, hand-crafted feature-based spacecraft navigation systems used feature descriptors and detectors. However, recent advances in DL have significantly improved the robustness and efficacy of computer vision algorithms, particularly for image classification [105] and segmentation [106]. Reflecting this trend, DL-based spacecraft pose estimation algorithms have surpassed traditional feature-engineering methods [107]. AI enhances VBN by addressing imaging system challenges such as noise, variable lighting, and changing shadow patterns. The adaptability of AI in processing onboard sensor data aids in rapid, well-informed decision-making. In spacecraft navigation near celestial bodies, monocular cameras are typically used to identify surface landmarks through object detection techniques. DL-based object detectors play a crucial role in detecting specific features on the celestial surface, and have been widely applied to lunar crater detection tasks for both navigation and geological purposes [108, 109]. While the scientific community has planned lunar base camps [110] and sample extraction in areas of interest like the polar regions, the confirmed presence of frozen water has revived manned lunar exploration. H₂O can provide insights into lunar history and be repurposed as rocket propellant or breathable air. Achieving these objectives presents new challenges for spacecraft localization systems. Currently, there is no specific requirement for a lunar positioning system. Nevertheless, the ESA has established a cut-off value of 1 km accuracy for most Martian applications [111]. Spacecraft venturing beyond Earth need specific payloads or support systems, relying on facilities such as the aforementioned DSN or ESTRACK. This requirement translates into high mission costs with limited operational capabilities. Furthermore, satellite links are not always guaranteed, ground stations are not easily accessible, and telemetry commands are not available in real-time.

Autonomous navigation systems reduce ground intervention and enable autonomous orbit control. Such systems are attractive because they can be applied to a wide range of space missions, including planetary exploration, studies of moons, and approach phases of comets, asteroids, and other celestial bodies. The recent advancements in computer vision and AI have generated significant interest in autonomous onboard OPNAV for its small size, weight, and power requirements [112]. OPNAV systems are classified into two types, depending on the spacecraft's distance to the target body: horizon-based systems are used when the celestial body disk is largely visible, while landmark-based systems utilize specific morphological features such as craters [112].

In landmark-based VBN, specific features are detected in an onboard map to gain positional knowledge, which is integrated into a navigation filter. Early applications of VBN date back to missile technology before the advent of GPS [113–116]. The standard OPNAV algorithm approach is computationally intensive, requiring real-time rendering of Digital Elevation Map (DEM)s and template matching [115, 117–119]. In contrast, crater-based VBN does not require DEMs but instead uses crater detection and pattern matching algorithms to relate observations to a database. A navigation filter then estimates the spacecraft’s state in terms of position and velocity.

Downes et al. [120, 121] proposed a transfer-learning approach using a U-Net architecture [122], based on DeepMoon [10], which detected lunar craters from elevation imagery. By fine-tuning the model on Lunar Reconnaissance Orbiter Camera (LROC) intensity images, they developed a network that segments craters from monocular images. However, this method, relying on segmentation, requires additional processing steps to convert segmentation maps into crater center coordinates and diameters, which increases computational latency. Furthermore, traditional least-square matching algorithms, such as Random Sample Consensus (RANSAC)-filtered methods [123], can lead to navigation state corruption, filter reinitializations, and potential mission aborts during critical phases such as lunar descent [112].

3.1.2 Landmark-based VBN

Contrarily, landmark-based VBN systems using craters do not require carrying DEMs and high computational burden but only require an image processing algorithm to detect craters and a pattern matching algorithm to relate these observations to a database. This is usually followed by a navigation filter to estimate the spacecraft state in terms of position and velocity.

However, the development of a crater-based VBN requires addressing several issues. One is the crater detection problem since sensors can generate various outputs depending on changes in the surface radiation, electronic element warming, or the inherent fluctuation of discrete photons [120, 121]. Though also the pattern recognition problem of matching craters with a catalogue of known craters is a troubling task. In past, this led to navigation with unknown landmarks [112, 124–127] and the extensive applications of horizon-based OPNAVs also at close distances. The crater matching problem is generally divided into two main types of problems. The first category is based on a least-square approach and requires precise knowledge of spacecraft position to perform matches. The second category, challenged in this research, does not rely upon this assumption and goes under the name of the lost-in-space problem. To solve this issue robustly, a crater-matching algorithm based on geometric invariant descriptors has been implemented [112, 128, 129]. Finally, a third problem consists in the position retrieval from matches and its integration into an EKF.

Downes et al. [120, 121] proposed a transfer-learning procedure. Using the same U-Net architecture [122], already trained by [10], they fine-tuned the weights on their custom dataset of intensity images. In this way, the network thus obtained can segment craters from monocular images. However, this method relies on a semantic segmentation task. Therefore, it requires additional processing steps to convert the segmentation maps of individual crater rims into center coordinates and diameters. Finally, craters are matched, and their positions are fed in input into an EKF. This methodology constrains the usage of an additional image processing chain to separate each crater rim (e.g. dilation, erosion, and convex-hull operators). Besides, as in other previous works [130, 131] their matching algorithm is not robust because relies on a least-square approach

(RANSAC filtered). This can create situations where corrupted navigation states render otherwise good images ineffectual, leading to unnecessary filter reinitializations, trajectory aborts (e.g. during lunar descent), or other undesirable events [112].

3.1.3 Chapter Structure

To address the limitations inherent in traditional methodologies, Section 3.2 of this chapter provides a comprehensive discussion on the proposed crater-based VBN system, termed “FederNet”. This system is designed with a high degree of robustness, leveraging the framework of projective invariants for crater matching. The design simplicity of FederNet is a key attribute, as it eliminates the need for additional, computationally expensive image preprocessing steps. Specifically, the crater detection problem has been reformulated by training a two-stage detector, which introduces a novel approach to this domain.

For the initial implementation, Mask R-CNN [132] was selected as the baseline model, integrated with a ResNet-101 backbone coupled with a Feature Pyramid Network (FPN) [132, 133] for multi-scale feature extraction. This combination was chosen to exploit the hierarchical feature representation capabilities of FPN and the accurate region proposal generation of Mask R-CNN, which is particularly well-suited for pixel-level precision required in crater detection tasks. The multi-scale representation enhances object detection performance, especially in scenarios involving instances with varying sizes and shapes, such as craters.

Notably, the integration of AI onboard spacecrafts, while holding significant promise for autonomy in navigation, is constrained by the limited power budgets available. Achieving real-time performance in such resource-constrained environments necessitates tailored model architectures that balance the trade-off between accuracy and computational efficiency. Strategies such as model quantization, which reduces the bit-width of model weights and activations, or model distillation, which transfers knowledge from larger, more complex models to smaller, more efficient ones, are essential techniques to mitigate the computational loads.

The Section 3.3 elaborates on this concept, proposing enhancements of the FederNet system, culminating in the introduction of “FederNet v2”. This updated version of the system suggests a detector optimized for deployment on low-power hardware platforms without compromising on the system’s ability to perform accurate and efficient crater detections in real-time. The design modifications include architectural refinements that streamline the model’s computational footprint, making it more suitable for onboard AI deployment, and a completely novel branch to deal in situations where craters are not available, such as during descent trajectories.

3.2 FederNet v1

This section provides a detailed explanation of the FederNet system, presenting its architecture and the corresponding experimental results obtained during its evaluation. The architectural breakdown covers the key components of the system, including the selection of crater detection module, the crater matching mechanism, and the integration of these measurements into a navigation filter. The experiments conducted serve to validate the system’s performance under different environmental conditions, underscoring its robustness and highlighting its suitability for deployment in real-world applications.

3.2.1 System Architecture

In summary, the FederNet system can be divided into the following four distinct modules:

1. **Crater Detection:** The DL-based crater detector identifies craters within elevation images captured by 3D sensors such as interferometric synthetic aperture radar, light detection and ranging technology, or high-resolution satellite stereo imagery. The detection pipeline utilizes the Mask R-CNN architecture [132] for instance segmentation and object detection. This approach eliminates the need for additional image processing, such as manual extraction of crater rims, thereby reducing computational complexity while requiring more sophisticated model training.
2. **Crater Matching:** After the craters are detected, their locations and radii are transmitted to a crater matching algorithm. This algorithm, adapted from the work of Hanak et al. [128, 129], is updated to handle the larger crater catalogues available today. FederNet processes the Robbins crater catalogue [7], which includes over one million entries, compared to the 8,673 craters in the USGS lunar crater database used by earlier studies [134].
3. **Position Estimation:** The crater matching algorithm determines correspondences between detected craters and entries in the crater catalogue. These correspondences are used to establish the spacecraft’s position, which is continuously updated throughout the mission.
4. **Extended Kalman Filter (EKF):** The spacecraft’s position measurements, derived from the crater correspondences, are fed into an EKF. The EKF incorporates an Eulerian propagator to refine and predict the spacecraft’s trajectory, ensuring accurate position estimation over time.

The following Sections 3.2.1-3.2.1 explain in detail the proposed framework in all of its parts.

Crater Detection Algorithm

Before describing the algorithm, the reader should know that crater counting and shape retrieval from orbital imagery have always been a key for understanding planetary age and evolution [9, 135–140] since they provide the relative age of the surface unit and information on the surface geology. For this reason, in the past crater detectors have been intended for geological surveys. First methods largely used image processing techniques [130, 137, 141–143] experiencing significant sensitivity to image quality, brightness, and shadows. The difficulty to predict these qualities

from camera and noise models poses an insurmountable problem and requires human intervention for each scenario. As a result, these crater detectors are not reliable or suitable for autonomous operations. DL algorithms offer promising opportunities because CNNs are capable of extracting low-, mid- and high-level features from images stacking together convolutional and pooling layers. The extracted features can be applied to various computer vision tasks, such as large-scale image recognition, object detection, semantic segmentation, and instance segmentation. Previous crater detectors were based on U-net architecture [122], one of the most commonly used networks for image segmentation. Conversely, the detector proposed implements Mask R-CNN, a network developed for instance segmentation and object detection. This helped to eliminate the usage of template matching approaches of methodologies based on popular image feature descriptors such as SIFT [144], SURF [145], BRIEF [146], or ORB [147]. As stated above, being the segmentation output distinguished for each instance, the usage of additional image processing steps are not required. The key innovation of this detector lies in its optimization for navigation, where identifying all craters in an image is not required. By raising the confidence score threshold to 0.95, only the most certain craters are retained. The crater detector was trained on the same datasets used in the DeepMoon project [10], which have been widely used to evaluate various crater detection models. These datasets include over 30,000 lunar tiles, cropped from the Lunar Reconnaissance Orbiter (LRO)-Kaguya merged 118 m/pixel DEM [148], downsampled to 8-bit using GDAL. Ground truth labels were sourced from the crater catalogs by Head et al. [3] and Povilaitis et al. [4]. This selection allows comparison with other DL-based crater detectors, though Mask R-CNN required different labels. Using transfer learning, we fine-tuned the COCO [149] pre-trained weights. The model was trained for 100 epochs following the multi-stage approach (30 heads, 70 all) in [132], using Stochastic Gradient Descent with a learning rate of 10^{-3} . Training parameters are listed in Table 3.1.

Table 3.1: Mask R-CNN model training parameters

Network Parameter	Value
Backbone	Resnet-101+FPN
Backbone Strides	[4, 8, 16, 32, 64]
Detection Max Instances	400
Detection Min Confidence	0.5
Detection Nms Threshold	0.4
Image Shape	[512 512 3]
Learning Momentum	0.9
Learning Rate	0.001
Max Gt Instances	400
Mean Pixel	[165.32, 165.32, 165.32]
RPN Anchor Ratios	[0.5, 1, 2]
RPN Anchor Scales	(4, 8, 16, 32, 64)
RPN Bbox Std Dev	[0.1 0.1 0.2 0.2]
RPN Nms Threshold	0.7
RPN Train Anchors Per Image	256
Validation Steps	16
Weight Decay	0.0001

A pre-processing strategy was applied following the approach of [9], thus using the CLAHE algorithm to boost contrast. Even if FPN [150] neck is used to capture the multi-scale local features, in several but rare cases, the model the model has completely gone wrong estimating craters with a huge

diameter. Thus, post-processing was also applied to filter out invalid detections. The filter is based on an adaptive threshold of the confidence score, depending on crater size.

Each step of the detector is reported in Figure 3.2, where it is possible to notice the variation of craters detected at each step, in comparison with the ground truth data coming from the Head et al. [3] & Povilaitis et al. [4] merge crater catalogue.

Figure 3.2: Crater detections (green) at each pipeline step, paired with ground truth data (red) from Head et al. [3] & Povilaitis et al. [4] merge crater catalogue. (Source: Del Prete et al. [5])

Crater Matching Algorithm

The crater matching algorithm developed is based on the work of [128, 129]. This research is well known in the space community for proposing a re-visitation of a star tracker algorithm based on projective invariants, i.e., geometric features independent of camera pose. The matching scheme can be summarized in three steps, using the same assumptions as in [128, 129].

Step 1: Crater Triads Generation In the first step, crater triads are generated by considering all the possible sets of three different craters. Unlike the star tracker algorithm, this approach accounts for false detections by including as many potential matchable craters as possible. The invariants chosen are the interior angles of the triad and the ratio between the crater radii and the centroid distances. These two descriptors preserve the angular and spatial distribution of a crater triad, respectively.

Let the three craters in a triad be represented by their centroids C_1, C_2, C_3 , and radii r_1, r_2, r_3 . The projective invariants are given by the following equations:

1. **Interior angles of the triad:** The angles $\theta_{12}, \theta_{13}, \theta_{23}$ between the centroids of the craters are calculated using the cosine rule:

$$\cos(\theta_{ij}) = \frac{|C_i - C_j|^2 + |C_j - C_k|^2 - |C_i - C_k|^2}{2|C_i - C_j||C_j - C_k|}$$

where $|C_i - C_j|$ is the Euclidean distance between the centroids C_i and C_j .

2. **Radius-distance ratios:** The ratio between the radii of the craters and the distances between their centroids is computed as:

$$R_{ij} = \frac{r_i}{|C_i - C_j|}$$

These projective invariants are computed for each triad, both for craters detected in the image and craters from the catalogue.

It should be outlined that since the number of crater triads grows approximately as N^3 , where N is the number of craters, the computational complexity of the algorithm is the computational complexity from $O(N^3)$. Thus, the complexity of the process becomes a bottleneck, particularly when dealing with dense crater fields.

Step 2: Dataframe Generation In the second step, two database are generated—one for the image craters and one for the catalogue craters. Each dataframe contains columns for the unique ID of each crater and the projective invariants (i.e., interior angles and radius-distance ratios) for each triad. This structure facilitates the comparison between craters from the image and the catalogue.

Step 3: Crater Matching via Joint Correspondences In the third step, the crater matching problem is solved as a mergubg based on matching criteria using a comparison operator. In this case, the comparison operator checks if the projective invariants (angles and radius-distance ratios) of the triads match within a given tolerance:

$$\text{Match}(\text{triad}_{\text{image}}, \text{triad}_{\text{catalogue}}) \iff |\text{invariants}_{\text{image}} - \text{invariants}_{\text{catalogue}}| < \epsilon \quad (3.1)$$

where ϵ represents the tolerance to account for discrepancies in crater sizes and positions between the image and the catalogue.

It must be noted that while tolerances improve flexibility, they also increase the risk of false matches. To address this, two validation functions are applied to filter out incorrect matches:

1. **Motion-based orientation validation:** This function checks if the orientation of the matched triad is consistent with the known direction of motion of the spacecraft.
2. **Crater disposal validation:** This function verifies the spatial arrangement of craters within the triad to ensure consistency with the expected geometry.

By accounting for these factors, the algorithm effectively reduces false positives, which are an intrinsic challenge in crater detection due to the inclusion of all possible triads. Matches that pass the validation process are then used as input for the position estimation algorithm. It is noteworthy that the number of the crater triads computed is approximately N^3 of the craters under investigation [5]

This refined approach ensures that the algorithm is robust against false detections, while still considering all potentially matchable craters for accurate localization.

Position Estimation Algorithm

This algorithm exploits the positions of the craters known both in the images and in the database to determine the spacecraft’s position. With the help of the matched triads, it is possible to establish a scale factor between pixels and degrees ($S = 1 \text{ px}/1^\circ$), due to the fact that the relative distances between craters are known both in pixels and latitude/longitude degrees.

Assuming the sensor’s spatial resolution is known, the calculation of the footprint (d) can be obtained through S . Finally, the altitude of the spacecraft can be easily retrieved through the linear equation:

$$d = 2H \tan\left(\frac{FOV}{2}\right) \quad (3.2)$$

which relates the footprint and the Field Of View (FOV) of the sensor with the altitude (H). The latitude and longitude of the spacecraft position are determined differently: the relative distances (in pixels) between craters and the image center are acquired and re-scaled using S to generate residuals.

The spacecraft in-plane localization is then carried out by exploiting the residuals, which relate the sensor's center position to each crater's position. Once a triad is matched, a single position is estimated. Assuming that most matches are correct, the localization measurements coming from each triad on the same image are then filtered using the interquartile method (40-60) and averaged out. Finally, the measurements are incorporated into the EKF, which is built with a Keplerian propagator.

Extended Kalman Filter

The EKF incorporates an orbital propagator with PEA measurements to calculate the estimated state of the spacecraft.

The state vector includes satellite position and velocity vectors in selenographic coordinates.

At each time step, the spacecraft state is propagated from the previous estimated state to the current state by the EKF.

The position measurements are used to generate a measurement residual, which is exploited by the EKF to correct the propagated state. Orbit propagation was approached as two-body motion, thus a simple Keplerian propagator was selected. A propagator of such a type determines the motion solely due to two-body gravitational acceleration, not taking into account non-sphericity effects of the central body, gravitational interaction with other objects, solar radiation pressure, and lunar angular velocity.

This simple propagator was chosen to highlight the capabilities of the developed system.

The 8(5,3)th-order Dormand & Prince method for numerical integration was applied for orbit propagation using fixed step size. The satellite dynamic model used for satellite orbit propagation is:

$$\ddot{\vec{r}}(t) = -\frac{\mu}{|\vec{r}|^3}\vec{r}(t) + \vec{w}(t) \quad (3.3)$$

where $\ddot{\vec{r}}(t)$ is the acceleration vector, μ is the moon's gravitational constant, $\vec{r}(t)$ is the orbital position vector, and $\vec{w}(t)$ is the vector of process noise.

Some initial assumptions are needed to fulfill the filter's requirements when implementing the EKF.

An initial state estimate and an initial state error covariance matrix are required to start the EKF process. The initial state vector is given by:

$$x(t_0) = \begin{bmatrix} x & y & z & V_x & V_y & V_z \end{bmatrix}_{6 \times 1} \quad (3.4)$$

A diagonal *a priori* covariance matrix P_{k-1} with standard deviations (σ) of 50 km (position), 35 m/s (velocity) is assumed. With these assumptions, at the first time instant, the *a priori* covariance

matrix P_0 is given by:

$$P_0 = \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_x^2 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \sigma_y^2 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \sigma_z^2 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \sigma_{v_x}^2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \sigma_{v_y}^2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \sigma_{v_z}^2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.5)$$

Following [151], the state transition matrix [152, 153] $\phi_{k,k-1}$ is used to propagate the covariance matrix, given by:

$$\phi_{k,k-1} \approx I + F(t_k - 1)^T \quad (3.6)$$

where $F(t_k - 1) = \begin{bmatrix} 0_{3 \times 3} & I_{3 \times 3} \\ J_{3 \times 3} & 0_{3 \times 3} \end{bmatrix}$ and ' T ' denotes the matrix transpose.

In $F(t_k - 1)$, $J_{3 \times 3}$ is the Jacobian coefficient matrix given by:

$$J_{3 \times 3} = \begin{bmatrix} 3\mu x^2 r^{-5} - \mu r^{-3} & 3\mu x y r^{-5} & 3\mu x z r^{-5} \\ 3\mu x y r^{-5} & 3\mu y^2 r^{-5} - \mu r^{-3} & 3\mu z y r^{-5} \\ 3\mu x z r^{-5} & 3\mu z y r^{-5} & 3\mu z^2 r^{-5} - \mu r^{-3} \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.7)$$

To cope with deficiencies of the employed propagation model, a fixed diagonal process noise matrix Q_{k-1} is considered in the time update of the covariance matrix, given by:

$$P_{(k|k-1)} = \phi_{k,k-1} P_{k-1} \phi_{k,k-1}^T + Q_{k-1} \quad (3.8)$$

Representative process noise values used in this application are $(1km)^2$ (position), $(10^{-1}km/s)^2$ (velocity). These values, especially the position ones, were determined through a tuning process based on trial and error to ensure the filter remains responsive to new measurements while correctly estimating state and covariance when measurements from the PEA are unavailable or of low quality. As for the correction step, at time k a measurement z_k of the position state x_k is obtained through PEA. The residual vector \tilde{y} is calculated from:

$$\tilde{y}_k = z_k - H_k x_{(k|k-1)} \quad (3.9)$$

where H_k is the measurement matrix at the k^{th} time instant:

$$H_k = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.10)$$

Based on $P_{(k,k-1)}$, H_k and R_k matrices, the covariance matrix S_k and the Kalman gain K_k are calculated according to:

$$S_k = H_k P_{(k|k-1)} H_k^T + R_k \quad (3.11)$$

$$K_k = P_{(k|k-1)} H_k^T S_k^{-1} \quad (3.12)$$

where R_k is the measurement noise covariance matrix, which generally represents Gaussian zero-mean noise. Representative measurement noise values used in this application are (1km) (position). The updated (*a posteriori*) state estimate at time k is obtained from:

$$X_{(k|k)} = X_{(k|k-1)} + K_{(k)}\tilde{y}_{(k)} \quad (3.13)$$

The updated (*a posteriori*) estimate covariance matrix P_k is given by:

$$P_k = (I - K_k H_k) P_{(k|k-1)} (I - K_k H_k)^T + K_k R_k K_k^T \quad (3.14)$$

3.2.2 Experimental Results

This section describes the setup used to conduct the experimental test as well as the numerical results achieved. Two crater catalogues will be analyzed in this study: Robbins [7] and the merge of Head et al. [6] & Povilaitis et al. [4]. For testing the system, a reference orbit (Figure 3.3) has been

Figure 3.3: Reference Orbit highlighting two regions: (yellow) region A and (blue) region B

generated at 50 km altitude. Equatorial inclination was preferred to characterize the performance of the developed system on very different scenarios from the point of view of crater density and distribution. The altitude instead was set as a standard value for lunar orbiters such as [154]. Based on the designed trajectory, it is possible to identify different regions: as shown in Figure 3.3, the first one ranges from -60° to 23° of longitude (A), a second one from 105° to -147° of longitude (B), and other regions show intermediate characteristics. The region A has a coarse crater coverage, while region B shows a high sample number of craters. The initial orbit parameters have been set according to Table 3.2.

Table 3.2: Initial orbital parameters

Orbital Parameter	Value
a	1787.1 km
e	0
i	0.0°
ω	0.0°
Ω	0.0°
ν	270.0°

Orbit propagation has been performed through a 7th order Runge-Kutta integrator. The force model includes a lunar gravity field model (LP100K [155]), solar radiation pressure, and third-body effects (Sun & Earth).

Crater Detection Results

Herein the developed detector is compared to other crater detectors on the dataset of [10]. As stated above, all of them have been likewise trained and evaluated on the same dataset with the same metrics. The metrics used are precision and recall. Precision is a measure of result relevancy, while recall is a measure of how many truly relevant results are returned. The recall (R) of a given class is defined as the ratio of true positives (T_p) to the sum of true positives and false negatives (F_n). Similarly, precision (P) is defined as the ratio of true positives to the sum of true positives and false positives (F_p). The F1-score is the harmonic mean of precision and recall. The three metrics can be expressed together as:

$$R = \frac{T_p}{T_p + F_n}, \quad P = \frac{T_p}{T_p + F_p}, \quad F1 = 2 \frac{P \cdot R}{P + R} \quad (3.15)$$

Precision, recall, and F1-score metrics results are summarized in Table 3.3, where it is possible to notice the results achieved by FederNet. The model detects on average almost double (231.14%) the craters stored in the catalogue ([4, 6]), this is mainly due to the conservative way in which craters have been classified by remote scientists. Thus, lower recall has to be interpreted as the algorithm identifying more new real craters with respect to the ground truths. While the results can be considered in general similar, it is worth noting that FederNet achieved the top score for the precision which is fundamental for the matching phase.

Table 3.3: The recognition results of different networks comparing different metrics (M) over the test set: precision (P), recall (R), F1-score (F1), and fractional errors on craters coordinates (x, y, r) of Mask R-CNN [9], Mask R-CNN (FederNet), DeepMoon [10], ERU-Net [11], ERU-Net-2 (i.e., ERU-Net with two Res-Blocks), DRU-Net [11], Aris-CNN [11], and D-LinkNet [12].

M	Mask R-CNN	DeepMoon	FederNet	ERU-Net	ERU-Net-2	DRU-Net	Aris-CNN	D-LinkNet
R	87.6 ± 8%	57 ± 20%	43.1 ± 20%	81.2%	80.2%	76.7%	76.1%	68.3%
P	66.5 ± 17%	80 ± 15%	81.1 ± 13%	75.4%	77.5%	77.9%	83.2%	77.2%
F1	0.75	0.66	0.53					
x	10.5%	10 ± 2%	10%	9.9%	9.6%	7.6%	9.6%	10.1%
y	7.5%	10 ± 2%	7%	10.0%	9.1%	7.0%	9.2%	10.0%
r	7%	8 ± 1%	7%	7.8%	7.7%	4.8%	7.2%	7.3%

Crater Matching Results

In this section, matching results between the two aforementioned crater catalogues are compared on the reference orbit. The FOV of the sensor has been set to 90° while the catalogue crater query has a search area of 100km × 100km, centered around the sensor position. Images recollected by an onboard imaging system have a spatial resolution of 512 x 512 px, and are acquired with a time step of 10 seconds. This step was chosen in consideration of the mean required time for processing

the entire pipeline. However, a lower time step would allow a more frequent measurement update, which is beneficial for the developed system.

The number of craters detected by the Crater Detection Algorithm (CDA) on the reference orbit has been computed. In this calculation, the confidence score threshold of the CDA has been set to 0.90 to filter the crater instances. This choice tunes the CDA for VBN, as finding all craters is computationally burdensome during the matching phase. In addition, this makes the predictions accurate and reliable. In Figure 3.4, the behaviors of the aforementioned crater catalogues as well as the craters detected during the orbit are shown. In the last part of the graphs of Figure 3.4, a small region of undetected craters is visible. This is not due to the CDA, but rather to the difficulty of properly handling the gigapixel size of the DEM. Thus, this small region was not processed by the system. In region A, the average number of catalogued craters by Head et al. & Povilaitis et

Figure 3.4: Crater matching results comparing: (top) detected craters with matched triads by (middle) Head et al. [6] & Povilaitis et al. [4] crater catalogue and (bottom) Robbins crater catalogue [7], respectively. [Different crater covered regions are marked in red, while values in $[1, 100]$ (blue line) and in $(100, \infty)$ (green line) are highlighted]

al. merge (H & P) is below 5, which significantly impacts system performance: it is crucial to have at least three craters to perform a match. Moreover, some regions showed a complete absence of catalogued craters. On the other hand, H & P performed well in region B with a good number of matches. Similar observations can be made for the Robbins crater catalogue. The average number of catalogued craters is much higher than the previous catalogue, showing no regions with a complete absence of craters. However, especially in region B, having such a large number of catalogued craters resulted in longer computational times for the matching phase. Nevertheless, it is clear that the Robbins crater catalogue has demonstrated better matching capabilities.

Position Estimation Results

This section reviews the PEA results. Referring to the reference orbit, measurement errors have been projected into the local East-North-Up (ENU) reference frame and are reported in Figure 3.5 and Figure 3.6. Notably, the middle graphs also show a magnification ($0 \div 1$ km) of the PEA results, highlighting regions with insufficient crater coverage. As seen from the graphs, these regions are more extensive in the merged crater catalogue compared to Robbins' catalogue.

Figure 3.5: Position errors prompted with the Head et al. [6] & Povilaitis et al. [4] merged crater catalogue. No measurement regions are highlighted in yellow.

Figure 3.6: Position errors prompted with the Robbins [7] crater catalogue. No measurement regions are highlighted in yellow.

In the majority of cases, results showed errors below 1 km, with some spurious measurements that needed to be rejected through the EKF implementation. Both crater catalogues demonstrated insufficient coverage during the first half of the orbit, whereas the second half showed a good number of measurements. More specifically, in the second half of the orbit, position measurements with errors below 500 m were obtained. The results also revealed critical zones without measurements, notably around -39° longitude due to the absence of craters, and around -90° longitude, caused by the failure of the Crater Matching Algorithm (CMA).

The statistical distributions of PEA measurement errors for the aforementioned catalogues are reported in Table 3.4. The data reveal that the Robbins catalogue exhibited a larger dispersion of errors over the entire orbit, mainly due to more frequent false matches leading to larger errors.

EKF Results

This section reviews the EKF accuracy results on the reference orbit. In order to reduce the influence of bad PEA measurements, a simple but effective approach based on gating and EKF has

Table 3.4: Statistical comparison of PEA measurement errors in the ENU frame between the Head et al. & Povilaitis et al. merged crater catalogue and the Robbins crater catalogue.

Catalogue	East (m)	North (m)	Up (m)
Head & Povilaitis (H&P)			
Mean (μ)	400.64	337.85	438.90
Std Dev (σ)	536.36	312.95	622.33
Robbins			
Mean (μ)	602.10	990.71	727.67
Std Dev (σ)	2587.73	5186.64	2896.89

been implemented. To make the approach more general, the initial state vector has been initialized with a random error on position between 0 and 15 km for each of its components: (X, Y, Z) in selenographic coordinates. The error distribution showed a Gaussian behavior, which justifies the introduction of a gating-based detection method determined by the statistical properties of the PEA measurements. Most of the PEA measurements can be effectively selected from all mixture measurements using the properly defined confidence region of 3 standard deviations, prompted at each step during the orbit. Once again, the two crater catalogues have been submitted for investigation.

Figure 3.7 shows the errors on position estimation in selenographic coordinates (Lunar Centered Lunar Fixed (LCLF)) with covariance bands ($\pm 3\sigma$) prompted for Head et al. & Povilaitis et al. Crater Catalogue. Errors and covariance bands largely increase in regions with scant crater

Figure 3.7: EKF accuracy results using Head et al. & Povilaitis et al. Crater Catalogue

coverage. On the other hand, the last part of the orbit, with more measurements, showed the best results, achieving a sort of convergence. Similarly, errors on position estimation in selenographic coordinates were computed for Robbins crater catalogue and reported in Figure 3.8. In this scenario, the initial error rapidly decreases because the Kalman filter benefits from a higher density

Figure 3.8: EKF accuracy results using Robbins Crater Catalogue

of measurements during the first stretch of the orbit. The most accurate results occur towards the end of the orbit, where the EKF performs updates almost continuously, leading to convergence. By comparing the results from both crater catalogues, as shown in Table 3.5, it becomes evident that the larger error in the east component stems primarily from regions with poor crater coverage.

Despite occasional false matches increasing errors in low-coverage areas, Robbins’ catalogue outperformed in overall EKF estimation. These false matches, often grid-like, are caused by entries in the Robbins crater catalogue not linked to the DEM, such as those from surface reflectivity models, cameras, and thermal cameras. However, Robbins’ catalogue still achieved superior performance due to more frequent corrections of propagator drift. The combination of gating and the EKF effectively filtered out erroneous measurements, enhancing overall accuracy. A final remark concerns the computational time required by the proposed system. While the

Table 3.5: Comparison of EKF position errors in the ENU frame between Head et al. & Povilaitis et al. merged and Robbins crater catalogues (Mean, Standard Deviation, and RMSE)

Catalogue	Region	Mean (km)			Std Dev (km)			RMSE (km)		
		East	North	Up	East	North	Up	East	North	Up
H&P	A	6.24	-0.01	-0.56	6.66	0.24	1.71	9.07	0.21	1.83
	B	-0.41	0.25	0.27	0.31	0.22	0.50	1.23	0.28	1.02
	Entire Orbit	2.91	0.18	-0.36	5.37	0.49	2.58	6.38	0.25	3.58
Robbins	A	2.90	-0.07	0.39	4.04	0.26	0.85	4.99	0.28	0.93
	B	-0.25	0.10	0.20	0.26	0.14	0.42	0.36	0.16	0.47
	Entire Orbit	0.95	0.03	0.21	2.63	0.22	1.13	2.80	0.23	1.15

PEA and EKF calculations can be considered instantaneous, the detection time depends on the model implemented and the hardware used. In more detail, the inference time of this model has been estimated to be generally below 0.45 seconds for the specific hardware used. Even with

modest hardware (NVIDIA® GTX 1060 6GB VRAM), the model completed its training after approximately 24 hours. It should be noted that this does not affect the inference burden since the training phase is accomplished on the ground, while the weights can be updated to the onboard model to increase its accuracy.

Different considerations arise for the matching times, which follow a different order of magnitude. Indeed, the required time grows exponentially with the number of matched triads. In Figure 3.9, the average matching time is reported by crater catalogue and region under inspection. As observed, for the Robbins crater catalogue, the time required for matching exceeds the step time in region B. This is mainly due to the high number of triads (>200) matched in that region. However, this is not the case for the merged catalogue, which shows an acceptable level of accuracy in that region.

In contrast, in region A, where the crater coverage is scant, the scenario changes, and the Robbins catalogue is the only one capable of providing a sufficient number of craters for matching.

In conclusion, while both crater catalogues are valid for regions with a regular number of craters, it is necessary to create a targeted crater catalogue to work effectively in regions with high or scant crater coverage.

Figure 3.9: Average time required by the matching algorithm reported by region and crater catalogue under inspection.

3.3 FederNet v2

As the lander’s altitude decreases, fewer craters are captured by the camera, and the visible craters become too small to be referenced in a lunar crater catalogue. This limitation makes the current system well-suited only for the preliminary descent phase, from the 100 km Low Lunar Orbit (LLO) down to an altitude of about 10 km, where many distinct and catalogued craters are visible within the sensor’s FOV.

To address this limitation, an additional operational mode is proposed for the VBN system, resulting in a dual-mode configuration tailored to the spacecraft’s varying altitude during descent. An in-depth analysis of the proposed system is conducted, with a focus on accuracy and timing in position estimation throughout a targeted trajectory. Preliminary testing of the AI-based crater detection module has been performed on representative hardware, evaluating the algorithm’s efficiency and latency.

3.3.1 System Architecture

The proposed visual navigation pipeline (Figure 3.10) is designed to provide navigation support throughout the entire descent, including phases where crater matching is no longer feasible.

The following subsections provide comprehensive details on the two distinct operational modes.

Figure 3.10: Flow diagram representing the proposed VBN system’s architecture in which the operational mode is selected based on specific criteria: if the altitude is below 10 km or no craters are detected, the relative mode is chosen. In absolute mode, images undergo crater detection and crater matches are identified. Then, the pose is estimated to solve the EPnP problem and integrated into the EKF. For the relative mode, it processes two frames at a time and computes their offsets through an essential matrix obtained by feature tracking, then integrates these offsets into the EKF.

Absolute Mode

This absolute mode enhances our previous work [5] with several significant advancements. First, crater detection transitions from relying on DEM to using high-resolution optical images, improving detection accuracy and applicability in various lighting conditions. Additionally, the position estimation process has evolved into full pose estimation, now capable of determining both the spacecraft’s position and attitude. This improvement is achieved by incorporating an EPnP solver, which allows for more precise and robust calculation of the spacecraft’s orientation relative to the lunar

surface. These upgrades enhance the overall reliability and accuracy of the navigation system.

More in detail, the two modules have been update as:

- **Crater Detection:** The deep learning-based crater detection module extends our previous work [156] to be deployed onboard and to account real optical images. To this end, it was trained on a dataset built from real optical images. A total number of 804 images have been obtained from the Wide Angle Camera (WAC) global mosaic [157]. This is a cylindrical map projection comprising over 15,000 images from -90° to 90° latitude and all longitudes, acquired from the LROC [158, 159]. Orthographic projection images centered along the equator have been taken into account. Each image is centered at 0° of latitude and is spaced from the other any 60° of longitude. Images with a resolution of 128.00 px/deg and 256.00 px/deg have been used and tiles have been extracted by cropping. Each original picture had a dimension of 14668×14668 pixels but a smaller squared area of 7168×7168 pixels has been taken into account to avoid distortions at the edges. From each of these images, a number of 134 tiles of 512×512 pixels have been obtained.
- **Pose Estimation:** The output of the matching pipeline yields 2D-to-3D correspondences, encompassing crater coordinates in both the camera reference frame and the LCLF frame. In this updated version of the algorithm, conversely to only satellite position, the camera pose in the LCLF frame, the efficient EPnP algorithm [160] is employed, optimized for resource-constrained spacecraft environments. Resolving the PnP problem ultimately determines the monocular camera’s pose.

Relative Mode

In low-altitude scenarios, the crater-based navigation system becomes less effective due to the decreased number of visible catalogued craters. As a result, alternative methods that track salient surface features between consecutive frames become essential for accurate navigation [161] [162]. The proposed feature matching pipeline is a key component of the relative navigation algorithm and is composed of two primary architectures: SuperPoint [163] and SuperGlue [164]. Below is a detailed breakdown of the pipeline, covering feature extraction, feature matching, and essential matrix estimation.

- **Feature Extraction:** The SuperPoint network is a highly efficient architecture for detecting feature points and generating descriptors from images. It employs a VGG-like [165] encoder to reduce the image’s dimensionality. Two decoders then process the shared and spatially reduced input to output both keypoint locations and corresponding descriptors [163]. SuperPoint achieves a balance between lightness and accuracy, making it well-suited for applications such as Simultaneous Localization and Mapping (SLAM) and Structure from Motion (SfM) [166–168].
- **Feature Matching:** SuperGlue is designed to match sparse local features between images. It addresses this problem by solving a differentiable optimal transport problem, with costs predicted using a Graph Neural Network (GNN). The architecture leverages a flexible context aggregation mechanism based on attention, enabling it to reason about the 3D structure of the scene and to perform more accurate feature assignments [164]. SuperGlue has been widely used

in SfM [168]. The more recent LightGlue [169] enhances efficiency by dynamically adjusting the number of layers based on the input image pair’s complexity and discarding non-matchable points early, thereby focusing attention on the most informative areas.

- **Essential Matrix Estimation:** Once 2D point correspondences are established, the relative pose between two consecutive camera viewpoints is estimated using the essential matrix. This process relies on RANSAC for outlier rejection [123], followed by matrix decomposition and verification against the cheirality condition to ensure correctness [170]. Scale ambiguity is resolved by incorporating altimeter measurements generated during the virtual landing scenario.

3.3.2 Experimental Results

To evaluate and validate the performance of the proposed architecture, a testing pipeline has been established. Firstly, a dataset of synthetic images has been generated along a reference descent trajectory, to support the assessment of the VBN module’s performance across both operational modes. Subsequently, further testing of the crater detector on dedicated hardware has been performed to evaluate inference times and power consumption. A landing trajectory covering approximately 17 kilometers in altitude, with a duration of about 36 minutes. Figure 3.11 depicts the lander’s trajectory within the virtual scenario, alongside two illustrative examples of synthetic images generated from this environment. The chosen landing site is situated on the border of the Shackleton crater, positioned at the lunar South Pole. This selection was made based on analyses of the average annual exposure to solar illumination, aiming to identify the most viable locations for lunar landings [171]. While the investigation of optimal landing guidance falls outside the scope of this study, the reference trajectory was generated considering fuel consumption and thrust constraints, aligning with the specifications of the ESA Large Logistics Lander (EL3) [172].

The lander’s dynamics were propagated factoring in the following forces acting on the spacecraft for both powered and ballistic segments: gravitational force from the main celestial body, third body effects from both the Sun and the Earth, and solar radiation pressure on the spacecraft surface at a distance of 1 AU from the Sun. The lander has an initial wet mass of 2500 kg and a dry mass of 1200 kg.

A dataset of synthetic images of the lunar surface was generated starting from the DEM generated by the LRO Lunar Orbiter Laser Altimeter (LOLA). With a resolution up to 5 m/pixel, this DEM enabled to construct a high fidelity 3D model of the lunar terrain traversed by the lander. The surface was subsequently imported into Unreal Engine 5 [8], leveraging its capabilities to handle high-polygon meshes and high-fidelity scenes through innovative technologies such as Nanite [173], Virtual Shadow Maps (VSMs) [174] and Lumen [175]. This virtual landing scenario facilitated the creation of high-resolution images under varying lighting conditions. A material simulating lunar regolith was applied to the surface to enhance realism. Post-processing techniques, such as Contrast Limited Adaptive Histogram Equalization (CLAHE), were employed to ensure alignment between the synthetic images dataset and a dataset of real images captured by the LRO’s WAC.

Figure 3.11: Reference descent trajectory within the virtual landing scenario based on Unreal Engine [8] (left). The synthetic image (a) has been captured from the environment at longitude 0.96° W and latitude 75.80° S. Image (b) has been generated at longitude 1.66° W and latitude 82.62° S

Absolute Mode

The performance assessment of the absolute pose estimation algorithm was conducted according to the following methodology: a sequence of uniformly spaced images was captured along the first portion of the landing trajectory, at 15 km of altitude. Each image was input to the absolute pose estimation algorithm, which performed crater detection, matching with the selected catalogue [176] and pose retrieval by solving the related PnP problem through the EPnP solver. The camera frame rate has been set to 1/5 Hz.

Figure 3.12 provides the outcomes of the crater matching task for a synthetic image sample that the crater detector has not encountered during the training phase. The detected craters (in green) have been matched with the corresponding catalogue craters (in yellow).

The average absolute position error has been computed as the Euclidean norm of the vector difference between estimated and true lander positions in the LCLF reference frame. This mean error has been estimated to be 270.1 m.

For all stages of the absolute navigation algorithm, computational times were computed using commercial hardware (Intel® Core™ i7-8086K Processor @5GHz and 16 GB of system RAM) yielding the following results: approximately 1.08 s on average for the crater detector CPU inference, about 90 ms for the matching phase, and less than 2 ms for the EPnP solver.

Relative Mode

The relative navigation algorithm has been tested along the final segment of the trajectory, covering the altitude range from 10 km to 2 km and lasting approximately 150 seconds. To assess the pipeline's navigation performance, the displacement error relative to the ground has been evaluated. Figure 3.13(a) display said error, split into its horizontal and vertical components, and evaluated at each new frame acquisition along the selected trajectory portion. The camera's framerate was set to

Figure 3.12: An example of crater detection and matching. The green craters are those detected by the crater detector. The yellow craters are the corresponding catalogue craters.

1/4 Hz, and the number of keypoints to detect for each frame was configured to 1024 for the testing procedure. Both the horizontal and vertical errors display a negative trend with decreasing altitude. The average displacement error along the trajectory has been estimated to be approximately 27.4 m for the horizontal component. The vertical error component is about 0.8 meters and can be attributed to the altimeter measurements being directly integrated into the navigation pipeline. The rotation error relative to terrain was estimated by simulating a yaw slew maneuver along the final trajectory segment, and by evaluating the error committed on the measured rotation. The chosen maneuver starts with a 30° rotation lasting for about 20 seconds, followed by a 40 seconds coasting phase where the lander proceeds along the trajectory in a crabbed fashion. Finally, the maneuver ends with the lander performing another 30° slew maneuver to recover the initial attitude configuration.

By exploiting the virtual scenario capabilities, it was possible to generate a synthetic image sequence during the lander’s slew at varying camera frame rates. This sequence was subsequently used in the pose estimation algorithm to retrieve the instantaneous and mean relative attitude errors. Figure 3.13(b) depicts a comparison between the actual rotation and the rotation measured by the relative navigation pipeline. Very limited deviation from ground truth can be appreciated, with a maximum cumulated error of about 0.7° , indicating a good correlation between the rotation estimates provided by the pipeline and the actual rotations.

Testing the relative navigation algorithm on commercial hardware (see Section 3.3.2) yielded an average LightGlue CPU inference time of 3.81 s, and 50 ms for the pose estimation.

To compare the relative efficiency and effectiveness of each operational mode in VBN, Table 3.6 presents an analysis contrasting the positional accuracy of both the absolute and relative modes. The analysis highlights that the absolute navigation pipeline yields an estimation error of approximately 300 m along the trajectory, consistent with the anticipated performance at these relevant altitudes. The relative mode demonstrates notably low error margins in horizontal displacement, consistently remaining under 150 m.

Figure 3.13: (a) Horizontal and vertical components of the relative displacement error along the selected trajectory segment. (b) Comparison between actual rotation and rotation measured by the relative navigation pipeline. The maximum deviation is approximately 0.7° .

3.3.3 Onboard Implementation

As stated above, with the expanding uptake of AI onboard satellites, the possibility of effectively streamlining computational loads to AI-dedicated chips is increasing. These components can accelerate or execute with high energy efficiency in some modules of the processing chain. The landscape of platforms for onboard AI deployment in satellites is notably limited to a few devices supported by various In-Orbit Demonstration on Class V/IV² spacecrafts and on-ground radiation testing. This can be explained by the complexity of qualifying ground platforms for space applications and by the low maturity of AI models and workflows for onboard deployment.

In this study, we show a demonstration of the optimization and testing of the crater detector module. To facilitate a rigorous and exhaustive evaluation, we conducted empirical testing of the optimized crater detector module on two established hardware platforms with a proven flight legacy. Specifically, our selection included the Intel[®] NCS2 and the Ubotica CogniSAT-XE1 (XE1), which incorporates the Intel[®] Movidius[™] Myriad[™] 2 chip.

A simple but effective model for the crater detection module has been tested: we combine ResNet-50 as a backbone for feature extraction with head layers similar to the ones of SSD [177]. To tailor the model more effectively to onboard devices, we removed certain layers³ from the original implementation for a more streamlined design. A pivotal modification in the *conv4_x* layer involved setting strides to a uniform 1×1 , diverging from typical configurations. *BatchNorm* layers were added after each convolution in the SSD heads to boost stability and training efficiency.

The model training has been performed with mixed precision using an NVIDIA[®] A100 GPU.

²ESA Mission Classification and Project Adoption of New Microelectronics Development, available online at: <https://tinyurl.com/2s5shdkj>

³All the *conv5_x*, the *Average Pooling*, and *fully-connected* layers in the classification heads.

Table 3.6: Absolute and relative mode accuracies in terms of mean position error, mean horizontal displacement and mean vertical displacement.

VBN Mode	Performance
Absolute	Mean Position Error: 270.1 m @1/5Hz
	Mean Horizontal Position Error: 216.1 m @1/5Hz
	Mean Vertical Position Error: 54.0 m @1/5Hz
Relative	Mean Horizontal Displacement Error: 27.4 m @1/4Hz
	Mean Vertical Displacement Error: 0.8 m @1/4Hz

Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD) with a momentum of 0.9 was utilized for optimization. A critical element in our training methodology was the learning rate scheduler. We adopted a cosine annealing approach, starting with an initial learning rate of $2.6e-3$. To enhance training, we implemented learning rate decay, and a linear warmup strategy during the first epoch, incrementally increasing the learning rate from a low to a higher value. This technique helps avert early training divergence due to an excessively high starting learning rate.

Subsequently, the model underwent post-training quantization using the OpenVINO toolkit (v2020.3) to compile it in half-precision. These specific training strategies were crucial in optimizing the model for quantization, ensuring both effective performance and compatibility. The model’s efficacy was assessed using average precision and average recall, considering various scales and IoU thresholds. Table 3.7 presents the ultimate results obtained through an exhaustive hyper-parameter tuning process, employing a grid search technique. Ultimately, the model was successfully deployed on two designated devices, yielding inference times under one second. Figure 3.14 presents a bar plot comparing the inference times for processing a single image (tensor size $1 \times 3 \times 300 \times 300$) on each device. As it can be observed, the NCS2 demonstrates a performance that is three times faster than that of the XE1 board.

Table 3.7: Average Precision (AP) and Average Recall (AR) prompted at different scales and intervals of Intersection over Union (IoU).

Metric	IoU	Area	Max Detections	Value	
AP	0.50:0.95	<i>all</i>	100	0.34	
				0.67	
				0.30	
	0.50:0.95	<i>small</i>		0.23	
				<i>medium</i>	0.55
				<i>large</i>	0.58
AR	0.50:0.95	<i>all</i>	1	0.047	
			10	0.30	
			100	0.46	
		<i>small</i>	0.38		
			<i>medium</i>	0.65	
			<i>large</i>	0.66	

Figure 3.14: Latency comparison of the quantized model for crater detection. The bar plot illustrates the time performance, in seconds, of two different devices under test, i.e., the CogniSAT-XE1 (XE1) and the Intel® Neural Compute Stick 2 (NCS2).

3.4 Discussion and Conclusion

3.4.1 Discussion

Despite the achievements of this study, certain limitations remain, and there are clear opportunities for further improvement. A key focus of our ongoing research is the optimization of the LightGlue network. While the network demonstrates promising capabilities, optimizing it for onboard deployment presents a significant challenge. This requires striking a balance between maintaining high accuracy and minimizing computational demands.

Moreover, the efficiency of the crater-matching pipeline presents another critical area for improvement. Currently, the pipeline faces a computational bottleneck due to its quadratic complexity, which scales with the number of craters [5]. This poses a significant challenge, particularly in scenarios involving large datasets with numerous craters. To address this, our future work will focus on developing more advanced algorithms that reduce computational load without compromising the accuracy of crater matching.

One promising direction is the implementation of more efficient data structures or leveraging machine learning techniques to intelligently prioritize or filter crater comparisons. Alternatively, integrating parallel processing methods or hardware accelerators, such as VPUs, could significantly enhance computational speed.

The current quadratic complexity also raises concerns regarding scalability, especially for large-scale lunar or planetary surveys where thousands of craters must be analyzed. Improving the efficiency of the crater-matching process would not only reduce computational time but also enhance the overall feasibility of applying this method to extensive datasets.

In summary, optimizing the LightGlue network for onboard use and addressing the computational inefficiencies in the crater-matching pipeline are critical areas for future research. These advancements will not only enhance the practicality of this study but also expand its applicability in broader space exploration and remote sensing missions.

3.4.2 Conclusion

In the study [5], we introduced FederNet, a VBN system designed for autonomous navigation in lunar and planetary missions. The first version of the system, FederNet v1, demonstrated the ability to meet the requirements for planetary positioning systems. Despite using medium-resolution DEM and a basic Keplerian propagator, FederNet is capable to cruise with a navigation accuracy below 400 meters when a sufficient number of well-distributed craters is available for matching [5, 156]. A key advantage of this system is its independence from Earth-based operators, leading to significant reductions in operational resources and costs. However, the current implementation has limitations, particularly in the size and complexity of the DL model used for crater detection, which is too computationally heavy for onboard deployment. Additionally, another limitation lies in its functional requirements of observing craters [156].

To address these issue, FederNet v2 has been introduced in [35] focusing on a tailored solution for autonomous lunar landing operations. The study innovates FederNet v1 by integrating a dual-mode VBN approach, adapt at switching between “absolute” and “relative” modes depending on altitude and crater visibility. To the knowledge of the author, this represents the first research on adaptive VBN. Our simulated descent experiments over Shackleton crater mark a first step in validating the AI-based system for onboard use. In terms of accuracy, the system’s relative mode achieved an average horizontal displacement error of merely 27.4 m at 1/4 Hz and an impressively low vertical displacement error of 0.8 m at the same frequency, showcasing the system’s high precision. Our evaluations using CogniSAT-XE1 and NCS2 have confirmed the capability of operating the crater detection module with inference times under one second and with an overall AP of 0.67.

Chapter 4

Maritime Situational Awareness

4.1 Introduction

4.1.1 Overview

MSA refers to the effective understanding of activities within the maritime environment that could affect safety, security, and the overall economy. For improving MSA, Ship Detection (SD) has been a topic of interest since the development of the first remote sensing techniques. Knowing what is happening at sea and achieve a real awareness of maritime domain respond to the needs of a wide range of maritime policies, such as irregular migration/border control, maritime security, fisheries control, anti-piracy, oil pollution, and smuggling. This has pushed the development of projects, toolboxes, techniques, with the final scope of monitoring maritime activities. As delineated in the Blue Worlds Initiative of ESA¹, our ability to monitor, control, defend, connect and exploit the maritime territory, its resources and its pathways is essential for achieving a safeguarding of all the involved interests, from the economic ones to the environmental ones.

The firsts maritime monitoring services relied on cooperative systems such as the AIS [178]. AIS messages—exchanged in real-time between vessels and shore-based stations—embed fundamentals information such as vessel identity, position, speed, course, and destination. AIS data faces several limitations that hinder its effectiveness in ensuring a comprehensive maritime domain awareness. One major limitation is the system’s limited coverage, as the effective range of AIS is roughly 20 nautical miles for ground-based stations, restricting its ability to monitor ships beyond coastal waters [179]. Another issue is its cooperative approach as it relies on active transmissions from ships. This means that vessels can deliberately disable their transponders to avoid detection [180]; this class of vessel is often referred to as “dark vessels”. Additionally, regulatory gaps exist, as International Maritime Organization (IMO) regulations mandate AIS usage for certain vessel classes, but smaller vessels or those not subject to these regulations can operate without AIS, leading to incomplete maritime monitoring [180]. Finally, one last problem of AIS regards the integrity of the data as incorrect or corrupted AIS messages can reduce the reliability of the system [181]. To address these shortcomings, there is a critical need for a complementary source of information. Satellite-based remote sensing systems have emerged as the key tool, providing global and non-cooperative detections that can track maritime activities [182].

¹Blue Worlds Task Force: <https://shorturl.at/9bzEt>

4.1.2 Low Latency Maritime Enforcement

Low latency maritime enforcement refers to the ability to carry out real-time or near-real-time surveillance, monitoring, and enforcement activities in maritime environments. Considering the enormous impact of latency on maritime monitoring, the efficient and timely recognition of vessels is mandatory to allow maritime authorities to take quick enforcement and rescue operations.

Within this context, the traditional data processing chains based on the classical bent-pipe approaches [16, 94] face significant challenges. With reference to the Figure 4.1, the “sensing-communication-decision-feedback” cycle can incur in substantial delays due to inherent limitations, such as the increased latency for data download, the ground station availability and the high-level products calculation [1].

Additionally, given the the large amounts of data generated by missions like Sentinel, which produces over 12 TB of data daily [183], the need to transmit satellite data to Earth strains the available communication bandwidth [16, 94]. To mitigate this issue, AI onboard satellites poses itself as promising solution significantly reducing the amount of data transmitted by: a) pre-filtering the collected information, and b) performing real-time processing directly onboard. As displayed in Figure 4.1, instead of sending all raw data back to Earth, AI algorithms can be used to analyze and prioritize data, transmitting only the most relevant or high-priority information. Within the maritime surveillance framework, AI can be used to detect and classify vessels or anomalous activities directly onboard, discarding irrelevant data, such as large areas of open water, and sending only detections or event-driven insights to ground stations. This onboard processing reduces the need to downlink vast volumes of raw data, optimizing bandwidth usage while maintaining mission-critical insights [184]. Regarding the sensors utilised, SAR remains the preferred choice due to its unique capabilities. In fact, SAR’s active imaging system uses microwave pulses that interact with targets, like ships, which typically return a stronger backscatter signal than the surrounding ocean clutter, making them stand out as bright pixel clusters in SAR imagery. This ability to detect vessels regardless of time of day is particularly useful for addressing illegal activities that often occur at night.

Figure 4.1: Pictorial representation of traditional data handling chain (top) vs. onboard-AI approach (bottom) for vessel detection.

Optical satellites are now gathering attention [185] representing an additional source of information, and offering distinctive features which are also helpful with contextual interpretation. With advances in AI and data processing, optical imagery can now be analyzed more efficiently, making it a valuable tool for enhancing MSA.

4.1.3 Chapter Structure

This chapter focuses on addressing key challenges in maritime surveillance, particularly in the detection and identification of ships and their wakes, as well as demonstrating a multi-mission satellite approach for enhanced maritime domain awareness.

Section 4.2 addresses the problem of ship detection, focusing on the dataset development and the training of a model specifically designed for this task. The model is subsequently deployed on representative hardware to demonstrate its efficacy in operational environments. The section provides a comprehensive overview of the methodology, dataset characteristics, and performance evaluation of the deployed model.

Section 4.3 shifts the focus to the detection and identification of ship wakes. This section describes the datasets—gathered from optical and SAR data—curated for this purpose, and details the model training process aimed at accurately detecting and identifying ship wakes. Emphasis is placed on the unique challenges posed by ship wake detection, including variations in wake patterns and environmental conditions, and how the developed models address these challenges.

The Section 4.4 presents an demonstration of benefits coming from the application of a “Tip & Cue” technique, simulated using data from three cooperating satellite missions: the European Sentinel-1, the Italian COSMO-SkyMed (first generation), and the Argentinian SAOCOM. The objective is to demonstrate how the combined use of multiple satellite platforms can enhance MSA. By leveraging the complementary capabilities of these missions, the section highlights how multi-satellite cooperation can lead to more effective and timely detection of maritime activities, showcasing the benefits of an integrated approach to monitoring the maritime environment.

4.2 Detection of Vessels

This section outlines the use of AI for SD onboard. It begins by introducing the first two datasets of raw multi-spectral data specifically developed for SD, explaining the strategy behind their creation and the pre-processing strategy adopted. Following, the model development is discussed in detail, highlighting the training methods and optimization techniques used. Finally, the deployment of the model on a representative hardware is analyzed, including timing and power benchmarks along with considerations for real-time processing in resource constrained environments.

The first raw multispectral datasets for MSA were developed from S-2 and VEN μ S satellite imagery. The creation of such datasets involves addressing challenges such as band-to-band alignment, noise, and accurate vessel annotation, while leveraging AIS information.

Missions The S-2 mission, part of the EU’s Copernicus program, includes Sentinel-2A (launched June 2015), Sentinel-2B (March 2017), and Sentinel-2C (launched September 2024), providing high-resolution multispectral imaging of Earth’s land and coasts. Operating in a sun-synchronous orbit with a 290 km swath width and 5-day revisit at the Equator, each satellite is equipped with a MSI

capturing 13 spectral bands: four at 10 meters (B_2, B_3, B_4, B_8), six at 20 meters ($B_5, B_6, B_7, B_{8A}, B_{11}, B_{12}$), and three at 60 meters (B_1, B_9, B_{10}). These data enable detailed monitoring of vegetation, soil, water, and land use. Available processing levels include Level-1C (top-of-atmosphere), Level-2A (bottom-of-atmosphere), and higher-level products. The MSI’s 12 staggered detectors provide the high swath width, producing granules for each spectral band.

As defined in [1], L0 data refers to sensor-acquired information equalized and compressed onboard, then decompressed and supplemented with metadata after downlinking but unprocessed geometrically or radiometrically². This raw data, from our previous works [1, 30], represents the earliest processing stage before co-registration, radiometric calibration, and ortho-rectification, essential for higher-level products. L0 products are not publicly distributed.

The VEN μ S mission, a collaboration between Israeli Space Agency (ISA) and CNES, focuses on EO. Launched in August 2017 and operating in sun-synchronous Low Earth Orbit (LEO), it captures multi-spectral images every two days over 120+ sites with 5-meter resolution from VIS to NIR. The VEN μ S MSI, the VEN μ S SuperSpectral Camera (VSSC), offers high spatial, temporal, and spectral resolutions [186], [187], [188]. The VSSC, a push-broom imager, includes a 0.25 m catadioptric objective, a 1.75 m focal plane with narrow-band filters, and four detector units. Each unit has three Charge-Coupled Device (CCD)-Time Delay Integration (TDI) arrays sensing three spectral bands: A (B_1, B_2, B_5), B (B_{10}, B_{11}, B_{12}), C (B_7, B_8, B_9), and D (B_3, B_4, B_6), capturing all 12 bands per acquisition. Product levels include L1C, Level-2A, and Level-3 (10-day composites) [189]. L0 products are archived but not shared. Ben Gurion University’s Remote Sensing Lab processes and disseminates products for three Israeli sites.

Finally, Figure 4.2 compares the spectral responses of the MSIs of VEN μ S and S-2, highlighting their similarities and differences.

Raw Data Characteristics As discussed earlier, most of literature focuses on methods applied to high-level products, due to the limited use and availability of raw data. Consequently, approaches for handling raw data remain relatively new and underdeveloped, as working with raw data introduces unique and often uncharted challenges. In this section, we outline these challenges and propose effective solutions to address them.

It is essential to recognize that the L0 bands represent raw, decompressed data in its most fundamental form. As such, they do not undergo the standard ground segment processing pipeline, which includes computationally-intensive tasks such as calibration, ortho-rectification, and georeferencing; processing required to generate an L1C product. Indeed, they exhibit various forms of radiometric noise and artifacts (Figure 4.3). In the case of VEN μ S, this noise is particularly pronounced, including effects such as stray light [190] or signal non-uniformity across the camera detectors’ pixels and fixed pattern noise (stripe noise). This spatially coherent kind of noise is typically found in multispectral data [191] and arises from improper correction of the Charge-Coupled Device (CCD) response function, owing to unexpected temperature changes on the photoelectric system [192]. Lastly, an unusual artifact, termed “radiometric spike” was identified in VEN μ S images by [193]. These spikes affect hundreds of pixels across all spectral bands, both in-flight and during ground measurements, showing an offset variation dependent on incoming radiance. The spikes’ amplitude

²See S-2 Product Specification Document (PSD v15): <https://sentinel.esa.int/documents/d/sentinel/s2-pdgs-cs-di-psd-v15-0>

Figure 4.2: Graphical comparison of the normalized spectral responses between the MSI on the VEN μ S satellite (top) and the S-2 (bottom) highlighting key differences in their spectral band coverage. Specifically, the VEN μ S bands B_i ($i = 1, 5, 6, 12$) do not have corresponding bands in the S-2 imager. Conversely, bands B_8 and B_9 of S-2 are absent in VEN μ S, indicating that each MSI is optimized for different spectral features.

and location vary by spectral band, but their shape remains consistent. Each spike influences four consecutive pixels oppositely based on their position in the left or right register, and their locations are stationary between ground and in-flight observations. The Figure 4.3(a-b) clearly shows the artifacts and noise affecting VEN μ S imagery.

For what concerns S-2 images, the data do not present the same level of noise and artifacts of VEN μ S MSI as the Figure 4.3(c-d) highlights. This is due to onboard equalization, aimed at enhancing the compression rates, that takes into account dark signal variations and inter-pixel offsets [194, 195].

While DL methods manage noise and artifacts well, misaligned bands pose greater challenges. Models can lose spatial information, affecting accuracy, and pixel/box-level annotations need careful alignment across bands. This is especially crucial for small objects like vessels, where even a 1-pixel shift can degrade performance. To address this, we propose a coarse-to-fine bounding box strategy. Initial coarse labeling is followed by automated refinement using four thresholding techniques: Otsu [196], Li [197], Isodata [198], and Mean [199]. These methods segment the image by separating foreground from background pixels based on calculated thresholds. The formulas for each method

Figure 4.3: (a) Unequalized VENµS L0 image of the Ebro Delta, showing significant stray light artifacts in band B_2 , which affects the visibility of underlying features. (b) Striping noise observed in band B_2 of the VENµS L0 image captured over the port of Ashdod, illustrating the impact of lack of calibration on coastal imagery. (c) Radiometric noise present in band B_3 of the S-2 L0 image over an algal bloom area, highlighting the challenges of detecting subtle biological features amidst sensor noise. (d) Radiometric noise detected in band B_3 of the S-2 L0 image over the Danish Fjord, demonstrating the effects of sensor-induced noise on the accurate interpretation of aquatic environments.

are presented below.

$$\begin{aligned}
 Otsu : \quad t &= \underset{t}{\operatorname{argmin}} [\omega_{\text{bg}}(t)\sigma_{\text{bg}}^2(t) + \omega_{\text{fg}}(t)\sigma_{\text{fg}}^2(t)]; \\
 Li : \quad t_{i+1} &= t_i + \frac{t_i - \text{Li}(t_i)}{1 + \text{Li}(t_i)}; \\
 Isodata : \quad t &= \frac{m_L(t) + m_H(t)}{2}; \\
 Mean : \quad t &= \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N x_i
 \end{aligned} \tag{4.1}$$

Notably, the terms used in the equations are defined as follows: $\omega_{\text{bg}}(t)$ and $\omega_{\text{fg}}(t)$ represent the probabilities of the background and foreground classes, respectively. The $\sigma_{\text{bg}}^2(t)$ and $\sigma_{\text{fg}}^2(t)$ denote the variances of the background and foreground classes. The terms $m_L(t)$ and $m_H(t)$ are the means of the lower and higher intensity classes, respectively. Finally, N is the total number of pixels, and x_i represents the intensity of the i -th pixel.

After thresholding, we then retain the pixels that are present in at least two of the segmentation maps. In the end, we iterate this step for each spectral band, producing an accurate vessel annotation within the L0 data for each of the spectral band under analysis.

Data Acquisition and Labelling The data acquisition and labeling strategy follows the algorithmic framework in [1]. Initially, task-relevant external data, specifically AIS records, is gathered. Then, L1C data is employed for labeling, as L1C images enable precise visual identification of vessels and extraction of their latitude-longitude coordinates. An advanced image matching algorithm [68] is applied to transfer annotations from L1C to L0. Residual errors from L0-L1C misalignment or band-to-band coregistration issues are minimized through a coarse-to-fine labeling technique.

Two datasets thus constructed from scratch, using VENµS and Sentinel-2 images, covering distinct geographic regions (see Figure 4.4(a)). These datasets target detection and classification tasks, leveraging AIS auxiliary data, including Maritime Mobile Service Identity (MMSI), vessel type, dimensions, status, speed, position, and timestamp. However, AIS time intervals do not provide

real-time ship data due to vendor storage policies, leading to potential unreliability in areas with dense traffic, low navigation activity, or narrow waterways.

Figure 4.4: Geographical coverage of the S-2 and VENµS datasets (a). Histograms show bounding box area and aspect ratio distributions for training, validation, and test sets of S-2 (b) and VENµS (c).

4.2.1 Datasets Compiled

Vessel Detection from Sentinel-2 Raw (VDS2Raw) Building upon a previous work [30], where the first raw multispectral dataset (VDS2Raw) was introduced, the methodology outlined in THRawS [200] was employed. A reference dataset of Sentinel-2 L1C products containing vessels was identified, based on the work of Ruiloba et al. [201], which includes Sentinel-2 L1C tiles from 2019, captured in Danish coastal areas.

The dataset was compiled by applying a polygon surrounding the Region of Interest (ROI), covering all ships for each of the eight acquisition days, with sufficient margin to ensure all relevant bands were downloaded. This resulted in the acquisition of 390 L0 granules, which were then decompressed to obtain raw data. For labelling, bands B_i ($i = 2, 3, 4$) were considered, with B_2 serving as the reference for manual annotation. Bounding boxes around each vessel were manually drawn using the coarse spatial coregistration technique from [200]. Missing pixels, resulting from coregistration, were filled from adjacent granules when possible; otherwise, the areas were cropped, yielding granules with varying pixel areas.

Out of 390 downloaded granules, 166 were selected for further analysis and split into training (105), validation (27), and test (34) sets, with 483, 119, and 93 annotations, respectively. The

average granule size is approximately $2588.9 \text{ px} \times 1669.4 \text{ px}$, and the mean bounding box size is $13.59 \text{ px} \times 15.67 \text{ px}$.

In contrast to the preliminary version, VDS2Raw Official is now presented. Enhancements include the integration of additional AIS records provided by the Danish government³, with second-level accuracy, improving temporal resolution. Additionally, the B_8 band was incorporated, providing a 10m spatial resolution, enabling more detailed object detection. These improvements offer a more comprehensive and precise dataset, facilitating robust scientific applications.

The vessel width and length distribution, as well as vessel classes, are presented in Figure 4.5 (a). Most vessels are observed to have a width below 10m and a length around 25m. The dominant classes, *Cargo*, *Tanker*, and *Fishing*, are shown in Figure 4.6 (a). Due to the spatial resolution of S-2, the VDS2Raw dataset presents a greater challenge compared to VDVRaw.

Vessel Detection from VEN μ S Raw (VDVRaw) The Vessel Detection from VEN μ S Raw (VDVRaw) dataset was developed using a ROI that covers the open sea near the port of Ashdod, Israel (Figure 4.4 (a)). Imagery of this region was taken by the VEN μ S MSI roughly every two days around 8:30 UTC during the initial phase of its scientific mission. AIS data for vessels in the ROI was obtained from a maritime analytics provider⁴. A key limitation of this dataset is that only one AIS record per vessel was available per day within the ROI, typically logged at midnight UTC. As a result, no information was available about the vessel’s exact position when the spacecraft captured the image of the region.

Nonetheless, vessels frequently stay anchored for long periods, often several days, while awaiting clearance from port authorities to enter the port. This practice allows port authorities to efficiently manage maritime traffic, taking into account both ship characteristics and current conditions [202]. For this study, a database was compiled, comprising 3,827 vessels labeled with bounding boxes in 282 multispectral images collected during VEN μ S’ first mission phase. Of these vessels, 2,733 (71.4%) have corresponding AIS records found in the MarineTraffic database. The vessels are categorized into 18 distinct types. Figure 4.6 (b) presents the length and width statistics for vessels in the training, validation, and test datasets, while Figure 4.6 (b) shows a bar chart of the different categories listed in the AIS database. As depicted, the dataset is skewed heavily toward the *General Cargo* class, resulting in most vessels being about 100 meters in length and 15 meters in width across all datasets.

Flags (F_l) were added to denote different vessel features: presence of visible wakes ($F_l=1$), cloud cover ($F_l=3$), vessel location at the image border ($F_l=2$), and proximity to other vessels ($F_l=7$). These flags can be combined to provide more detailed information about each vessel.

The distribution of vessels by flag type is as follows: 3,264 vessels (85.3%) had no specific flags, 457 vessels (11.9%) showed visible wakes, 21 vessels (0.5%) were positioned on the image border, 74 vessels (1.9%) were obscured by cloud cover, 4 vessels (0.1%) were near other vessels, 1 vessel (0.0%) had both cloud and wake flags, and 6 vessels (0.2%) had both proximity and wake flags.

This process ultimately produced a detailed dataset that integrates AIS data along with additional vessel characteristics.

³<https://web.ais.dk/aisdata/>

⁴MarineTraffic: www.marinetraffic.com

Figure 4.5: The AIS characteristics of the raw vessel datasets analyzed through various statistical visualizations. Histograms and kernel density estimates of length and width distributions are presented across training, validation, and test subsets for both the VDS2Raw (a) and VDVRaw (b) datasets.

Dataset Comparison The two datasets cover different geographic regions and time periods, with distinct vessel type distributions (Figure 4.6). Despite analyzing similar spectral bands (Figure 4.2), their characteristics differ. While the dominant vessel types in VDS2Raw are *Tanker* and *Cargo*, it includes a wider range of vessel types like *Sailing*, *SAR*, and *Fishing*, due to different AIS records. VEN μ S has better spatial resolution than Sentinel-2 MSI, but with higher noise and artifacts. The AIS data for VDVRaw, collected only once per day, contrasts with the timing precision of VDS2Raw. This study does not focus on performance differences between models but highlights their behavior when applied to raw data from distinct tasks. A comparison of the two datasets is summarized in Table 4.1.

Table 4.1: Comparative table showing the differences between the VDS2Raw and VDVRaw datasets.

Attribute	Sentinel-2	VEN μ S
Dataset Name	VDS2Raw (Official)	VDVRaw
Source	Raw granules from Sentinel-2 products	Images from VEN μ S satellite sensors
Spatial Resolution	10m	5.3m at Nadir
Spectral Bands	B_2, B_3, B_4, B_8	12, spanning visible to NIR
Reference Dataset	Ruiloba et al.[201]	From scratch
Area of Focus	Danish Fjords	Port of Ashdod, Israel
Time Period	2019	2018 to end of October 2020
Labeling	Manual, Polygons	Semi-Manual, Bounding Boxes
AIS Included	Yes	Yes
Sample Size (Avg)	2588.9 px \times 1669.4 px	2798 px \times 1929 px
BBox Size (Avg)	13.59 px \times 15.67 px	-
Reference Band	B_2	B_5
Coregistration Technique	Coarse Spatial (Meoni et al. (2023))	Affine Transform (SIFT)
N. Samples	166 (105 Training, 27 Validation, 34 Testing)	284 (140 Training, 85 Validation, 57 Testing)
N. Annotations	695 (483 Training, 119 Validation, 93 Testing)	3.827 (1921 Training, 1061 Validation, 845 Testing)

Figure 4.6: The AIS characteristics of the raw vessel datasets analyzed through various statistical visualizations. Bar plots (a) and (b) illustrate the frequency distribution of each vessel category within the VDS2Raw and VDVRaw datasets, respectively.

AIS Records AIS records are essential for tracking maritime vessels, but they present several challenges. Firstly, data providers typically sample AIS messages at intervals of several minutes, leading to gaps in continuous tracking and historical AIS records are often maintained only with a low frequency, further limiting their effectiveness for retrospective analysis. Secondly, raw multi-spectral imagery used for georeferencing can be imprecise, further complicating the task of accurately locating vessels. Thirdly, AIS messages themselves can be corrupted, falsified, or contain erroneous information as highlighted by [203] and [204]. These issues collectively contribute to significant difficulties in matching labelled ship locations with those indicated by AIS data. Given that the AIS data in the two datasets differs significantly in temporal sampling, two distinct strategies were employed to address the matching problem.

For the VDS2Raw (v2) dataset, which features a high sampling rate, a structured multi-step approach was implemented. In the first step, metadata is extracted to facilitate temporal and geographical filtering of the AIS data. This step retains the useful AIS records, thereby focusing only on the most relevant data points. In the second step, a cost matrix is constructed based on a weighted combination of perpendicular and Euclidean distances between the AIS points and the bounding box centers. The weights of this matrix have been further adjusted to account the navigational status of the vessels, giving more importance to the vessel in movement. Then, an Hungarian algorithm [205] is systematically applied to optimally assign MMSIs to the bounding box centers for each image granule. Notably, to ensure consistency across all image granules, each MMSI is uniquely assigned to a single bounding box. The assignment results have been stored and visually inspected to further verify the correctness of the matches.

It is important to state that, during the association process, we encountered instances where a single MMSI was a candidate for different bounding boxes in near, but different, granules. Given also the complexities of handling densely trafficked areas, we deliberately avoided re-matching the unmatched bounding boxes with the globally-stored unmatched MMSIs. Instead, we preferred to

focus on determining the best association between a unique MMSI and multiple bounding box candidates within the current set of processed granules. This decision is motivated by a lack of absolute trust in the AIS data due to the aforementioned issues.

For the VDVRaw dataset, featuring only one daily record, the AIS data was associated with the vessels based on a spatial and temporal criteria. Spatially, AIS data points were selected within a 300-meter radius of the vessel’s center in the L1C image, ensuring spatial alignment. Temporally, to address the limitation of AIS data providing only one daily record around midnight Coordinated Universal Time (UTC), a temporal window was applied, including records from the day the L1C image was captured, as well as the day before and after. The broader range improved the chances of accurately matching the AIS record to the vessel’s position in the image. This dual approach of combining spatial proximity with a flexible temporal range ensured that the vessel’s position closely matched the corresponding AIS records. This simple but effective approach was adopted because many vessels in the database remained stationary for extended periods. Nonetheless, any discrepancies were further resolved through visual inspection to ensure accurate matching.

As a final note, we found it particularly convenient to compile the AIS data directly within the COCO annotation file [149]. We insert the MMSI, information about vessel’s type and rout inside the annotation attribute of each vessel annotated in the file. We named this extended format as AISCOCO.

4.2.2 Methodology

The proposed methodology enhances MSA by leveraging satellite data and DL techniques for vessel detection. The processing begins with band-to-band registration, as in Chapter 2. For Sentinel-2 (S-2), a global, statistically-based CSC registration method is employed [1]. This method is effective for S-2, but VEN μ S imagery posed challenges due to optical distortions at the borders, resulting in a registration error exceeding 5 pixels. To address this, a SIFT-based non-linear registration approach [60] was utilized, leveraging keypoint matching for more precise alignment of spectral bands.

For vessel detection, the methodology adopts VarifocalNet (VFNet) [206], a dense object detector that combines the anchor-free FCOS framework [207] with Adaptive Training Sample Selection (ATSS) [208]. This approach refines bounding boxes without predefined anchor boxes, which are critical for detecting small, variable-scale objects like ships. The backbone of VFNet employs ResNet-18 [209], a lightweight convolutional neural network, for feature extraction. Additionally, a Feature Pyramid Network (FPN) [150] module is integrated to address the multi-scale characteristics of vessels. A key feature of VFNet is its star-shaped deformable convolution layers [206], which refine bounding box predictions by capturing spatial context from background sea regions, improving detection accuracy, particularly in challenging environments.

In summary, the processing chain consists of:

1. **Band-to-Band Registration**, ensuring pixel-level alignment across multispectral bands.
2. **Vessel Detection**, employing VarifocalNet for accurate detection of ships using anchor-free, deformable convolution techniques. The network architecture representation is depicted in the Figure 4.7 in all of its parts.

Figure 4.7: VFNet Architecture description comprehensive of encoder, FPN neck, and head layers devoted to bounding box regression and classification. The star-shaped deformable convolution in the heads employs a coarse-to-fine refinement of the bounding box proposals without the need of prior anchor boxes.

The proposed methodology successfully addresses challenges in maritime detection tasks by optimizing for energy efficiency, multi-scale feature learning under varying imaging conditions.

4.2.3 Experimental Results

This section evaluates the model’s performance on the custom datasets using single and multi-band inputs. Table 4.2 summarizes the evaluation, optimization, and training techniques applied. Key components include the system setup, hyperparameter tuning, data augmentation, and training strategies to improve model generalization.

Table 4.2: Summary of Model Evaluation, Optimization, and Training Techniques

Setting	Description
System Setup	Linux-based system, NVIDIA A100 GPU (40GB), 16-core AMD EPYC-Rome processor at 2.8 GHz.
Hyperparameter Optimization	Grid search optimizing learning rate, epochs, batch size, learning rate schedule
Early Stopping	Patience of 30 epochs
Data Augmentation	Rotations, flips, scaling, shearing to increase variability and model generalization
Input Size	2048×2048
Optimizer	Stochastic Gradient Descent (momentum=0.9, weight decay=0.0001)
Learning Rate Scheduler	Linear warm-up (10% epochs), multi-step decay (factor 0.8 up to 50% of epochs), cosine annealing (final phase)

Sections 4.2.3-4.2.3 explore the advantages and challenges of using single vs. multiple spectral bands. We compare model performance across different spectral bands, focusing on Sentinel-2 bands at 10m resolution and VEN μ S bands at 5m. The goal is to determine when combining bands yields the best results. It’s important to note that performance may vary depending on the dataset characteristics, which we account for by analyzing band behavior in both datasets.

Metrics Vessel identification from raw multispectral data faces challenges due to the lack of calibration, band-to-band registration, and geometric corrections, compounded by atmospheric and sea conditions. Effective evaluation must consider these factors when assessing model performance. The IoU [149] is a widely-used metric for detection tasks, measuring overlap between predicted and actual bounding boxes. Given two shapes A and B , IoU is the ratio of their overlap area to their union area. It helps classify true positives (TP) and false positives (FP) based on a threshold, with related metrics like Precision (P), Recall (R), and F1 score (F_1) derived as:

$$\text{IoU} = \frac{|A \cap B|}{|A \cup B|}, \quad P = \frac{\text{TP}}{\text{TP} + \text{FP}}, \quad R = \frac{\text{TP}}{\text{TP} + \text{FN}}, \quad F_1 = 2 \cdot \frac{P \cdot R}{P + R} \quad (4.2)$$

High Recall is crucial for detecting all vessels, while high Precision minimizes false alarms, ensuring better resource allocation for marine agencies. The F1-score provides a balanced measure of overall model performance, especially relevant for object detection. However, IoU is sensitive to small localization errors, especially for small objects, where slight misalignments can result in large drops in IoU [210, 211]. IoU's scale-invariant property maintains the same value when bounding boxes are uniformly scaled, but this can lead to high variance in results for small objects. This inconsistency complicates model evaluation when detecting smaller objects, as IoU is overly sensitive to minor localization errors.

To address this, the Scale-adaptive IoU (SIoU) [211] introduces a scaling factor p that adapts based on object size, reducing sensitivity to small shifts. SIoU is formulated as:

$$\text{SIoU}(b_1, b_2) = (\text{IoU}(b_1, b_2))^p, \quad \text{where } p = 1 - \gamma \exp\left(-\frac{\sqrt{w_1 h_1 + w_2 h_2}}{\sqrt{2\kappa}}\right) \quad (4.3)$$

Here, b_1 and b_2 are bounding boxes with dimensions w_1, h_1 and w_2, h_2 , respectively. The parameter γ controls the scaling effect, especially for smaller objects, while κ affects how quickly the scaling diminishes with larger objects. SIoU offers a more robust evaluation for small object detection by compensating for localization errors.

Single-Band Analysis

VDVRaw Several factors significantly influence the overall detection accuracy of the studied model, including the spectral response of each band and its associated noise level. Figure 4.8 illustrates these factors for each spectral band. The top panel displays a vessel (Cargo Type) while the bottom panel presents (a) the mean intensity values of vessels and sea surface, (b) the number of HOG [212] features computed at various thresholds (τ), and (c) the Precision, Recall, and F_1 scores evaluated at an SIoU threshold of 0.40. The number of HOG features is considered a measure of the information content within each spectral band. HOG calculated with a 2×2 kernel provide insights into the amount of variability and, consequently, the information contained within the band. By applying different thresholds, we identified a growing pattern in information content from B_1 to B_{12} , as shown in Figure 4.8 (b). Furthermore, to account for the quality of the input information to our model, we indirectly measure the noise by calculating the average spectral response over the sea surface. We then compare it with respect to the average spectral response of vessels in each band, noting an interesting behaviour. Recalling that spectral bands are uncalibrated, the model's performance shows a direct correlation with the number of features

present in the bounding boxes for each band. We measure this “quantity of information” by estimating the number of strong gradients, or changes, in adjacent 2×2 kernels. Specifically, we use the HOG feature descriptor [212] with different thresholds. The two kinds of information, quality (a vessel-to-sea ratio) and quantity (number of strong gradients) enable us to identify a correlation with the model results.

By looking at Figure 4.8(a), it is possible to notice a descending trend in the average spectral response (expressed in DN) of the sea surface moving from lower to higher wavelengths. A similar trend is present in the number of HOG features, this time growing from lower to higher bands. The

Figure 4.8: VEN μ S (VDVRaw) mean intensity (DN) for vessel and sea clutter (a), mean detection metric values (b), and normalized number of HOG features (c) in each spectral band under consideration. Fluctuation of the vessel in the various bands due to the residual co-registration errors.

bands B_1 and B_2 are particularly sensitive to water clarity and depth variations, thus resulting much more affected by noise. Band B_1 shows the lowest performance with a mean Precision of 0.42, mean Recall of 0.54, and mean F_1 Score of 0.47. The bands $\{B_i\}_{i=2}^5$ show a progressive improvement in all metrics, peaking at band B_5 that achieves a mean Precision of 0.75 and a mean Recall of 0.82, resulting in a mean F_1 Score of 0.78. The highest-performing bands are $\{B_i\}_{i=6}^{12}$, which are characterized by similar metric values. Among these, the bands B_{10} , B_{11} , and B_{12} have the highest mean F_1 Scores (around 0.81), and provide the most stable performance across all metrics.

VDS2Raw Consistently with VEN μ S, we assess the performance of the model on the several bands of S-2. Figure 4.9 provides an overview of the key factors for each spectral band under consideration (B_i for $i \in \{2, 3, 4, 8\}$).

Figure 4.9: Sentinel-2 (VDS2Raw) mean intensity for vessel and sea clutter (a), mean detection metric values (b), and normalized number of HOG features (c) in each spectral band under consideration. Fluctuation of the vessel in the various bands due to the residual co-registration errors.

The top panel in Figure 4.9(a) shows the mean intensity values for vessels and sea clutter, which serve as an indicator of the quality of the input data. Similar to our analysis for VEN μ S, the vessel-to-sea ratio is a critical measure for understanding the noise characteristics in each band. Figure 4.9(b) displays, like in the previous paragraph, the mean values of the detection metrics—Precision, Recall, and F_1 score—for each spectral band. It is evident that certain bands consistently outperform others, with bands closer to NIR demonstrating the highest values across all three metrics. This observation aligns with the trend observed for VEN μ S, where NIR bands with a higher number of strong gradient features and better vessel-to-sea ratios yielded superior detection performance. The bottom panel of Figure 4.9(c) shows again the normalized number of HOG features calculated for each band at varying thresholds. As with VEN μ S, the number of HOG features serves as a measure of the information content in each band. Also in this case, a consistent increase in the number of HOG features is observed from increasing wavelengths.

Once again, when examining both the vessel-to-sea ratio and the number of strong HOG features, the duality information content—quality and quantity—enables us to draw a correlation with the model’s detection metrics. Differently from the VEN μ S case, the improvements are less prominent with increasing wavelengths. In particular, the bands B_3 and B_8 scored higher Precision and Recall values, respectively. The results in terms of F_1 score lie consistently around 0.7 for the B_3 , B_4 and B_8 bands.

In conclusion, consistent with the findings from VEN μ S, the Sentinel-2 analysis shows that bands lying in spectral regions close to 800nm demonstrate remarkable results in Precision, Recall, and F_1 scores. This further corroborates the relationship between the number of strong HOG features in bounding boxes for each band and the model’s performance, underscoring the importance of both spectral response and noise levels in vessel detection from raw data.

Multi-Band Results

VDVRaw For VDVRaw, instead of evaluating all possible combinations from the 12 spectral bands of the VEN μ S MSI, we focused on selecting the most dissimilar bands to provide the model

with diverse, complementary information. We used two metrics to quantify band dissimilarity: the PCC and ED. The PCC measures linear relationships between bands, while the ED assesses their geometric separation. Together, these metrics help identify band combinations that maximize informational diversity. The PCC is defined as:

$$\rho_{B_i B_j} = \frac{\text{cov}(B_i, B_j)}{\sigma_{B_i} \sigma_{B_j}}, \quad (4.4)$$

where $\rho_{B_i B_j}$ is the correlation coefficient between bands B_i and B_j , $\text{cov}(B_i, B_j)$ is their covariance, and σ_{B_i} , σ_{B_j} are their standard deviations. The ED between bands B_i and B_j is:

$$d(B_i, B_j) = \sqrt{\sum_{k=1}^n (B_{i,k} - B_{j,k})^2}, \quad (4.5)$$

where $d(B_i, B_j)$ is the distance, and $B_{i,k}$, $B_{j,k}$ are the k -th elements of B_i and B_j .

The analysis focused only on the bounding boxes around vessel structures to ensure relevant regions were considered. Figure 4.10 shows the dissimilarity matrices obtained using PCC and ED, illustrating the dissimilarity between spectral bands to guide the selection of the most informative ones.

Figure 4.10: Dissimilarity matrices obtained over the VDVRaw dataset (bbox only): PCC (left) and ED (right).

Based on the dissimilarities identified, we selected various sets of band combinations to optimize the model’s performance. In doing so, we intentionally excluded lower-performing bands identified in previous analyses to focus on combinations that maximize the diversity of information provided to the model. This selective approach is designed to enhance the model’s ability to differentiate and detect features more effectively by leveraging the most distinct and informative spectral bands.

For two-band combinations, three pairs emerged as particularly significant: B_5 (visible) with B_8 (visible), B_5 (visible) with B_{10} (near-infrared) and B_5 (visible) with B_{12} (near-infrared). These pairs were notable for their distinct spectral information, making them effective in distinguishing between various features within the data. The strength of these combinations lies in their simplicity and ease of implementation, which can be highly beneficial in applications requiring quick, preliminary analysis. However, the reliance on only two bands may limit the breadth of spectral variation captured, potentially overlooking subtler features that could be detected with additional bands.

For this reason, we identified two other sets of three-band combinations: B_3 , B_4 , and B_7 (all visible

RGB) as well as B_5 (visible) with B_{10} and B_{11} (both NIR). The strength of these combinations is their ability to capture a wider range of spectral variation, thus offering more variegated insights into the structures of vessels under analysis. Finally, for four-band combinations, two key sets were highlighted: B_3 , B_4 , and B_7 (all visible) with B_{11} (near-infrared), as well as B_3 , B_5 , and B_7 (visible) with B_{11} (near-infrared). These combinations are particularly valuable as they offer a comprehensive view of the spectral characteristics, enabling a deeper and more detailed understanding of the data.

We evaluated the different band combinations using the same strategy applied to the individual bands, with the results presented in Table 4.3.

Table 4.3: VEN μ S (VDVRaw) evaluation metrics computed for different spectral band combinations: Precision, Recall, and F_1 score for detection.

Spectral Bands	Precision	Recall	F_1
B_{10}	0.82 (± 0.01)	0.87 (± 0.00)	0.85 (± 0.00)
B_5B_8	0.80 (± 0.01)	0.86 (± 0.00)	0.83 (± 0.00)
B_5B_{10}	0.81 (± 0.01)	0.86 (± 0.00)	0.84 (± 0.00)
B_5B_{12}	0.81 (± 0.01)	0.87 (± 0.00)	0.84 (± 0.01)
$B_5B_{10}B_{11}$	0.84 (± 0.01)	0.86 (± 0.01)	0.85 (± 0.01)
$B_3B_4B_7$	0.85 (± 0.00)	0.87 (± 0.00)	0.86 (± 0.00)
$B_3B_4B_7B_{11}$	0.84 (± 0.01)	0.87 (± 0.00)	0.86 (± 0.00)
$B_3B_5B_7B_{11}$	0.85 (± 0.00)	0.88 (± 0.00)	0.86 (± 0.00)

In general, results show how the performance of models utilizing multiple bands is superior to those using a single band. Among the double-band combinations, B_5B_8 and B_5B_{10} performed comparably, achieving precision values of 0.80 (± 0.01) and 0.81 (± 0.01), respectively. However, the B_5B_{12} combination exhibited a slightly higher recall of 0.87 (± 0.00), leading to a superior F_1 score of 0.84 (± 0.01). Moving to multi-band combinations, the triple-band setup $B_3B_4B_7$ recorded the highest precision at 0.85 (± 0.00), indicating a high degree of accuracy in detection while minimizing false positives. However, the 4-band combinations, such as $B_3B_4B_7B_{11}$ and $B_3B_5B_7B_{11}$, demonstrated a balanced performance across all metrics, with recall values of 0.87 (± 0.00) and 0.88 (± 0.00), respectively. Notably, $B_3B_5B_7B_{11}$ achieved the highest metric values among all combinations, suggesting its effectiveness in comprehensive detection with fewer missed instances.

However, it must be noted that although the application of multiple spectral bands yields performance improvements, these gains ($\approx 2\%$) are not substantial enough to justify the onboard implementation of a co-registration technique. When a resource constrained environment is concerned, such as the one equipped onboard a cubesat, these improvements are traded with an increased power consumption and delays in processing time.

VDS2Raw Complementary to the analysis performed for VEN μ S, we evaluate different spectral band combination for VDS2Raw, reporting the results in the Table 4.4, which summarizes the detection metrics for various double and triple spectral band combinations.

Among the double band combinations, B_3B_8 shows slightly better performance in terms of Precision (0.64), Recall (0.85) and F_1 Score (0.74). The triple band combinations are in general better performing than the double combinations across all metrics. The combination $B_2B_3B_8$ (blue, green, and near-infrared) consistently yields the best results, achieving the highest Precision (0.68), Recall

(0.81), and F_1 Score (0.74), although the Recall rate is not the highest overall. This indicates that incorporating the near-infrared band B_8 with the visible bands B_2 and B_3 enhances the model’s ability to detect features more accurately. The combination $B_2B_4B_8$ (blue, red, and near-infrared) and $B_2B_3B_4$ (blue, green, and red) also perform well, with F_1 Scores of 0.70 and 0.72, respectively, suggesting that adding the third spectral band improves overall performance. However, they are slightly less effective than $B_2B_3B_8$, emphasizing the importance of the near-infrared band in improving detection accuracy.

In conclusion, adding a near-infrared band to visible bands resulted in improvements in performance, and our findings demonstrate that using a triple band combination, particularly the $B_2B_3B_8$, is more effective for detection tasks than double band combinations. We argue that this is primarily due to the increased spectral diversity and complementary information provided. Compared to the best single band, B_8 , the improvement in performance evaluated in Precision is significant. Notwithstanding, the improvement is again negligible in terms of a more balanced metric such as F_1 score (0.74 vs. 0.70).

Table 4.4: Sentinel-2 (VDS2Raw) evaluation metrics computed for different spectral band combinations: Precision, Recall, and F_1 score for detection.

Spectral Bands	Precision	Recall	F_1
B_8	0.59 (± 0.08)	0.85 (± 0.03)	0.70 (± 0.07)
B_2B_4	0.55 (± 0.04)	0.75 (± 0.02)	0.63 (± 0.03)
B_2B_3	0.50 (± 0.06)	0.77 (± 0.03)	0.61 (± 0.05)
B_2B_8	0.56 (± 0.05)	0.74 (± 0.03)	0.64 (± 0.04)
B_3B_8	0.64 (± 0.06)	0.85 (± 0.02)	0.74 (± 0.05)
B_4B_8	0.62 (± 0.05)	0.83 (± 0.02)	0.71 (± 0.04)
$B_2B_4B_8$	0.65 (± 0.03)	0.76 (± 0.02)	0.70 (± 0.02)
$B_2B_3B_4$	0.66 (± 0.09)	0.80 (± 0.08)	0.72 (± 0.09)
$B_2B_3B_8$	0.68 (± 0.02)	0.81 (± 0.04)	0.74 (± 0.02)

4.2.4 Onboard Proof-of-Concept

The section first discusses the practical challenges of applying the model in a real-world scenario, particularly focusing on the onboard implementation, highlighting the practical results of the deployed system.

As demonstrated earlier, owing to the marginal improvements in multiple band combinations, thus we select a single band, i.e. B_8 for Sentinel-2 and the B_{10} for VEN μ S.

The model’s robustness when facing different sensor conditions is evaluated in the first part of this section. Then, the practical implementation details are discussed, and finally, power and latency results are presented.

Impact of SNR and MTF

Critical insights can be drawn when benchmarking models under different sensor characteristics, specifically the MTF and SNR. This information is crucial as the onboard data distribution can shift significantly from the one faced during training, as remarked in [41]. We evaluate the effect of this domain gap by analysing the model behaviour against different sensor working conditions.

The optical system can be modelled using the MTF and SNR to simulate the sensor’s spatial re-

sponse and noise levels. The MTF aims to replicate the spatial domain response of the image (i.e., emulating the signal recorded by the instrument detector element), which is closely associated with the instrument characteristics, such as pixel size and system F-number. The MTF filter is thus represented as a two-dimensional kernel with independent across- and along-track parameterizations. By utilizing key instrument parameters (mainly the pixel pitch that determines the sampling frequency and the F-number that determines the cutoff frequency for each band), a two-dimensional MTF kernel of size $n \times n$ is computed [41]. The corresponding Point Spread Function (PSF) kernel is obtained as the inverse Fourier transform of the MTF kernel, and this PSF kernel is convolved with the input image using a sliding-window approach.

Let $M(B_i)$ the MTF amplitude at the Nyquist frequency for each spectral band B_i , the MTF function (expressed in terms of normalized frequency with respect to the Nyquist) can be represented as:

$$MTF(B_i, k) = e^{\ln M(B_i) \cdot k^2} \quad (4.6)$$

The $M(B_i)$ are known for Sentinel-2 ($M_{S2}(B_i) \approx 0.3$ [195]), and for VEN μ S ($M_V(B_{10}) \approx 0.15$ [190]), therefore we can perform a deconvolution of the input image with the source PSF followed by a convolution with the target PSF as in the simulator tool of [41], with a single step adopting the Gaussian hypothesis.

Concerning the noise simulation, an additional noise term (N) is imposed to the raw images to account for SNR conditions, following again the formulation by [41]:

$$N(i, j, b_n) = \frac{L_{ref}(b_n)}{SNR(b_n)} \cdot \mathcal{N}(0, 1), \quad (4.7)$$

where $\mathcal{N}(0, 1)$ is a Gaussian variable with zero mean and unit standard deviation, and L_{ref} the reference radiance. Notably, the Equation (4.7) must be modified from the work of [41] to address raw data since the information is stored as DNs. Therefore, instead of a reference radiance, we adopt a DN_{ref} of 100 for both VEN μ S and Sentinel-2 imagery. We impose this additional noise term on the existing noise, starting from a SNR value of 174 (theoretical SNR ratio for Sentinel-2 at the B_8 band); we assume the same initial value also for VEN μ S.

Under the hypothesis of this modelling framework, we apply varying levels of SNR and MTF to evaluate the model's robustness and generality. The results, displayed in Figure 4.11, illustrate the detection metrics: precision, recall, and F_1 score. As shown in the graphs, the left panel displays results for the VDS2Raw dataset, while the right panel shows results for VDVRaw. The results indicate that lower MTF values—leading to increased image blurring—decrease the detection performance, with precision metric being the most affected among the three.

At higher SNR rates, evidence also shows that the S-2 model is much more influenced by MTF variations, mainly due to the lower spatial resolution. An interesting behaviour is noted for both models: lower MTF values shift the plateau from which model performance begins to decline rapidly. This can be attributed to the fact that lower MTF values act as a median filter, thus mitigating the noise and thereby reducing the number of false alarms. In summary, for relatively low SNR values, having a lower MTF is advantageous.

Regarding the SNR, lower values, which correspond to increased noise (as illustrated in the top and bottom panels of Figure 4.11 for Sentinel-2 and VEN μ S imagery, respectively), lead to reduced detector performance. The results highlight again that VDVRaw is more resilient to noise due to

Figure 4.11: Detection performance metrics (precision, recall, and F_1 score) across varying levels of MTF and SNR for the datasets VDS2Raw (left panel) and VDVRaw (right panel). The top and bottom panels show the impact of different SNR values on Sentinel-2 and VEN μ S raw tiles, respectively.

the higher spatial resolution of the sensor, whereas the model trained on VDS2Raw demonstrates degraded performance.

Onboard Implementation

Benchmarking tests were conducted on a Raspberry Pi 4B (Quad core Cortex-A72 ARM v8 64-bit SoC @ 1.5GHz), a popular low-power device, coupled with the Intel[®] NCS2 connected through USB bus. The NCS2 features the Intel[®] Movidius[™] Myriad[™] X VPU. This chip is designed to accelerate deep learning tasks at the edge, featuring 16 programmable 128-bit VLIW Vector Processors and can execute over 4 trillion operations per second (TOPS).

To enable onboard deployment, several modifications were made to the detection model. The input dimensions were reduced to optimise memory usage, aligning with the memory constraints of the VPU. As this VPU does not natively support deformable convolutions, the star-shaped deformable convolutions were replaced with a custom-developed module. More in-depth, we introduce the RADC module. The RADC module, drawn in Figure 4.12, integrates skip connections with dilated convolutions at multiple dilation scales.

For each dilated convolutional block with dilation d_i , the output \mathbf{X}_i is given by:

$$\mathbf{X}_i = \text{ReLU}(\mathbf{X} *_{d_i} \mathbf{W}_i + \mathbf{b}_i) + \mathbf{X} \quad (4.8)$$

where \mathbf{X} is the input tensor, $*_{d_i}$ denotes the dilated convolution with dilation rate d_i , \mathbf{W}_i represents the weights of the i -th dilated convolutional layer, \mathbf{b}_i is the bias of the i -th dilated convolutional layer, and $\text{ReLU}(\cdot)$ is the Rectified Linear Unit activation function. Subsequently, the Channel

Figure 4.12: Proposed RADC module integrates skip connections with dilated convolutions at multiple dilation scales to enhance feature extraction across various receptive fields. The module also incorporates a channel attention mechanism to dynamically re-weight the channels on the last layer of the module.

Attention Module (CAM) computes an attention map \mathbf{A} that re-weights the channels of the output:

$$\mathbf{A} = \sigma(\mathbf{X}_3 * \mathbf{W}_{\text{att}}) \quad (4.9)$$

where $\sigma(\cdot)$ is the sigmoid activation function, and \mathbf{W}_{att} represents the weights of the attention layer. The attention map \mathbf{A} is applied to the output of the last dilated convolutional block:

$$\mathbf{X}_{\text{att}} = \mathbf{X}_3 \odot \mathbf{A} \quad (4.10)$$

The different dilation rates (d_i where $i \in [2,4,8]$) favour learning multi-scale feature representation by greatly enlarging the receptive fields at different levels, thereby helping the modelling of complex sea surface distributions. The CAM layer further refines the feature maps, enhancing the model’s ability to focus on the most important channels for vessels and the sea surface.

This new version of the model built on top of VFNet—termed RADCNet—is then trained using automatic mixed-precision technique. Upon completing the training phase, the model is converted into its Intermediate Representation (IR) using the OpenVINO framework, utilizing the 16-bit floating-point format. This conversion is necessitated by the VPU’s limitation to 16-bit floating-point precision.

RADCNet closely matches the original VFNet across all metrics, maintaining high precision, recall, and F_1 scores, as shown in Table 4.5.

In terms of parameter count, RADCNet exhibits a modest increase of approximately +3 million parameters, primarily attributable to the introduction of the RADC module. However, in terms of throughput, RADCNet substantially surpasses VFNet, achieving a frame rate of 18 images per second compared to VFNet’s 14 images per second. Latency measurements were conducted over 2000 iterations, with 5 warmup iterations, on the Linux system detailed in Table 4.2. These results highlight the significant influence of memory access costs and demonstrate RADCNet’s competitive performance, underscoring its suitability for deployment in resource-constrained environments.

Table 4.5: Comparison of Precision, Recall, F_1 score, number of parameters, and FPS between VFNet and RADCNet models on VDS2Raw (B_8 band) and VDVRaw (B_{10} band) datasets. Despite being quantized, RADCNet shows minimal performance degradation. [Benchmark computed using 2000 iterations with a warmup of 5]

Model	Dataset	Precision	Recall	F_1	Params (M)	FPS (img/s)
VFNet	VDS2Raw	0.59 (\pm 0.08)	0.85 (\pm 0.03)	0.70 (\pm 0.07)	19.68	14.9
RADCNet	VDS2Raw	0.63 (\pm 0.05)	0.81 (\pm 0.04)	0.71 (\pm 0.04)	22.04	18.0
VFNet	VDVRaw	0.82 (\pm 0.01)	0.87 (\pm 0.00)	0.85 (\pm 0.00)	19.68	14.9
RADCNet	VDVRaw	0.80 (\pm 0.02)	0.84 (\pm 0.03)	0.82 (\pm 0.02)	22.04	18.0

Power and Latency Benchmarks

This subsection presents the timing and power consumption results of the on-device tests. Latency was first evaluated on single models, then the entire processing chain, including pre-processing (tiling, normalization), and inference has been benchmarked.

Figure 4.13 presents the evaluation conducted on the detection model, whereas Figure 4.14 displays the power consumption of the edge-AI hardware.

Several batch size dimensions have been considered along with different input sizes. The results are averaged over one thousand iterations using the benchmark tool of OpenVINO. The average inference time is shown in Figure 4.13(a). Additionally, the throughput has been estimated and reported in Figure 4.13(b). In the end, the graph of Figure 4.13(c) considers the input size of 2048×2048 pixel image and applies the Slicing Aided Hyper Inference (SAHI) approach [213] to perform a complete inference using smaller tiles.

Regarding power consumption, Figure 4.14 illustrates the power consumption profile of the Intel[®] NCS2 connected via USB to the Raspberry Pi 4B. The device executes inference tasks. Specifically, subplots (a), (b), and (c) display the power consumption for the detection model with input dimensions of 256×256 for batch sizes of 1 and 2, and 352×352 for a batch size of 4, respectively. In the proposed configuration, the NCS2 operates with a baseline idle power consumption of 0.66W. Power measurements are sampled at intervals of $\Delta t = 10$ ms using the FNIRSI FNB58 USB tester. The number of inference operations conducted is set to 1000. In the end of the manuscript, we present

Figure 4.13: Benchmark of detection model compiled using OpenVINO: graph (a) presents the average latency (ms), graph (b) illustrates the average throughput (FPS), and graph (c) displays the total inference time for an image with dimensions 2048×2048 pixels.

Figure 4.14: Graph displaying the power consumption of the Intel[®] Neural Compute Stick 2 (NCS2) connected through USB bus to the Raspberry Pi 4B. The device performs separate inferences using the detection model (graphs (a), (b), and (c), having an input shape of 256x256 with batch size 1 and 2, and 352x352 with batch size 4, respectively). In the proposed setup, the NCS2 consumes 0.66W in its idle state, data sampling is performed with a $\Delta t = 10$ ms using the FNIRSI FNB58 USB tester, and the number of inferences selected is 1000.

an end-to-end demonstration of our system, processing a complete acquisition with results averaged over 10 iterations. The pre-processing phase is highly efficient, with an average duration of 0.49 seconds, suggesting that tasks such as normalization and resizing are not the primary computational bottlenecks. Conversely, the detection inference stage, tasked with identifying vessel locations, is the most time-consuming step, with an average execution time of 22.97 seconds, underscoring the complexity of the detection process.

These performance metrics indicate that the detection stage consumes the majority of computational resources. Notably, our system’s execution time is approximately double that of comparable benchmarks, which we attribute to our Python-based implementation as opposed to the more optimized C++ implementations used in the benchmark tools.

4.3 Detection of Ship Wakes

A critical role in monitoring and understanding human activities at sea is held by the detection of moving vessels, a challenging task that can be accomplished, in specific conditions, by inspecting their long wakes left in the sea. The wake generated by moving ships is rich in information regarding the vessel and their instantaneous state, and—since ship wakes extend for kilometers—wakes can be detected also in low and medium resolution data. Their detection, recognition, and reconstruction can significantly contribute to the improvement of MSA [214] since they: (a) provide additional information about the route, i.e., ship velocity and heading, and (b) enable the detection of ships not imaged in SAR images due to their motion, materials, and sizes.

Indeed, first attempts of detecting ship wakes were deeply investigated on the coherent imaging system of the SAR, owing to its unique characteristics. In recent years, researchers are increasingly using optical imagers for their true-color images and higher spatial resolution, which improve scene clarity and make them ideal for surveillance. In contrast, SAR imagery, while advantageous in all-weather and day-night conditions, is prone to speckle noise, which can be mitigated through techniques like multi-looking, though at the cost of image sharpness. Additionally, many distinctive features of ship wakes in SAR images become less visible or are difficult to discern, especially at lower incidence angles, where these features often blend with the surrounding sea clutter [215]. This limitation reduces SAR's effectiveness in detecting fine wake structures, further contributing to the growing preference for optical systems in specific surveillance and monitoring applications.

The appearance of wakes can vary significantly based on factors like ship speed, hull shape, orientation, sea conditions, wind speed, and in case of radars, radar signal wavelength, and observation geometry. In addition, their aspect may resemble other phenomena such as sea surface films [216]. Traditional techniques for detecting ship wakes in SAR imagery rely on the assumption that the wake structure is composed of distinct, linear patterns (Figure 4.15a). As the Figure 4.15b displays, a ship wake in a SAR image can be visualized as a fan-shaped arrangement of bright, linear features converging towards a central dark line, representing the turbulent wake, along with narrow-V wakes and the characteristic Kelvin wake pattern [217].

(a) Wake Structure.

(b) Wake observed in X-band SAR image [31].

Figure 4.15: Pictorial representation of the ship wake components (a) and its SAR imaging: (1) turbulent wake, characterized by low backscatter intensity; (2), (3) bright, diverging arms of the narrow-V wake; (3), (4) boundary lines of the Kelvin wake.

Based on this assumption, the wake detection problem is typically addressed with domain transforms such as Radon [218, 219] or Hough [220]. In this regard, many studies have been conducted on the detection of ships by wake using SAR images by the exploitation of the RT [221–224], often in combination with threshold-based techniques like Constant False Alarm Rate (CFAR). These “traditional” methods, however, suffered from high false positive rates, due to the interference of sea clutter, and were not robust against specific cases like, wake detection near coasts [225]. Other studies attempted to estimate ship speeds from SAR images by analyzing the shape of Kelvin wakes, which manifest as V-shaped bright or dark lines. They also examined the azimuth offsets between the wake’s vertex and the ship’s hull [225–227].

Concerning optical imagers, in 2022, Li et al. [228] published a useful review of hull and wake detection methods for infrared remote sensing imagery. The information in that review serves to contextualise the field and its evolution in the context of optical remote sensing and DL-based detection up to the year of publication.

Radon Transform A RT-based approach is a deterministic method which models ship wakes as linear features [218]. The RT of a two-dimensional function $f(x, y)$ is defined as the integral of $f(x, y)$ along a straight line parameterized by the distance ρ from the origin and the angle θ . Mathematically, this is expressed as:

$$R_f(\rho, \theta) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(x, y) \delta(\rho - x \cos \theta - y \sin \theta) dx dy \quad (4.11)$$

where θ represents the angle of the line with respect to the horizontal axis, ρ denotes the perpendicular distance from the origin to the line, and $\delta(\cdot)$ is the Dirac delta function, which ensures the integration is carried out along the line defined by ρ and θ .

In practice, the RT maps lines in the image domain to points in the Radon domain: each line is thus transformed into a distinct peak either dark or bright. Since ship wakes are characterised by clusters of lines consisting in a multitude of pixels, Radon domain of a ship wake will consequently involve clusters of dark or bright spots. To address this limitation, [229] introduces a filtering method based on a stochastic matched filtering approach, designed to maximize the SNR. Meanwhile, [230] proposes a detection algorithm that extrapolates linear features while isolating and suppressing false alarms.

Nevertheless, it is important to acknowledge that the RT rearranges a line detection problem into a point detection problem, effectively disregarding non-linear features in the observed patterns, such as the corners produced by Kelvin wakes. Furthermore, it is important to underscore that the assumption of representing wakes as linear features may not be generally applicable. Therefore, this assumption makes the method unable to detect all potential curved wakes and thereby restricts its practical applicability. This is significant for small vessels operating near coastlines, often involved in illicit activities, where sailors frequently alter their direction, producing curved wakes (Figure 4.16). The unpredictable motion of these vessels, denoted as CM-vessels, introduces complexity into the application of RT-based techniques, particularly in dense and dynamic environments where frequent changes in direction are common. For the purposes of this thesis, we define a CM-vessel as any vessel whose heading angle θ changes by at least 25° , i.e., $\Delta\theta \geq 25^\circ$.

The RT technique faces also several other inherent limitations, one being the requirement of remov-

ing or masking of the ship from the image before applying the transform, as clusters of bright or dark pixels in sea clutter can disrupt the computations. This interference is common in maritime environments due to natural surface films that generate similar artifacts, while wakes often vary in shape and brightness due to water noise or signal interference. Finally, one last limitation stems from the need to accurately position the wake vertex at the center of the image tile for precise RT analysis, and furthermore, the RT cannot process tiles containing multiple wakes.

Figure 4.16: An example of a CM-vessel producing a curved ship wake, where Kelvin wakes are observable. Acquisition gathered by Sentinel-2 satellite over the Danish Fjords.

DL-based Wake Detection In contrast to RT-based methods, DL-based techniques emerged as a powerful tool for retrieving ship wakes. Among all Computer Vision (CV) algorithms, OD represents one of the most effective for automatic target recognition [231, 232], aimed at recognizing instances of a predefined set of classes and (e.g. ship, wake, oil spill) and accurately locating them in the image with bounding boxes.

An interesting model came from Xue et al. [233], developing an end-to-end CNN-based detector called WakeNet. Several innovative concepts came from the work, one being the addition of a specific head for regression of the wake tip coordinate and Kelvin arm direction, which smartly employs RT within its structure to highlight linear features. Another interesting idea is the application of a spectral and a multi-scale attention module, which works by exploiting the X-shaped spectral pattern of wakes after the application of Fourier Transform. WakeNet is an anchor-based detector, and was trained on a specifically built dataset the authors called Ship Wake Imagery Mass (SWIM). This dataset contains more than 11.6K optical images of ships and their wakes taken from both space-borne, at very high resolution, and aerial sensing platforms. One interesting thing to note about this dataset is the way annotations are structured. Since the wedge-shaped Kelvin arms are often prominent in optical imagery, the annotation includes both oriented bounding boxes and landmarks, including wake tip coordinates and the directions of the two Kelvin arms.

More recently, in 2024, Liu and Zhao [234] showed an interesting approach to the problem of wake detection. In particular, their focus was on the issue of enhancing their dataset and counteracting the low data availability issue often encountered in wake detection tasks. In particular, they focus on Kelvin wake detection in optical imagery. Firstly, they developed a dataset Gaofen-1 2-m resolution panchromatic images. These optical training images were divided into 224×224 pixel sub-images and were processed before classifying them as either wake samples or natural surface samples. In total, 2124 wake samples were used for training. The authors then used a method

based on linear theory to simulate further samples of Kelvin wakes and enhance their dataset. In particular, they employed a point source perturbation coupled with sea surface slope probability density functions. This theoretical basis allows for the precise modelling of wake characteristics, particularly the specular reflections of sunlight on the wake regions, which are crucial for Kelvin wake identification. They simulated different values of Sun zenith angles, azimuth angles for both the Sun and the sensing platform, and varying speeds of representative motorboat model with specific dimensions (10 m by 3.2 m, with 1 m of draft). They produced 1.4 times the number of the real wake samples to enhance their dataset without losing the features that only the real samples would contain. They used this data to train and test a model based on the GoogLeNet architecture, which employs Inception modules [235].

Methodologies at Comparison As a result of its current constraints, the limited applicability of RT methods hinders the automatic processing of images without human intervention, making it unsuitable for autonomous monitoring systems. Despite these disadvantages, the RT method can differentiate wake components by simply estimating specific merit indices, as originally proposed by [225, 236]. In DL-based methods this recognition is not straightforward and requires careful attention; in this ambit, a viable solution will be demonstrated in the present manuscript.

Given the aforementioned consideration, it is possible to conclude that DL approaches are more suitable for wake detection because: a) they better generalize on different data distributions, thereby not requiring manual tuning, and b) they can capture a more complete representation of relevant pattern information, rather than being limited to linear features.

The approach was initially tested on SAR data, taking advantage of its ability in monitoring ocean surface features [217, 236]. Subsequently, optical data were analyzed, and the models were validated using this different information source. This dual assessment approach ensures a more robust and precise validation of the proposed method.

A comparison of the advantages and disadvantages of the two techniques is summarised in Table 4.6.

Table 4.6: A comparative analysis of the strengths and limitations of RT and OD methods for ship wake detection.

	Radon Transform	Object Detection
<i>Pro</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Allows ship route & velocity estimation 2. Can reconstruct wake components 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Generalisation and robustness 2. Can process large tiles in an autonomous manner 3. Inference speed is faster 4. Scalable architecture to work on embedded systems
<i>Cons</i>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Cannot detect CM-vessels 2. Wake vertex must be at the centre of the tile 3. Ship and other disturbances must be masked 4. Can process only a single wake per tile 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Cannot detect wake components in its base formulation 2. Results not (generally) explainable

4.3.1 Datasets Compiled

SAR Ship Wake Detection (SSWD) The developed SSWD consists of 261 wake chips, each with dimensions of 512×512 pixels, extracted from Interferometric Wide (IW) swath Sentinel-1 SAR imagery acquired in Vertical transmit-Vertical receive (VV) polarization mode.

These images, obtained from the Copernicus Open Access Hub, correspond to Level-1 Ground Range Detected (GRD) products, with a pixel spacing of approximately $10 \text{ m} \times 10 \text{ m}$ (ground range \times azimuth).

The Figure 4.17a summarizes the number of chips acquired in each procurement site of SSWD. The total number of wakes labelled is 291: it is greater than the number of chips since the 12% of chips include more than one wake. Figure 4.17a shows also the statistical distribution of the wake orientation. The relevant angle is computed counter-clockwise with respect to the ground range direction. As Figure 4.17a displays, the dataset covers highly trafficked maritime regions, including the Strait of Gibraltar, Egadi Islands (Italy), the Gulfs of Genoa and Naples (Italy), the English Channel, and Liaodong Bay (China). These sites were carefully selected to maximize the diversity of the dataset, incorporating various ship classes, headings, speeds, and orientations, which refer to the ship's moving direction within the image.

It is evident that the dataset exhibits a balanced distribution: orientations between 0° - 90° and 180° - 270° are almost equally represented as those between 90° - 180° and 270° - 360° . Maintaining a balanced orientation distribution thus enhances model accuracy, supports generalization, and ensures a more robust model training SAR as the sensor's imaging characteristics are orientation-dependent.

After subsetting the data, a conversion to 8-bit depth was carried out by clipping the histogram at 95%. This process involves reducing the range of backscatter values, keeping the most significant portion of the data while discarding the outliers. By clipping the histogram at 95%, the top 5% of intensity values were removed, enhancing contrast in the remaining data. This conversion to 8-bit depth was performed to highlight surface features, such as ship wakes, making them more distinguishable, while also ensuring efficient storage and compatibility for further analysis.

Figure 4.17: SSWD characterisation: (a) statistical distribution of wake chips across various procurement sites and orientation distribution categorized by four quadrants (0° - 90° , 90° - 180° , 180° - 270° , 270° - 360°), and (b) geographic locations of the procurement sites shown on a cartographic map.

Significant attention was paid to the annotations, as incorrect labelling could compromise the accuracy of the dataset. The data annotation process was carried out utilizing polygonal annotations instead of rectangular bounding boxes. When wakes are misaligned with the vertical or horizontal axes, their narrow shape leads to excessive inclusion of surrounding sea within rectangular bounding boxes. Polygonal annotations address this problem by providing more precise boundaries, especially during rotations in the data augmentation process. Moreover, polygonal annotations are more effective for training segmentation models, as they capture the shape of the wake more accurately.

Finally, it is important to emphasize that ships were excluded from the polygonal masks. This exclusion is critical to prevent the incorrect association of features between wakes and bright ships, which is not always the case in practice, such as with go-fast vessels [237] or in instances of large azimuth offsets [238].

Multi-Spectral Ship Wake Detection (MSSWD)

The MSSWD features 50 L2A images gathered by Sentinel-2 satellites. For MSSWD, only the 10 m bands of the MSI have been considered, i.e., B_2 , B_3 , B_4 , and B_8 bands.

The compiled dataset consists of 661 optical image chips containing wakes characterised by different configurations, e.g. single ship wake, multiple ship wakes, false ship wakes (e.g. crests and airplane wakes) and few negative examples of offshore sea clutter with no wakes. Even though the size of the dataset is low in comparison of classical DL datasets, efforts have been concentrated more on the quality of the data rather than on its quantity. The wake chips thus obtained presents several different configurations in which it is possible to distinguish vertical upwards and downwards wakes, horizontal left-headed or right-headed wakes, tilted wakes, but even offshore cluttered sea and false wakes crops have been selected. This key choice was made to introduce the right amount of variety in the dataset, as will be shown in the next subsections. Moreover, MSSWD reflects the real difficulty of the detection problem since images have been collected in congested and crowded scenarios where even clouds are partially occluding the visibility of the features. Finally, data augmentation has been extensively implemented in order to mitigate the small dataset dimension and to further enlarge the variety of the samples.

Concerning data acquisition and labelling, the Danish coasts and fjords were selected due to the free data policy of Denmark AIS data [239, 240]. To the knowledge of the authors, MSSWD is the first dataset of ship wakes containing multi-spectral information and accompanied by coupled AIS information.

Regarding the cropping strategy, each wake chip is characterised by one or more clearly visible ship, large and significant portion of the wake, and also portions of sea clutter. This is because OD needs to sample both foreground and background features for estimating the gradients. Data labelling has been executed by manually annotating the chips with polygonal annotations. This choice leads two major advantages, allowing: the benchmark of instance segmentation frameworks, and a better refinement of the bounding boxes during the data augmentation. The data labelling process is articulated in several steps. Firstly, wakes are identified in optical images by a remote-sensing expert. Secondly, the areas containing ship wakes are cropped and manually annotated. The V-shaped annotation follows the contour of the ship wake, touching the Kelvin wakes when observable. Background complexity and diversity of the scenes is also another important property of MSSWD,

as sea surface presents several sources of clutter, like natural or artificial surface films, upwellings, several types of waves, and other effects generated by local weather condition. Traditional methods of ship and wake detection have shown limitations in discriminating these from clutter, and it is thus important to include them in the dataset for sake of robustness.

As already stated, MSSWD consists of 661 multi-spectral images containing 1059 ship wakes in different configurations. Starting from the AIS data and the image chips cropped with SNAP, QGIS [241] has been utilised to recognise the individual ships on the basis of the day of acquisition, latitude and longitude coordinates, and MMSI. For the purposes of this analysis, only the SOG, COG, and ship categories were considered to portray an overview of the presented MSSWD. The Figure 4.18 reports these distributions.

As expected, the vast majority of ships are cargo-type (54.02%), followed by tankers (14.86%) and passenger vessels (14.46%). Moreover, the table presents an “undefined” percentage related to ship type data unavailability that involves 15 ships of the MSSWD. As previously stated, it was not possible to retrieve AIS data of all ships of the MSSWD, and 561 out of 1059 are “dark” vessels.

There are multiple possible reasons for the presence of these many dark vessels. The most likely possibility is that those ships did not have an AIS transponder onboard, or it was not turned on, and they were thus being non-collaborative. Another possibility is that the AIS data were not updated in an appropriate time. Regardless, the information provided in Figure 4.18 is only related to available instances of AIS data. The shape of the ship wakes depends on various factors, among these, the dimensions of the ships represent a distinctive parameter. Figure 4.18 shows some other characteristics of interest of the ships in the MSSWD. The chart in Figure 4.18 (b) presents the SOG distribution in the MSSWD dataset, showing a wide range of velocities from very slow (~ 2 kn) to fast ships (~ 25 kn). The right chart of Figure 4.18 (c) contains the COG distribution of ships in the MSSWD. Regarding the former, comparison with the detection results will be illustrated in the next sections in order to verify if slow ships are actually detected.

It is intuitively understandable how the formation of the characteristic structures of ship wakes and their visibility in remotely sensed imagery is highly correlated with their SOG. As for the COG, although the graph shows two distinct peaks at 50° and 250° , these do not significantly detract from the diversity of the dataset. The overall coverage of the angular spectrum remains nearly uniform, and any imbalance introduced by these peaks can be mitigated through the use of rotations during training.

Additionally, factors such as ship construction materials and hull shapes remain important considerations in the dataset’s variety. The length-width distribution of ships contained inside MSSWD is reported in Figure 4.19. From the graph, it is possible to understand how the dataset contains ships with different sizes, from ~ 20 to ~ 400 meters of length, and from ~ 5 to ~ 60 meters of width.

Figure 4.18: MSSWD ship type (a), SOG (b), and COG (c) distributions.

Figure 4.19: The length-width distribution of ships within the MSSWD. The dataset features a diverse range of ship sizes, with lengths ranging from approximately 20 meters to 400 meters, and widths varying from around 5 meters to 60 meters.

4.3.2 Experimental Results

Experimental Setup

All the experiments on SSWD are supported by a local machine with the 64-bits Ubuntu 18.04 operating system. The software configuration consisted of python environment, PyTorch 1.9.0 framework, CUDA 10.2, cuDNN 8.1.0. The hardware used include NVIDIA GTX-1060 GPU (6GB memory), Intel[®] i5-8600K CPU @3.60GHz and 16 GB RAM.

Results on SSWD

Faster R-CNN [242], RetinaNet [243], Mask R-CNN [244] and Cascade Mask R-CNN [245] have been benchmarked with different backbones combinations. The utilized baselines include both ResNet-50 and ResNet-101 coupled with: (a) FPN: use ResNet + FPN with standard conv and Fully-Connected (FC) heads for mask and bounding box prediction; (b) ResNet+C4: use ResNet conv4 backbone with conv5 head; (c) DC5 (Dilated-C5): Use a ResNet conv5 backbone with dilations in conv5, and standard conv and FC heads for mask and box prediction, respectively.

A fine-tuning procedure is carried out for all the models on SSWD, evaluating several different pre-training configurations. In particular, both the pre-trained weights of ImageNet [246] and COCO dataset [149] have been fine-tuned but, since ImageNet weights have achieved lower results, they have not been reported. This crucial results highlighted that domain transfer from classification datasets may be sub-optimal because of the large gap between the camera and SAR images.

The fine-tuning has been performed training 5000 epochs with SGD and a learning rate of 0.0005. The training strategy involves early-stopping and weak data augmentation strategy, consisting of resizing, shifting, flipping, and rotating.

The performance of both weights pre-trained with a single epoch, and heavily trained with 12 epochs on COCO has been evaluated, as shown in Table 4.7. The table presents scores for AP, AP₅₀, and AP₇₅. In this case, AP_L is the same as AP, because it was not possible to estimate AP_S and AP_M, indicating that in SSWD, there are not enough small and medium wake instances to compute these metrics accurately. Deeper networks involving ResNet-101 encoder have achieved better performance (by mean +2 ÷ 5% AP) on SSWD. The best backbone combination is ResNet + FPN, followed by slight improvements of ResNet + DC5 against ResNet + C4. In all cases, the model heavily tained on coco have shown the best performance. The model reaching the highest scores in the evaluation metrics is Cascade Mask R-CNN which achieved an AP of 67.63.

Results on a Sentinel-1 product Wake detection is herein discussed for a VV-polarized IW-GRD Sentinel-1 image (Figure 4.20) gathered over the Gulf of La Spezia, Italy. The satellite image is completed by AIS data, acquired by the AIS ground station of La Spezia-Castellana (Station #890) at latitude and longitude of 44.07° North and 9.82° East, respectively, and from an altitude above sea level of about 200 m. Figure 4.20 shows also three scenarios selected in different environments and sea-state conditions: Scenario A illustrates the detection over a condition of the rough sea with surface natural films (Figure 4.21), Scenario B includes an area of quiet sea condition (Figure 4.23), and Scenario C is characterized by areas of wind-speed change (Figure 4.22). It is worth detailing that with the nomenclature surface film are included eddies or other surface currents as used in [216].

Table 4.7: Evaluation of several object detection models on SSWD

Model	B_1	B_2	Pre-Train Epochs	AP	AP_{50}	AP_{75}
Faster R-CNN	ResNet50	C4	12	61.21	95.01	64.26
		DC5	12	60.92	96.92	69.80
		DC5	1	59.97	96.19	71.01
		FPN	12	61.50	98.62	63.44
	ResNet101	C4	12	62.39	98.51	64.88
		DC5	12	61.50	94.28	66.30
FPN		12	63.91	95.07	75.75	
RetinaNet	ResNet50	FPN	1	60.54	94.98	69.59
		FPN	12	62.24	96.59	69.48
	ResNet101	FPN	12	65.27	97.99	71.41
Mask R-CNN	ResNet50	C4	1	61.17	94.09	61.26
		C4	12	60.88	94.59	71.35
		DC5	1	61.10	96.64	63.29
		DC5	12	61.89	96.90	66.49
		FPN	1	60.51	94.98	69.59
	FPN	12	60.95	94.42	65.03	
ResNet101	C4	12	65.91	96.24	78.34	
	DC5	12	65.68	96.66	64.60	
	FPN	12	65.49	99.06	81.18	
Cascade Mask R-CNN	ResNet50	FPN	1	64.07	95.94	70.26
		FPN	12	67.63	95.99	73.15

Figure 4.20: Sentinel-1 GRD (IW) image gathered in VV polarization over La Spezia on 18/07/2020 at 17:14 UTC (latitude-longitude coordinates). Product ID: S1A_IW_GRDH_1SDV_20200718T171436_20200718T171501_033512_03_E220_DEFC.

In order to analyze the detection performance of the best-trained model, i.e. Cascade Mask R-CNN (ResNet-50 + FPN backbone) [245], it is worth noting that there is a significant difference between a tile and entire Sentinel-1 imagery. Indeed, a raster-tiling and a Non Maximum Suppression (NMS) algorithm are required as pre-processing and post-processing steps, respectively, to not lose the receptive field.

Land masking and byte-scaling were applied using the SNAP processing toolbox from ESA, utilizing the Shuttle Radar Topography Mission (SRTM) 3-second DEM with an extended shoreline of 10 pixels. A 1000×1000 pixel sliding window was then employed for parsing the whole SAR image, moving with a stride of 500 pixels. Despite the use of relatively modest hardware, the process generated 4264 tiles in under 800 seconds, achieving a frame rate of 5.33 images per second. As it is possible to notice from Figure 4.21, in scenario A two collaborative ships and a dark vessel in the middle are present. The blue rectangles in Figures 4.21-4.22 represent the bounding boxes output of Cascade Mask R-CNN after the NMS. As stated above, NMS and raster-tiling are demanded due to the impossibility of performing an end-to-end training with a single GPU.

The narrow natural surface films have been imaged as almost straight feature and hence have been interpreted by the algorithm as ship wakes. However, all the wakes have been detected with the commonly assumed confidence threshold of 0.55.

Figure 4.21: Detections over Scenario A (Azimuth-Ground Range coordinates). Dark vessel in middle indicated in red.

Figure 4.22: Detections over Scenario C (Azimuth-Ground Range coordinates).

Figure 4.23: Detections over Scenario B (Azimuth-Ground Range coordinates)

More in detail, the trace of the ship wake on left has shown an interesting behaviour since it

extends for several kilometers: in the section where the contrast is poor, the detector was not able to find the wake, but in a close section the contrast boost led the detection again feasible. In a quiet sea condition, scenario B in Figure 4.23, the detector has shown a remarkable performance being able to capture all the wakes with no false alarms. For the sake of highlighting the capability of the algorithm, the binary mask obtained by the segmentation branch of Cascade Mask R-CNN and the confidence score of one of the two detected wakes it is also reported.

In the scenario C in Figure 4.22 the wind-speed change has generated a variation of the backscattered energy from sea, thus a particular pattern is visible. Still, the detector has been able to handle this situation with no false alarm generated in bright/dark border and the unique ship wake in the scene is correctly detected.

Error Analysis From a statistical point of view, an error analysis of the detector has been conducted on whole SAR images covering the Gulf of Genoa, Italy.

They are IW swath mode Sentinel-1 C-band images gathered in VV polarization, and correspond to Level-1 GRD products. All the images are acquired in ascending phase with a ground range and an azimuth spacing of 10m.

The following Table 4.8 lists the image identifiers completed by wind and maritime traffic data, provided by in situ measurements at Genoa and La Spezia stations, respectively. The images are not present in the paper for brevity but are reported in the supplementary materials of the paper [223].

Table 4.8: List of products under inspection for error analysis.

Date		6 July 2020	
Image ID	S1A_IW_GRDH_1SDV_20200706T171436_20200706T171501_033337_03DCC6_1122		
Image ID	S1A_IW_GRDH_1SDV_20200706T171411_20200706T171436_033337_03DCC6_3302		
Wind@Genoa	Speed: 2 m/s	Direction: 204°N	
Wind@LaSpezia	Speed: 5 m/s	Direction: 134°N	
Date		18 July 2020	
Image ID	S1A_IW_GRDH_1SDV_20200823T171414_20200823T171439_034037_03F36B_5DA2		
Image ID	S1A_IW_GRDH_1SDV_20200823T171439_20200823T171504_034037_03F36B_447E		
Wind@Genoa	Speed: 2 m/s	Direction: 188°N	
Wind@LaSpezia	Speed: 2.5 m/s	Direction: 150°N	
Date		23 August 2020	
Image ID	S1A_IW_GRDH_1SDV_20200823T171414_20200823T171439_034037_03F36B_5DA2		
Image ID	S1A_IW_GRDH_1SDV_20200823T171439_20200823T171504_034037_03F36B_447E		
Wind@Genoa	Speed: 2 m/s	Direction: 188°N	
Wind@LaSpezia	Speed: 2.5 m/s	Direction: 150°N	
Date		29 August 2020	
Image ID	S1B_IW_GRDH_1SDV_20200829T171409_20200829T171434_023141_02BF02_2FD4		
Image ID	S1B_IW_GRDH_1SDV_20200829T171344_20200829T171409_023141_02BF02_36A0		
Wind@Genoa	Speed: 1.1 m/s	Direction: 194°N	
Wind@LaSpezia	Speed: 9.4 m/s	Direction: 210°N	

Denoting again with TP the true positives, TN the true negative, and FP the false negatives. The available data allow us to affirm that when the turbulent wake is clearly focused by SAR, the trained detector provides almost 100% of TP, i.e. all the wakes are detected by the model, 0% of TN, i.e. no wake imaged in the scene is lost, but it is very difficult to quantify the FP. This is due to the impossibility of the identification of a ground truth, even with a visual inspection of the SAR image. In some cases, false positives clearly derive from other features over sea, such as natural surface films, but in other cases, mainly when the ship is not imaged, it is not possible to discriminate about the nature of the feature.

Domain shift to X-band SAR imaging In this section the generalizability reached by the developed detector is assessed through the application of the model against multi-domain unseen data. In this ambit, the detection performance are hereby evaluated on the German TSX and Italian CSK X-band products. Main characteristics are reported in Table 4.9 where it is possible to notice that the products are in Azimuth-Slant Range coordinates.

In fact, the wake detector has been trained on C-band images which, in terms of complexity, offer relatively fewer features compared to X-band SAR imagery. In addition to polarization and incidence angles, variations in spatial resolution significantly influence shifts in the data distribution. In particular, CSK data is acquired in a different polarization, i.e., HH. Furthermore, the geometric configuration introduces additional complexity; while the training dataset was based on GRD, the X-band products are in Single-Look Complex (SLC), which fundamentally alters the imaging representation. This mismatch plays a critical role in the model’s ability to generalize effectively across domains, making particularly intriguing to examine its behaviour.

Firstly, the results over TSX data are evaluated. These images hold some characteristics similar to sentinel-1 IW products, i.e. same polarization, same wake characteristics present, but the resolution and the wavelength of the signal are different. A subset of TSX product is reported in (Figure 4.24a). The product gathered over the Gulf of Naples, Italy on June 9th, 2011 shows two wakes in opposite azimuth directions. The sea state is in a quiet condition and the two turbulent wakes are sharply distinguishable from the sea clutter.

The findings shown in Figure 4.24b demonstrate that the detector is able to recognize the presence of two different ship wakes; this is very interesting since the two wakes barely cross in the bottom which could be prone to lead to a false interpretation as a unique V-shape wake. The confidence scores are still high enough and the contour of the ship wakes is well defined.

Finally, results are evaluated on CSK data which are completely different in terms of sensor, resolution, polarization, and different wake characteristics present.

Table 4.9: Main characteristics of TerraSAR-X (TSX) and COSMO-SkyMed (CSK) X-band products

Parameter	CSK Image	TSX Image
Acquisition Date	30/06/2008	09/06/2011
Acquisition Mode	Stripmap	Stripmap
Product Type	SLC	SLC
Incidence Angle (local)	$\sim 24^\circ$	$\sim 28^\circ$
Polarization	HH	VV
Resolution (slant range-azimuth)	3m x 3m	1.2m x 6.6m

In Figure 4.25a a subset of CSK SLC image in Azimuth-Slant Range coordinates is reported. The image is gathered in HH polarization over the Gulf of Naples, Italy on June 30th, 2008. It contains a ship wake in which the Kelvin wakes generated by the vessel motion are clearly visible. Results shown in Figure 4.25b confirm the generalization of the proposed methodology. As expected, the segmentation mask well contours the turbulent and narrow-V wakes but does not recognize the kelvin cusps. However, this is quite understandable since the detector has not been trained to recognize such features which are not imaged in medium resolution C-band imagery, like Sentinel-1 IW products. It is worth noting that the confidence score is enough high to discriminate the wake from the surrounding surface films which have not been misjudged by the algorithm.

Figure 4.24: Subset (2000×2000 pixels) of the TSX product (TSX1_SAR_SSC_BT X1_SM_D_SRA_-20110609T164931_20110609T164939) gathered in VV polarization over the Gulf of Naples, Italy on June 9th, 2011 (Azimuth-Slant Range coordinates)

Figure 4.25: Subset (1825×1563 pixels) of the CSK product (CSKS1_SCS_B_HI_0B_HH_RA_SF_-20080630045711_20080630045718) gathered in HH polarization over the Gulf of Naples, Italy on June 30th, 2008 (Azimuth-Slant Range coordinates)

Results on MSSWD

This section discusses the multi-band analysis obtained by training and testing several different OD architectures on the MSSWD. The results are presented both in quantitative and qualitative terms. To obtain a fair comparison of the models and of the spectral bands, all the sources of non-deterministic behaviour were suppressed. This was obtained by setting the cuDNN (CUDA Deep Neural Network library, which is a GPU-accelerated library from NVIDIA designed to enhance deep learning computations) benchmark on deterministic mode, setting the seed manually, and suppressing test-time augmentation if originally applied.

The limited size of the MSSWD dataset arises from the labor-intensive difficulty of identifying ship wakes in multi-spectral imagery. To mitigate this limitation, a training approach was employed, incorporating transfer learning across various pre-trained models. Pre-training from COCO proved not only beneficial but essential to address the scarce labeled data.

All models were fine-tuned to convergence, with the hyperparameters optimized using a simple grid-search algorithm. Both the SGD and Adam optimizers were evaluated, each with a decaying learning rate schedule, either step-wise or cosine annealing. During the initial epochs, Adam exhibited faster convergence compared to SGD. However, in the final epochs, SGD achieved superior performance. Notably, the cosine annealing learning rate schedule was particularly effective for the models employing smaller encoders. Concerning data pre-processing, since images are encoded in

Table 4.10: Implemented techniques for pre-processing, data augmentation, and post-processing. (Note: * CL indicates clip limit, BrL indicates brightness limit, and BL indicates blur limit).

Technique	Stage	Parameters
Histogram Equalisation	Pre-processing	3σ
CLAHE	Pre-processing	$CL^* = (1.4)$
Flip	Data Augmentation	Probability = 0.5
Random Brightness	Data Augmentation	Probability = 0.25, BrL* = (-0.05, 0.05)
Random Contrast	Data Augmentation	Probability = 0.25
Rotate	Data Augmentation	Probability = 0.33
Blur	Data Augmentation	Probability = 0.1, BL* = (3, 5)
Normalisation	Post-processing	[0, 1.0]

16-bit depth, a prior histogram equalisation has been carried out using a confidence interval peaked around the mean with a variance of 3σ ; this better highlight spatial surface feature as ship wakes as well.

Then, a CLAHE technique [247] has been applied to regularise the brighter/darker portions of the image. This technique was proven to improve the feature visibility while simultaneously avoiding noise amplification.

The input size was fixed to 768×768 pixels for all the architectures under evaluation. Model over-fitting was monitored and an early stopping strategy was implemented.

As better detailed in Table 4.10, the data agumentation strategy is composed of: a) Flipping, both horizontal, vertical or diagonal, b) Photo-metric distortion with random brightness and contrast boost, c) Rotating, and d) Blurring the images. Finally, post-processing normalisation was applied to the input for tensor computations.

A massive model analysis has been performed and the results are reported in Table 4.11, which provides a thorough overview of the performance reached by all the OD architectures developed in

recent years. The Table 4.11 has been organised comparing models of different design complexity, following a top-down structure. The models reported in the first part of the table are multi-stage algorithms, namely Faster [248], Mask [249], Cascade [249], Sparse [250] and Hybrid Task Cascade R-CNN [251]. As stated above, this class of architectures is made of anchor-based detectors. All the following methods, i.e. TridentNet [252], RetinaNet [243], FSAF [253], and SSD [254], are all one-stage networks. The other category under investigation is the one-stage anchor-free, which, in this analysis, consists of FCOS [255], FoveaBox [256], VFNet [257], and CenterNet [258]. It is worth noting that, within category of methods, another possible differentiation can be done whether the methods rely upon a key-points approach. Finally, it is possible to find the transformer-based methods, such as DETR [259] and Deformable DETR [260]. These methods eliminate the need for NMS by adopting a bipartite matching approach, ensuring a one-to-one prediction to ground truth assignment.

Table 4.11: Evaluation results for various models on the B_8 band of MSSWD in terms of AP at different thresholds of IoU. Detection models categorized in multi-stage, one-stage, anchor-free, and transformer-based.

Model	Backbone	AP_{50}	AP_{75}	AP
Multi-stage				
Faster R-CNN	ResNet-50	0.76	0.27	0.12
Mask R-CNN	ResNet-101	0.79	0.33	0.08
Cascade Mask R-CNN	ResNet-101	0.80	0.32	0.52
Mask R-CNN	ResNet-50	0.76	0.26	0.26
Hybrid Task Cascade	ResNet-50	0.76	0.28	0.53
Hybrid Task Cascade	ResNet-101	0.74	0.31	0.43
Mask R-CNN	ResNet-50	0.76	0.28	0.23
Cascade Mask R-CNN	HRNet-40	0.52	0.18	0.35
One-stage				
TridentNet	ResNet-50	0.25	0.03	0.12
FSAF	ResNet-50	0.74	0.29	0.48
SSD	VGG16	0.20	0.05	0.20
RetinaNet	ResNet-18	0.73	0.27	0.34
RetinaNet	ResNet-34	0.78	0.35	0.13
RetinaNet	ResNet-50	0.79	0.34	0.26
RetinaNet	ResNet-101	0.77	0.42	0.24
RetinaNet	EfficientNet-B3	0.26	0.05	0.07
RetinaNet	Swin	0.72	0.26	0.32
Anchor-Free				
Sparse R-CNN	ResNet-50	0.17	0.01	0.02
FCOS	ResNet-50	0.71	0.27	0.41
FoveaBox	ResNet-50	0.74	0.31	0.32
FoveaBox	ResNet-101	0.79	0.33	0.51
VFNet	ResNet-50	0.78	0.36	0.55
CenterNet	ResNet-18	0.20	0.04	0.19
Transformer-based				
DETR	ResNet-50	0.03	0.01	0.14
Deformable DETR	ResNet-50	0.20	0.05	0.08

The methods have been likewise evaluated in terms of AP at different thresholds of IoU. It is worth noting that for maritime monitoring application, an IoU of 0.5 can be still considered satisfactory.

The results indicate that Cascade Mask R-CNN, when combined with a ResNet-101 backbone, achieves the highest performance in terms of AP_{50} , while RetinaNet with a ResNet-101 backbone outperforms others in AP_{75} . HTC with ResNet-50 delivers the top score in AP . Table 4.11 further highlights that models such as Cascade Mask R-CNN, FoveaBox, Faster R-CNN, HTC, RetinaNet, FSAF, and VFNet exhibit strong performance, all surpassing a threshold of 0.75 in AP_{50} , with corresponding AP_{75} and AP scores showing consistent trends, indicative of their robust fitting to the training data. Conversely, the performance for DETR and Deformable DETR show high variability and erratic behavior, highlighting the difficulty of the encoder-decoder heads in the domain transfer to MSSWD. The erratic behavior can still be linked to the transformer-based architecture of DETR and Deformable DETR, which process data in a sequence-to-sequence manner and are less biased, statistically speaking, than other modern DL architectures.

Based on these considerations, one crucial aspect must be pointed out: the results scored on MSSWD slightly deviate from the ones benchmarked on the COCO dataset for which they were developed. The reason behind this different scoring lies to the data of MSSWD itself, being composed with completely dissimilar characteristics from the classical camera images. The reader should consider that the ship wake detection problem is dissonant from the generic OD problem since: a) the number of features but also the feature complexity is significantly inferior, b) the instances are seen from a bird-eye perspective, and c) there are no problems such as occlusions, elevated number of classes, highly overlapped bounding boxes, and class imbalance that require engineering the network architecture.

Encoder Module Analysis Using RetinaNet as the reference model and varying only the feature extractor, it was possible to analyze the impact of different backbones on performance. The backbones examined include EfficientNet-B3, ResNet-18, ResNet-34, ResNet-50, ResNet-101, and the transformed-based Swin architecture. The results indicate that ResNet-101 achieves the highest score in terms of AP_{75} , while ResNet-50 performs best for AP_{50} . The ImageNet weight initialization was found to be less effective for fine-tuning and have been excluded from the Table 4.11. Regarding AP_{50} , ResNet-18, ResNet-34, ResNet-50, and ResNet-101 showed comparable performance, though ResNet-18 and ResNet-101 differ significantly in computational cost.

The high capacity of EfficientNet-B3 seems insufficient to capture the spatial content of MSSWD effectively, which may be due to another factor: satellite imagery tends to exhibit simpler features compared to typical deep learning tasks, and deeper networks without adequate skip connections may suffer from vanishing gradients. This is further supported by the results for VGG16, where the lack of skip connections and reliance on only convolutional and pooling layers may hinder performance. In contrast, ResNet backbones, with their extensive use of short skip connections, improve convergence and mitigate vanishing gradient issues.

Head Module Analysis Using ResNet-50 as the reference backbone and FPN as neck, the impact of the neck and head layers on performance was examined. The results, in terms of AP_{50} and AP_{75} , indicate that the various architecture classes exhibit generally similar values. Among multi-stage architectures, HTC achieved the highest performance, while RetinaNet was the most effective one-stage anchor-based detector.

One-stage anchor-free architectures are generally to be preferred due to their reduced design com-

plexity and fewer hyperparameters, which contribute to a more streamlined optimization process. Among these, FoveaBox exhibits notable performance while maintaining simplicity, positioning it as an efficient and effective option. Furthermore, VFNet demonstrates remarkable performance, closely approximating the results of the top-performing models, such as Mask R-CNN and its Cascade variant.

Single Band Analysis One crucial outcome of this work is that the numerical analysis has revealed how the B_2 , B_3 , B_4 , and B_8 bands have shown similar performance results, underscoring same visual features across all bands.

As illustrated by the box plots in Figure 4.26, no single band demonstrates significant performance improvements among the others. It is worth noting that the differences in few points of AP_{50} for this single-class problem are marginal. While the box plots for each band are statistically comparable, they still provide some insight. Specifically, B_8 (NIR) and B_2 (visible blue) exhibit higher variability in performance, whereas B_3 (visible green) and B_4 (visible red) show lower variability, possibly due to their lower average intensity in maritime imagery.

This similarity is likely a result of the pre-processing pipeline, which has minimized the subtle variations between the spectral bands being analyzed. Nevertheless, this step was essential for enhancing the prominent ship wake features in the complex and congested environments of MSSWD. Ultimately, it can be argued that for the task of ship wake detection spatial relationships more effective than spectral content, allowing the extraction of meaningful information from wake patterns. This finding aligns with previous studies utilizing RT.

Figure 4.26: The multi-band analysis results were performed on the B_2 , B_3 , B_4 , and B_8 spectral bands, focusing on the AP_{50} . No significant increase in average precision is observed among the different spectral bands.

Visual Scrutiny The Figure 4.27 shows the detection results of all the presented architectures using a common confidence score threshold of 0.75 on a single chip. This wake chip is characterised

by a V-shaped wake in a complex-background scenario where natural surface films can pose serious problem for RT method. As shown in Figure 4.27, the predicted bounding boxes are marked in green, with the addition of the segmentation output if a mask branch is present in the model in question. The Figure shows how structurally different detectors built with different parameters share a similar behaviour in detecting the ship wake. Nonetheless, some of them are able to provide a more refined detection than others, which is further shown in Table 4.11. Notably, Mask R-CNN identified two false alarms, whereas Sparse R-CNN failed to distinguish the ship wake from the background. This outcome aligns with its inconsistent performance during training, where no clear trend emerged compared to other detectors. Nonetheless, the results clearly show that all detectors successfully recognized and segmented the Kelvin components.

Figure 4.27: The recognition result (score threshold=0.75) of different OD architectures on the same chip: a) RetinaNet (ResNet-18), b) HTC (ResNet-50), c) VFNet, d) FoveaBox (ResNet-50), e) RetinaNet (EfficientNet-B3), f) RetinaNet (Swin), g) Sparse R-CNN (ResNet-50), h) Cascade Mask R-CNN (ResNet-101), i) RetinaNet (ResNet-101), l) Cascade Mask R-CNN (HRNet), m) RetinaNet (ResNet-34), n) Mask R-CNN (ResNet-50), o) Faster R-CNN (ResNet-50), p) FoveaBox (ResNet-101), q) FCOS (ResNet-50), r) RetinaNet (ResNet-50). [Product ID: S2A_MSIL2A_20210628T103021_N0300_R108_T33UUB_20210628T152020].

Error Analysis The Cascade Mask R-CNN is selected at hand for the visual evaluation of the test set, focusing on the characterisation in terms of AIS data of the detected ships. Because the spectral characteristics were shown to be less impactful when detecting ships wakes than the geometrical information, this analysis was conducted on one-band imagery; in particular, the B_8 band was chosen for this purpose. The table and figures presented below present an overview of the obtained results. In particular: a) 16 of the 198 ships reported in the test dataset were not recognised, b) 22 ships were not collaborative, c) in some particular cases, the model recognised multiple wakes as left by a single vessel, d) 3 false detections cases concerned sea ridges and aircraft wakes, as displayed in Figure 4.28. This last issue is mainly related to the features provided by the wakes in the training dataset. It needs to be noted that the vast majority of the ships present turbulent wakes as their predominant feature. In multi-spectral images, turbulent wakes appears as long white stripes, easily mistaken for sea crests and false wakes.

A primary concern regarding the MSSWD involves the presence of numerous slow-moving vessels under 20 m in length. To investigate the relationship between wake shape and detection performance, Table 4.12, alongside Figures 4.29 and 4.30, was constructed. These figures depict the vessel types, dimensions, and SOG within the test dataset. Subsequently, an analysis was performed on the detected ships. The results indicate that all small vessels, with speeds below 10 knots, were correctly identified—excluding cases where AIS data was unavailable—as shown in Figures 4.29 and 4.30.

Figure 4.28: False detections and clear sea overview presenting: a) aircraft wake b) aircraft wake c) bright line not clearly identified d) clear sea with no object to detect.

Table 4.12: Test dataset ship type distribution. Only the ships with available corresponding AIS data are reported

Ship Type	Percentage of Ships (%)	Number of Ships
Cargo	48.28	63
Tanker	14.48	18
Passenger	15.17	19
Tug	2.07	3
Pleasure	1.38	2
Sailing	2.07	3
Fishing	2.76	3
Dredging	2.07	3
Military	2.07	3
Law Enforcement	0	0
Pilot	0.69	1
HSC	0.69	1
SAR	0.69	1
Reserved	0	0
Diving	0	0
Other	0.69	1
Undefined	6.21	8

Figure 4.30: Analysis of the distribution of ships' SOG in the test dataset of MSSWD.

The model successfully detected 89% of the vessels in the test dataset with high confidence, using a threshold of 0.7. Notably, only 6 out of 16 undetected ships (3.9% of the dataset) remain unidentified for unknown reasons. Upon analysis of these anomalies, it was observed that the chip tiles were three times larger than the typical input size. When the images were cropped to regions around the undetected ship wakes, with dimensions smaller than 1000×1000 pixels, the network was able to accurately detect these vessels. For clarity, Table 4.13 lists all ships that were not detected by the model, while Figure 4.31 illustrates a representative case of misdetection. As shown in Table 4.13, the model correctly identified all small and slow vessels; the undetected cases correspond to larger ships with higher speeds. In particular, ships 1, 2, and 3 were missed due to the complexity of overlapping wakes, which introduced ambiguity and reduced the model's ability to accurately resolve these instances.

Table 4.13: Ship type, SOG, and dimensions of undetected ships. The last column reports the possible reasons for these misdetections.

#	Ship Type	SOG (knots)	Width (m)	Length (m)	Misdetection Understanding
1	Cargo	14.5	45	292	
2	Passenger	16.6	29	200	Overlapped wakes
3	Passenger	18.2	26	199	
4	Cargo	6.5	14	89	Overlapping wakes identified as one
5	Tanker	12.9	32	183	Wake obscured by clouds
6	Tanker	11.5	16	100	Overlapping wakes in a complex scenario
7	Cargo	8.2	13	90	
8	Passenger	15.7	27	170	Oversized ship
9	Undefined	12.8	26	130	
10	Cargo	15.4	25	148	Oversized ship
11	Tanker	12.9	27	178	
12	Cargo	8.6	13	90	
13	Tanker	6.4	24	144	Overlapping wakes identified as one
14	Cargo	9.3	13	88	Oversized ship
15	Passenger	11.1	12	70	Bright line overlapping a poor-in-features wake
16	Cargo	9.8	13	88	Oversized ship

Figure 4.31: 1441×1441 chip reporting 5 wakes including 3 undetected ships: red-marked, blue-marked and violet-marked ships refer to ships 1,2,3 respectively reported in Table 4.13. Product: S2A_MSIL2A_-20210605T102021_N0300_R065_T32UPF_20210605T132908

4.3.3 Wake Component Identification

As stated in this thesis, one of the limitations of OD methodologies lies in their lack of ability to identify wake components in their base formulation. In this thesis, the issue is addressed by designing a module specific for wake components identification [261].

The literature contains findings regarding the detectability of ship wakes [31, 229, 262–264], with SAR and optical differences: Narrow-V wakes are not captured in optical imagery, while Kelvin wakes consistently appear as bright lines, as documented in [263]. Software simulations of wake images have also been investigated [265]. However, a comprehensive analysis and identification of individual wake components within maritime scenarios is an intricate subject that has not garnered comparable attention from the scientific community.

As stated at the beginning of this chapter, for wake detection are based on the RT [219], mainly focusing on SAR data. RT-based methods, while capable of converting lines into peaks for wake identification, are sensitive to bright spots or interference in the image [263, 264]. Additionally, these methods are time-consuming, computationally intensive, and rely on the assumption that wakes are linear. Due to these limitations, they have not been widely adopted in operational maritime monitoring systems [266].

The proposed method overcomes RT limitations and provides a faster, automated, and generalizable alternative. Additionally, its efficiency also enable its applicability on low power devices [15]. To the authors' knowledge, few works address this problem using DL [267], with most based on extensions of existing object detection frameworks [268]. However, these methodologies primarily focus on the fan aperture, neglecting the turbulent component, and estimate the wake vertex by regressing from the bounding box's central coordinates.

Consequently, their usability is limited to cases where Kelvin arms are present for estimating heading angles. Additionally, while these methods resolve wake detection in an end-to-end fashion, they fail to distinguish wake detection from component identification, which is the focus of this study. These are two distinct problems that should be handled separately. Moreover, existing approaches using true color images limit equalization algorithms' ability to highlight ship wake features.

In summary, this study presents a novel, end-to-end keypoint-based DL technique for wake component identification, offering speed, efficiency, and autonomy, with no prior comparable research.

Methodology

For how it was conceived, it will serve as a stand-alone module applied in cascade to a region of interest identified by an object detector. In this regard, it requires a coarse, formerly identified, region of interest.

In this study, wake component identification is framed as a keypoint regression problem. The (x, y) coordinates of each keypoint are extracted by a CNN using low-, mid-, and high-level features, which are then fed into a fully connected layer with output size $2n$, where n represents the number of keypoints.

While keypoint localization using CNNs is not new [269, 270], no prior studies have used a DL-based architecture for this task. This work focuses on identifying two wake components—turbulent wake and Kelvin arms—by selecting four keypoints: wake vertex, turbulent wake end, and Kelvin arms' ends. The chosen network is EfficientNet-B0 [85], built on MobileNetV2's inverted bottleneck

blocks [271], incorporating depthwise separable convolutions, squeeze-and-excitation blocks [272], and compound scaling [85] for efficient channel attention and optimal network scaling based on input size.

Dataset Compiled

The keypoint regression dataset⁵ is constructed from MSSWD and it is compiled as follows. The dataset was created by inspecting the Sentinel-2 images of MSSWD, focusing on the B_8 for optimal sea surface feature recognition, minimizing atmospheric interference and surface glint.

The compiled dataset includes 588 ship wake chips, covering the various scenarios. The tiles undergone the same pre-processing described for MSSWD manually cropped around ship wake.

The dataset is diverse in terms of wake chip orientation, dimension, and background complexity. Each wake chip is annotated marking keypoints such as the wake vertex, the end of the turbulent wake, and the Kelvin arms, as shown in Figure 4.32. Recognizing wakes is further complicated by partial occlusions from clouds or natural surface films.

Figure 4.32: Keypoints data labelling on sample wake chip: (green dot) ship wake vertex, (blue dot) ending turbulent wake and (red dots) ending of Kelvin arms.

In 40% of the samples, the Kelvin arms are not visible, and in these cases, their annotations were omitted. Additionally, narrow V-wakes, which are undetectable in optical imagery due to Bragg scattering at optical wavelengths[263], were excluded from the study due to their limited relevance to route determination.

Experimental Results

This section reports the training and testing results of the implemented model. The framework utilized was Pytorch 1.12 (Cudatoolkit 11.3.1 & Cudnn 8.3.2) while the Linux machine used mounts a GTX 1060 with 6GB of VRAM. Data augmentation is used to increase the sparsity of the dataset. As a pre-processing step, a resizing matches the dimension of the tensor in input with the one of EfficientNet-B0 (224×224). It follows random rotations (100%), affine transforms (50%), and changes in brightness and contrast (20%). Finally, the tensors are normalized before going into the model.

A transfer-learning procedure has been adopted, fine-tuning the Imagenet weights on the developed

⁵Available on Zenodo (10.5281/zenodo.7947694).

dataset. The dataset distribution adheres to the standard practice of a 60/20/20 split, respectively for training, validation, and testing. The model has been trained for 500 epochs with a learning rate of $6 \cdot 10^{-4}$. The other relevant hyper-parameters chosen by a trial and error selection are: a) batch size of value 25, b) Adam optimizer, and c) weight decay of $5 \cdot 10^{-4}$. Notably, an increased batch size helped in stabilizing the training, lowering the loss, and dampening characteristic spikes of the loss function.

As far as the loss function is concerned, the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) function was selected for optimizing the model performance. The RMSE can be written as:

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (x_n - y_n)^2} \quad (4.12)$$

where x and y refer to ground truth and predicted tensors with n elements each. It is worth underlining that n is herein equal to 8 in the case of the manuscript.

The Figure 4.33 depicts the trends of training and validation losses over 500 epochs. The graph shows that overfitting has been properly handled. In particular, validation loss settles after the 100th epoch. The training phase, employing an early stopping strategy, took approximately one hour to complete.

Figure 4.33: Training and Validation Loss evaluated with RMSE.

Some examples of visual detection results on the test dataset are extracted and reported in Figure 4.34-4.36. The various chips show the wake vertex, the ending of the turbulent wake, and the ending of the kelvin arms with a green dot, a blue dot, and yellow dots, respectively. Additionally, red lines are drawn for better clarity of representation. Figure 4.34 shows two chip samples where the keypoints regressed are close to the ship wake imaged by the sensor. On the other hand, within Figure 4.35, it is possible to observe that while the wake vertex has been perfectly recognized the model struggles to identify Kelvin's arms. This usually happens when the turbulent wake is mistakenly assigned to one of Kelvin's arms or when Kelvin's arms are missing. Thus, one can conclude that this behavior is due to the poor detectability of Kelvin's arms under certain environmental conditions. Nonetheless, the results reported in Figure 4.36 show a high performance reached by the detector in quiet sea conditions identifying all the components.

Figure 4.34: Case A - The keypoint recognition results on different test set sample chips: (green dot) ship wake vertex, (blue dot) ending turbulent wake and (red dots) ending of Kelvin arms.

Figure 4.35: Case B - The keypoint recognition results on different test set sample chips: (green dot) ship wake vertex, (blue dot) ending turbulent wake and (red dots) ending of Kelvin arms.

Figure 4.36: Case C - The keypoint recognition results on different test set sample chips: (green dot) ship wake vertex, (blue dot) ending turbulent wake and (red dots) ending of Kelvin arms.

It is important to highlight that the developed framework has a very fast inference time, running at 114.12 Frames Per Second (FPS) while being only 5MB in size, making it ideal for deployment on embedded systems and edge-AI components. Although the model was trained on the B_8 band, it has also been tested on the B_2 , B_3 , B_4 bands, all sharing the same 10m spatial resolution. The model's performance is generally better when using B_8 data, but it also shows good generalization when applied to B_2 - B_4 bands (Figure 4.37).

Figure 4.37: The keypoint recognition results in different spectral bands of the same chip: (green dot) ship wake vertex, (blue dot) ending turbulent wake, and (red dots) ending of Kelvin arms.

Furthermore, the model was subjected to domain shift evaluation by testing on Landsat-9 imagery, which exhibits a coarser spatial resolution (30m) compared to the Sentinel-2 data it was trained on. Despite the inherent challenges posed by this domain shift, including reduced feature discernibility, Figure 4.38 demonstrates that critical elements such as the wake vertex, turbulent wake, and one of Kelvin's arms were still identified with commendable precision. This highlights the model's adaptability across varying spatial resolutions and different data distribution.

Figure 4.38: Domain adaptation results tested on Landsat-9 image chip: (green dot) ship wake vertex, (blue dot) ending turbulent wake, and (red dots) ending of Kelvin arms.

Error Analysis Figure 4.39 depicts the fractional errors along the (x, y) directions of the wake vertex recognition. Essential to note is that errors are normalized to the chip size. For generalizability, only the test set images were used for calculating the fractional errors. Very low errors are registered by the ship wake vertex keypoint, lying well below $\pm 10\%$.

Figure 4.39: Fractional errors for the x, y coordinates of the ship wake vertex keypoint (The $\mu \pm \sigma$ and $\mu \pm 2\sigma$ values are evidenced with the shades).

This expected behavior finds explanation in the higher presence and clarity of features, being the rallying point of all the wake components. The achieved statistics confirm that the performance of the proposed method is in line with that expected in Fig. 4.39.

The histogram in Figure 4.40 shows the Gaussian distribution of the heading angle errors. The histogram registered a quasi zero-mean and a standard deviation of $\pm 10^\circ$, which is acceptable for route estimation purposes [273].

In conclusion, the detector also struggles with wakes that only have a turbulent component, as shown in the left picture of Figure 4.35. While the detection of the turbulent component is at 95%, the model misidentifies around 30% of the Kelvin arms.

When evaluating performance, our method contrasts with the conventional RT technique, which offers greater precision but at the cost of reduced processing speed. Its accuracy and processing time depend heavily on the angular precision employed to scan the linear domain. With a standard angular precision of 0.5° , the Radon method yields a heading error within $\pm 1^\circ$ and wake vertex errors below $\pm 2^\circ$, running at roughly 2.9 seconds per a tile of size 300×300 pixels.

The trade-off between precision and processing time thus highlights the proposed method's suitability for real-time applications where computational efficiency is essential.

Figure 4.40: Histogram of heading angle errors showing a Gaussian distribution with quasi zero-mean and a standard deviation of $\pm 10^\circ$, which is within acceptable limits for route estimation.

4.4 Tip & Cue Preliminary Demonstration

The integration of insights coming from swarm of “sentient” satellites led the innovative concept of T&C. This approach refers to a collaborative interaction between two satellites, usually collocated on similar orbital planes, where the “Tip” satellite performs an initial wide-area scan using low- or medium-resolution sensor, and executes a preliminary detection of potential targets or anomalies. Then, this information is relayed to the “Cue” satellite, which focuses its sensor on the specific region of interest for further analysis. This combined approach take advantage of higher revisit time, allowing for continuous monitoring, and vessel tracking without ground-based processing.

In [33]⁶, we initially created a multi-mission dataset focusing on the collection of products covering same areas with a time gap lower than 15 minutes. Additionally, the performance of a deterministic ship detector—CFAR [274–277] with SLA [278–281])—were evaluated.

To the best of the authors’ knowledge, prior research on ship detection has primarily concentrated on either single-mission or single-acquisition methodologies. Therefore, this represents the first research of this kind.

The T&C capability is demonstrated in the present work by showcasing the benefits deriving from continuous monitoring trough the exploitation of multiple satellites. In the context of maritime surveillance, our preliminary findings demonstrate potential for T&C application.

Figure 4.41: Representation of the T&C concept. The “Tip” satellite conducts a wide-area scan, marking potential targets. The information is delivered by inter-satellite link (ISL) to the “Cue” satellite which focuses on regions of interest for detailed analysis.

⁶This work has been developed in the framework of the Italian Space Agency’s “Study of new methods and techniques based on the utilization of multimission/multifrequency SAR data”, project “COastal Area monitoring with SAR data and multimission/multifrequency Techniques - COAST”, ASI Contract N. 2021-11-U.0.

4.4.1 Dataset Compiled

Data collection started from the selection and identification of the region of interest. For study, three different scenarios, drawn in Figure 4.42, were selected for the purpose of maritime monitoring: Adriatic Sea, Sardinia, and the Egadi Islands.

Figure 4.42: Selected scenarios of interest for the realization of the MM/MF dataset: (a) Adriatic Sea, (b) Sardinia, and (c) the Egadi Islands.

- **Scenario 1: Egadi Islands** Marine Protected Areas (MPAs) are fundamental for the preservation and restoration of marine biodiversity, serving to protect critical habitats, species, and ecological functions. The Egadi Islands MPA, encompassing an area of 53,992 hectares, represents the largest marine reserve in the Mediterranean Sea. This region, located off the north-western coast of Sicily and comprising the islands of Favignana, Levanzo, Marettimo, and the islets of Formica and Maraone, was selected for this study to evaluate the algorithm's efficacy in monitoring MPAs. The preservation of such regions is crucial for ensuring the long-term sustainability of marine ecosystems, and thus the Egadi Islands provide an ideal test case for this purpose.
- **Scenario 2: Sardinia** Sardinia holds the record for the highest amount of seized fish products, indicative of extensive illegal fishing activity. This coastal region, specifically between Olbia and Stintino, was chosen to assess the algorithm's performance in detecting non-compliant fishing vessels and unauthorized trade in fish products. The area's history of high levels of poaching and the presence of non-collaborative vessels, which can be clearly observed in SAR imagery, makes it a critical location for the study of illegal fishing activities.
- **Scenario 3: Adriatic Sea** The Northern Adriatic Sea faces significant environmental degradation due to pollution and overfishing, leading to a drastic decline in fish stocks and a

profound alteration of the marine ecosystem. This scenario was selected based on the high prevalence of non-collaborative vessels involved in illicit activities, such as the trafficking of goods. The fast-moving nature of these vessels and their sporadic visibility in SAR images provide a challenging test case for the algorithm’s ability to detect and track such entities.

The construction of the Multi-Mission Dataset (MMD) involved three distinct SAR missions, i.e., the Italian COSMO-SkyMed (X-band), the Argentinian SAOCOM (L-band), and the European Sentinel-1 (C-band).

Technical description of the selected products are summarized in Table 4.14, highlighting key differences beyond their operational frequency wavelength. Regarding the Sentinel-1 acquisitions, data were collected in dual-polarization (VV+Vertical transmit-Horizontal receive (VH)) using the IW swath mode; however, only VH-polarized data were processed for this study. The CSK and SAOCOM products, on the other hand, were acquired in stripmap mode with HH and VH polarizations, respectively.

Table 4.14: Specifications of the MM/MF dataset in terms of acquisition mode, pixel spacing, polarization, and swath width.

Mission	Acquisition Mode	Pixel Spacing (range \times azimuth)	Polarization	Swath (km)
COSMO-SkyMed	StripMap	0.5m \times 0.5m	HH	40
Sentinel-1	IW	2.3m \times 13.9m	VH	250
SAOCOM	StripMap	<10m \times 10m	VH	65

4.4.2 Product Matching Strategy

As stated above, MMD products are filtered using a two-stage Product Matching Algorithm (PMA) based on temporal and spatial constraints (Algorithm 1).

In the temporal filtering stage, two products p_i and p_j are considered a match if their acquisition times $T(p_i)$ and $T(p_j)$ satisfy the condition:

$$|T(p_i) - T(p_j)| \leq \Delta T_{\max} = 15 \text{ minutes} \quad (4.13)$$

This threshold ensures that the positional drift of ships is negligible, and acquisition times are extracted from the metadata.

In the spatial filtering stage, the geospatial footprints $F(p_i)$ and $F(p_j)$ are compared to ensure coverage of the same area of interest using IoU. A valid spatial match occurs when $\text{IoU}(p_i, p_j) \geq \text{IoU}_{\min}$, with IoU_{\min} representing the minimum acceptable overlap. The footprints are further evaluated through visual inspection using interactive maps. Finally, the matched SAR products are validated against AIS ground truth across the three scenarios.

Upon completing the matching process, the paired SAR products were grouped by scenario. Each scenario is detailed individually in the Appendix. Here, we provide a summary of the number of matched product pairs, as shown in Table 4.15.

As illustrative example, two different sets of matched SAR products over the Adriatic region are presented in Figure 4.43. Figure 4.43a shows the pairing between COSMO-SkyMed and SAOCOM,

Algorithm 1 PMA**Input:**

- $P = \{p_1, p_2, \dots, p_n\}$: Set of SAR products
- $T(p_i)$: Acquisition time of product p_i
- $F(p_i)$: Geospatial footprint of product p_i
- $\Delta T_{\max} = 15$ minutes (Temporal proximity threshold)
- IoU_{\min} : Minimum acceptable Intersection over Union (IoU) for spatial overlap

Output:

- $M = \{(p_i, p_j)\}$: Set of valid matched pairs of SAR products

1: Step 1: Temporal Filtering

- 2: **1.1:** For each $p_i \in P$
- 3: **1.2:** For each $p_j \in P$ where $j > i$
- 4: **1.3:** Compute time difference: $\Delta T = |T(p_i) - T(p_j)|$
- 5: **1.4:** If $\Delta T \leq \Delta T_{\max}$
- 6: Mark pair (p_i, p_j) as a temporal match

7: Step 2: Spatial Filtering

- 8: **2.1:** For each temporal match (p_i, p_j)
- 9: **2.2:** Parse the footprint $F(p_i)$ and $F(p_j)$
- 10: **2.3:** Compute the Intersection over Union (IoU)
- 11: **2.4:** If $\text{IoU}(p_i, p_j) \geq \text{IoU}_{\min}$
- 12: Mark pair (p_i, p_j) as a valid match

Table 4.15: Number of matched product pairs between COSMO-SkyMed & Sentinel-1 (CSK-SEN), COSMO-SkyMed & SAOCOM (CSK-SAO), and Sentinel-1 & SAOCOM (SEN-SAO) across the selected scenarios.

Region	CSK-SEN	CSK-SAO	SEN-SAO
Adriatic	15	5	12
Sardinia	55	23	10
Egadi Islands	32	NA	NA

while Figure 4.43b demonstrates the matched products from COSMO-SkyMed and Sentinel-1. Finally, Figure 4.43c presents the matched products from Sentinel-1 and SAOCOM.

(a) COSMO-SkyMed and SAOCOM (b) COSMO-SkyMed and Sentinel-1 (c) Sentinel-1 and SAOCOM

Figure 4.43: Examples of matched products over the Adriatic region for different satellite pairs.

Within the ambit of T&C, the usage of AIS records (Figures 4.44a-4.44b) enables for precise knowledge of the same vessels in two different acquisitions.

(a) AIS-based location of the vessel (MMSI: 247391800).

(b) AIS-based location of the vessel (MMSI: 249512000).

Figure 4.44: Examples of same vessels across different satellite pairs. (a) COSMO-SkyMed (1505200) and Sentinel-1 (S1B_IW_SLC__1SDV_20201008T163951_20201008T164018_023724_02D155_77DD), (b) COSMO-SkyMed (1696271) and SAOCOM (EOL1ASARSAO1A1383006) products.

In Figure 4.44a, the Sentinel-1 satellite first acquired the scene, followed by COSMO-SkyMed, both over the Adriatic region acquiring an oil tanker (MMSI: 247391800). Similarly, Figure 4.44b shows another instance where the X-band (COSMO-SkyMed) and L-band (SAOCOM) SAR data were used to track the same oil tanker (MMSI: 249512000) leaving the port of Brindisi.

4.4.3 Experimental Results

Utilizing the developed MMD dataset and the trained ship wake detector for SAR images (see Section 4.3.2), a practical application of T&C for ship route reconstruction is demonstrated. Figure 4.45 illustrates the detection results of the same vessel's wake in two distinct SAR images. Specifically, the first image is captured by COSMO-SkyMed (X-band, HH polarization) and the second by Sentinel-1 (C-band, VH polarization), acquired at 17:04 and 17:13 Central European Time (CET), respectively. These paired products, part of the MMD dataset, were collected over the Egadi Islands on August 23, 2020. The images are further complemented with ancillary AIS data.

Figure 4.45 provides a zoomed view of the same vessel (identified by MMSI 247294400), a high-speed craft traveling at 10.28 knots with a course over ground of 166.5° . It is noteworthy that these products are SLC images, unlike the GRD format of the SSWD dataset. Nevertheless, the generalization capability of the detection model is demonstrated, as it successfully recognizes the visual pattern of a ship wake. As depicted in Figure 4.45, the multi-sensor data reveal how the same wake manifests differently at two radar frequencies (and polarizations).

The route reconstruction is made possible by leveraging the multi-sensor, multi-temporal data, allowing for the discretization of the ship's trajectory over two non-overlapping time intervals. The map in Figure 4.45 also highlights a commonly navigated route (dotted blue line) from Favignana Island.

Figure 4.45: Route reconstruction by wake detection in multitemporal, multifrequency SAR data: a) COSMO-SkyMed (1418705), b) Sentinel-1 (S1A_IW_SLC__1SDV_20200823T171258_20200823T171325_034037_03F36B_5D18) [Product COSMO-SkyMed processed by University of Naples Federico II under the COAST license of the Italian Space Agency (ASI); Original COSMO-SkyMed Product - ©ASI - (2021).]

This reference route is included to emphasize how the detected wakes precisely align with it. This result holds significant value, demonstrating that ship wakes not only indicate the presence of a vessel but can also be utilized to infer its past movements, and predict its route.

In the wake imaged by Sentinel-1, the distance from the wake vertex to the visible wake's end is approximately 3 kilometers (with coordinates $37^{\circ}48'42''\text{N}$, $12^{\circ}24'11''\text{E}$ for the vertex, and $37^{\circ}50'22''\text{N}$, $12^{\circ}23'34''\text{E}$ for the wake's end). Given the ship's speed of 10.3 knots, the wake represents the ship's location starting approximately 9.45 minutes before the SAR acquisition. The upper image, captured by COSMO-SkyMed, shows a wake approximately 4.6 km in length, corresponding to a duration of 14.7 minutes. As a result of the synergistic exploitation of consecutive acquisitions—particularly the wakes captured in these images—the ship's route can be tracked from 16:50 (14 minutes before the 17:04 acquisition) to 17:13, as though the vessel had been continuously providing AIS data throughout the period.

This highlights the potential of T&C for ship tracking, effectively filling gaps in AIS data and enhancing maritime situational awareness.

4.5 Discussion and Conclusion

4.5.1 Discussion

With the integration of AI onboard satellites, the findings reported contribute to the field of maritime surveillance by exploring innovative approaches for low latency responses. The system's ability to detect non-collaborative vessels using SAR or multispectral data provides actionable information pivotal for enforcing maritime regulations. It is worth noting that this kind of approach addresses the known limitations of AIS-based monitoring. One of the primary outcomes of these studies was the development of novel datasets such as SSWD, MSSWD, VDS2Raw, VDVRaw, or MMD which provide valuable resources for training AI models. The inclusion in these datasets of AIS ancillary information is another key contribution of the present work.

While the research showcased notable advancements, several technical challenges remain. When real-time processing is concerned, the timing and power benchmarks revealed that while the models are feasible for deployment, optimization is required to reduce latency and improve energy efficiency. Still, the wake detection models need refinements to be deployed on a edge-AI device. Furthermore, the processing of raw, unprocessed SAR data remains unaddressed and requires thorough attention. A robust preprocessing pipeline is necessary to ensure that meaningful information is extracted without compromising computational efficiency. Addressing these challenges will contribute significantly to improving the accuracy and reliability of surveillance systems based on SAR analysis.

Building upon these promising results, several areas for future research emerge. One critical direction is the enhancement of detection algorithms through ensemble techniques. These could help reduce the false positive rates, particularly in challenging operational conditions where environmental noise and wake artifacts interfere with detection. Another important aspect to consider is the refinement of multi-satellite cooperation strategies, which could enable continuous monitoring of vessels and enhance real-time maritime surveillance. By leveraging the complementary strengths of various satellite missions, such as the synergy between optical and radar satellites, it may be possible to achieve a more resilient and comprehensive approach to MSA. The T&C approach requires further studies on the concept of operations and mission scheduling which have not been treated in the present thesis. Additionally, future work should explore more sophisticated techniques for integrating deterministic models with AI-driven techniques. This hybrid approach could offer more precise vessel route predictions, filling gaps in AIS data and enabling continuous monitoring even in the absence of cooperative signals. Finally, adopting explainable AI techniques could enhance the robustness of the proposed models, making them more interpretable and ready for operational applications.

4.5.2 Conclusion

Within the framework of gIsAI onboard spacecrafts, the collective insights from the studies presented underscore the remarkable progress and ongoing challenges in satellite-based maritime surveillance. With a particular focus on for vessel and ship wake detection, each work contributes uniquely to the development of advanced detection models while illuminating avenues for further research.

The first study [282] showcased the potential of an end-to-end vessel detection pipeline from raw multi-spectral data, emphasizing the importance of avoiding unnecessary product corrections onboard. The findings demonstrated that a specific spectral region, lying around 800nm, achieved the

best performance for vessel detection across different sensors and datasets. While using less than 3W, the paper demonstrated the feasibility of near real-time execution (<22s) on a representative edge-AI device, mimicking processors available onboard current EO missions. Besides, limitations in leveraging multiple spectral bands were noted, the computational bottlenecks were identified, and a novel architecture has been proposed. To reduce latency, the analysis suggests that future iterations should focus on lightweighting the encoder module. Finally, noise was shown to significantly affect model performance. To address this, integrating advanced denoising techniques into the detection pipeline is recommended to enhance robustness, particularly in real-time operational environments. These advancements would lead to more reliable vessel detection systems, resilient to variations in MTF and SNR.

The second paper [223] extended this analysis by focusing on wake detection in SAR imagery. The introduction of the SSWD dataset was pioneering, offering the first dataset of its kind for SAR-based wake detection. The study demonstrated that models like Cascade Mask R-CNN, though effective, could benefit from lighter encoders that can reduce computational costs. A key challenge identified was the high false alarm rate, particularly in rough sea conditions, where wakes can resemble natural surface films. To mitigate this, the inclusion of deterministic models, such as those based on hydrodynamic laws or multi-polarization measures, was suggested as a future research direction. Nonetheless, its generalization capabilities, proved on X-band domain, successfully detected wake without any further trainings.

The third study [283] complements these findings by demonstrating that geometric features are sufficient for detecting ship wakes in multi-spectral imagery. The developed MSSWD dataset is a notable contribution, providing a benchmark for automatic detection of non-cooperative moving vessels. Concurrently, the paper [261] has assessed the capability of a DL module to recognize ship wake components in a keypoint regression fashion, marking the first implementation of a methodology of such kind. For this task a novel dataset was built from MSSWD, and the network architecture (EfficientNet-B0-lite) was tailored to accommodate keypoint localization through transfer learning. Notably, the developed wake component detector is both lightweight and efficient, with a model size of only 5MB and an impressive frame rate of 114 FPS on an NVIDIA® GTX 1060 GPU. The method also exhibited generalizability and domain adaptation capabilities when applied to Landsat-9 imagery. In summary, the trained end-to-end regressor serves as a reliable module for ship wake component identification, which can be cascaded to a wake detection framework. Future work aims to adapt this methodology to SAR data and datasets with enhanced spatial resolution. To address the false positive rate associated with Kelvin arms, ensemble techniques may be explored. Furthermore, a thorough evaluation of denoising techniques is deemed essential to improve robustness in challenging operational conditions.

Finally, the fourth study [33, 284] broadened the scope of research showcasing a AI-driven approach for ship route reconstruction by T&C. The developed MMD dataset, along with the AIS ancillary information and the trained ship wake detection model, enable the demonstration of ship route reconstruction. In the proposed T&C application, the synergic exploitation of multiple spacecrafts allows for a continuous monitoring of vessels, thereby offering improved analysis over an identified region of interest. The proposed methodology for route reconstruction by T&C demonstrates significant value for maritime surveillance since it fills gaps left by intermittent, corrupted or missing AIS data, providing actionable intelligence on unlawful ship routes. This capability enhances maritime

situational awareness, offering insights into past vessel locations and predicting future movements, and further strengthening the potential for real-time, continuous monitoring in diverse maritime environments.

Collectively, the key findings of these study suggest promising applications for maritime surveillance illustrating both the technical advancements achieved in vessel and wake detection and the interdisciplinary challenges that remain. Key areas for future work include developing more efficient models, integrating deterministic solutions, and refining methodologies for multi-modal and integrated techniques. These advancements pave the way for more resilient, operationally viable systems for real-time maritime surveillance.

Chapter 5

Conclusion

5.1 Introduction

The research question of the thesis seeks to address the challenges of efficiently accelerate the onboard processing of small satellites by using AI techniques. To answer the question, three areas of investigation have been advocated, i.e., wildfire response, autonomous navigation, and maritime situational awareness.

The Chapter 2 describes an end-to-end wildfire detection system using raw Sentinel-2 imagery. The system employs AI models optimized for resource-constrained hardware, achieving real-time detection with high accuracy. Tested on the CogniSat-XE2, a space-proven device, the system validates onboard wildfire detection and real-time processing for future missions.

In Chapter 3, the problem of autonomous navigation for space exploration is addressed. Our findings on the developed system are promising, showcasing navigation autonomy independently from the ground-based control.

The Chapter 4 addressed the issue of maritime situational awareness: by proposing models dealing with raw data, and by creating the first raw datasets, demonstrated ability to detect ships and wakes onboard. In particular, the methodology has been validated on representative hardware—NCS2—showing power consumptions below 3W and execution below 25s per product.

In each of these studies, the integration of AI not only enabled autonomy from ground stations but also slashed latency in the sensing-to-insight cycle. This breakthrough dramatically accelerates response times—vital for emergency operations, early warning systems, and life-saving search and rescue missions.

5.2 Summary of Main Results

Each chapter introduces novel contributions, and this section succinctly summarizes the key results and insights presented throughout the thesis.

The study presented in Chapter ?? demonstrate significant advancements in real-time wildfire detection using raw Sentinel-2 multispectral imagery, with a focus on optimizing both power consumption and processing latency. The proposed end-to-end system processes raw data directly, bypassing intermediate storage and achieving real-time performance by transmitting data to an AI accelerator. This results in faster inference and significantly reduces the time required for generating thermal

anomaly detection alerts. The system’s lightweight pre-processing step, CSC, plays a key role in maintaining computational efficiency while detecting thermal hotspots. This streamlined approach ensures the system is suited for resource-constrained environments, such as cubesats, without sacrificing accuracy. In terms of hardware performance, the integration of AI accelerators proved essential. Testing was conducted on space-targeted hardware, including the CogniSat-XE2 board, which is equipped with a Myriad X VPU. This hardware not only met the throughput demands for real-time processing but also optimized power consumption. Across various hardware setups, the Raspberry Pi 4 paired with the CogniSat-XE2 board showed an ideal balance between power efficiency and speed, achieving a time per granule of 1.8 seconds with an average power consumption of 5.5 W. Furthermore, the introduction of a novel dataset of raw Sentinel-2 imagery (THRawS), specifically tailored for thermal anomaly detection, marked a significant contribution to the field. This dataset supports future research in applying AI for spaceborne remote sensing applications. Overall, the study confirms the feasibility of real-time onboard AI processing for wildfire detection, while balancing power and computational constraints critical to space missions.

In Chapter 3 FederNet, a novel crater-based visual-based navigation system has been introduced for autonomous spacecraft navigation, particularly in lunar and planetary missions. The system addresses the challenges of navigating in irregular lunar gravity fields and without real-time ground-based support. FederNet enables autonomous position estimation by detecting and matching lunar craters with a pre-existing crater catalog. A deep learning-based crater detection algorithm using the Mask R-CNN architecture was trained on DEM images, significantly improving detection accuracy without the need for additional image processing steps. The system achieved high precision (over 81%) in crater detection, and the crater matching algorithm, based on projective invariants, enabled accurate position estimation, even in complex crater environments. FederNet demonstrated average position errors of less than 1 km, with specific phases achieving errors as low as 270 meters. The integration of an EKF further enhanced navigation accuracy. Additionally, FederNet v2 introduced a dual-mode system, combining landmark-based navigation with a feature-tracking mode for lower altitudes, achieving a horizontal displacement error of just 27.4 meters and a vertical error of 0.8 meters in descent simulations.

The Chapter 4 presented studies with novel contributions to the field of maritime surveillance using deep learning and satellite-based observation techniques. A key innovation lies in the development of a pioneering end-to-end deep learning framework for wake component identification, which employs keypoint regression to detect crucial features such as the wake vertex, turbulent wake, and Kelvin arms. This method provides a significant improvement over traditional Radon Transform-based approaches by offering a more efficient, automated, and scalable solution, optimized for deployment on low-power devices without sacrificing performance. Another central contribution is the introduction of new, carefully curated datasets for both optical and radar-based wake detection. These datasets—SSWD, MSSWD, VDS2Raw, VDVRaw, and the multi-mission, multi-frequency MMD—are the first of their kind, providing essential resources for training and validating machine learning models in ship detection and wake analysis. The developed keypoint-based method for wake component identification, surpassing traditional RT-based methods, represents the first fast, automated, and generalizable solution for deployment on low-power devices. This method was implemented using the EfficientNet-B0 architecture, achieving high inference speed (114 FPS) and compact model size (5MB).

Notably, as the first dataset to couple radar products over the same regions within a remarkably short 15-minute window, the MMD dataset enabled a pioneering demonstration of the Tip-and-Cue concept. By leveraging multi-sensor data with such temporal precision, this application opens up new possibilities in the realm of remote sensing. One being the tracking of non-cooperative vessels, allowing for more accurate predictions and dynamic monitoring of maritime traffic, a capability previously underexplored in maritime surveillance systems. Aided by the developed ship wake detector, we demonstrated route reconstruction which further enable the forecasting of future vessel movements—an advancement that significantly enhances maritime situational awareness.

In summary, the original contributions carried out in the three study areas investigated, mark a significant advancement in the field of onboard processing with DL techniques.

5.3 Limitations

As with any research endeavor, this work faces several limitations that must be acknowledged to ensure a balanced and transparent interpretation of the results. These limitations, although not undermining the significance of the contributions, provide critical insight into areas for further development and refinement.

A notable challenge relates to the deployment of ship wake detectors on representative hardware. While the proposed algorithms have demonstrated strong performance in controlled experimental environments, their real-world applicability, especially in resource-constrained satellite systems, remains to be fully tested. Ensuring that these models can operate efficiently on edge devices or embedded systems, where processing power and memory are limited, is essential for their operationalization in maritime surveillance tasks. This step requires not only testing but also potential optimization to meet the strict power and computational constraints of space-borne platforms.

Another limitation pertains to the high false alarm rate observed in SAR-based ship wake detection. While the system is designed to detect wake features in complex maritime environments, the presence of noise, rough sea conditions, or natural phenomena that resemble wakes can lead to misdetections. The current dataset, though substantial, still lacks sufficient diversity and volume to comprehensively train models across all possible maritime scenarios. As a result, the model’s ability to generalize to surface films is still constrained. Increasing the size and variability of the dataset, particularly enriching with maritime phenomena and underrepresented wake patterns, will be necessary to improve robustness and minimize false positives.

In a similar vein, the FederNet framework—designed for federated learning and real-time data processing—has not yet been fully deployed on representative hardware. Theoretical and software-based validations have confirmed its potential, but the real-world performance, especially in terms of latency and energy consumption, requires thorough testing on the hardware platforms it is intended to run on. Without this, its scalability and efficiency in operational environments remain speculative. A further technical limitation arises from the onboard equalization process applied to raw data granules of VDS2Raw. While this method enhances the usability of data for wake detection and other analytic processes, it introduces a loss of reversibility, meaning that the original raw data cannot be perfectly reconstructed. For most applications, this does not degrade performance; however, in situations where full data fidelity is required—such as for subsequent validation purposes or in downstream scientific analyses—this could present a concern. The non-reversible equalization process

introduces a trade-off between onboard data processing efficiency and downstream accuracy. Additionally, the scope of the dataset used for the thermal anomaly detection in Sentinel-2 imagery, while novel, is limited. The dataset, in its current form, may not fully capture the range of environmental conditions or operational scenarios that could affect system performance in real-world wildfire detection. Extending the dataset to cover more diverse atmospheric conditions, geographical regions, and seasonal variations is essential to ensure that the model's predictions are generalizable across different operational environments. Without this extension, the current findings, while promising, may not be directly applicable to all potential use cases.

In conclusion, while the research demonstrates significant progress in the field of spaceborne onboard processing, these limitations highlight areas where further investigation and refinement are needed. Addressing these challenges will be critical for improving the robustness, generalizability, and real-world applicability of the proposed methodologies.

5.4 Final Remarks

Across the three primary areas of investigation—wildfire detection, autonomous navigation, and maritime situational awareness—the work showcases novel methodologies that push the boundaries of what is currently feasible for small satellites with limited computational resources.

In the domain of wildfire response, the study demonstrates the capability of real-time, onboard thermal anomaly detection systems to operate autonomously using raw multispectral imagery. The introduction of AI-driven pre-processing pipelines combined with efficient hardware integration illustrates the potential for rapid emergency response applications, opening new avenues for spaceborne remote sensing systems.

For autonomous navigation, the development of FederNet introduces a novel crater-based navigation system that enables spacecraft to perform high-precision localization without ground-based support. This represents a breakthrough in autonomy for space exploration missions, particularly for lunar and planetary landings, where the system can reliably navigate using visual-based methods.

In maritime situational awareness, the work offers groundbreaking contributions through the development of deep learning-based ship and wake detection systems, optimized for low-power satellite platforms. This research sets the stage for future innovations in ship tracking and surveillance, particularly in complex environments where traditional systems struggle.

Each of these contributions is underscored by a strong focus on practicality—ensuring that the solutions proposed can be deployed on edge devices and embedded systems, overcoming the power and latency limitations typical of satellite operations. The datasets, algorithms, and methodologies introduced have laid the groundwork for future research and development, and their application extends well beyond the confines of the current studies. Looking ahead, the long-term potential of these research efforts is immense. The autonomy demonstrated in each domain has far-reaching implications for the future of space exploration, environmental monitoring, and global maritime security. By continuing to refine and expand on these foundational technologies, we move closer to fully autonomous, real-time satellite systems capable of transforming our ability to respond to critical events, navigate remote environments, and monitor vast oceanic regions.

In reflecting on the journey of this work, it is clear that the integration of AI into satellite systems represents a transformative leap forward. The advancements achieved point toward a fu-

ture where the entire data processing pipeline could be performed autonomously on orbit, allowing satellites to extract meaningful insights in real time. Rather than transmitting vast amounts of raw data back to Earth, these systems would send only the most critical information or actionable insights, reducing bandwidth requirements and dramatically increasing the speed of decision-making processes. This shift would enable more efficient use of satellite resources, revolutionizing fields like environmental monitoring, disaster response, and space exploration. In addition to its contributions on Earth, this research opens significant possibilities for the autonomy of space exploration. As spacecraft increasingly rely on AI-driven systems for real-time data analysis and decision-making, we move closer to missions that can operate independently from ground-based control. The advancements in onboard processing demonstrated in this thesis suggest a future where space exploration missions—whether to the Moon, Mars, or beyond—will rely on autonomous navigation, hazard detection, and resource identification. This autonomy will be crucial for long-duration missions where communication delays with Earth make real-time control impractical. AI-powered spacecraft will not only enhance the efficiency and safety of exploration but also enable humanity to explore deeper into the cosmos, navigating and responding to unknown environments with unprecedented independence.

While the challenges encountered were substantial, the outcomes of this research highlight the importance of persistence, innovation, and interdisciplinary collaboration. This thesis stands as a testament to the growing potential of small satellites to perform large-scale, high-impact tasks autonomously, meeting humanity’s most pressing needs both on Earth and in space, and heralding an era where satellites act as intelligent, self-sufficient systems in orbit.

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Appendix A

Appendix

A.1 Multi-Mission Dataset Products

A.1.1 Egadi islands

The products matched over the Egadi scenario are reported in Table A.1. As it is possible to observe from Table 4.15, there are no SAOCOM products coupled in this scenario. Analyzing the orbit type of COSMO-SkyMed products, it is possible to acknowledge that is always descending, contrarily to the orbit type of Sentinel-1 products which is always ascending. In the vast majority of the pairings, the COSMO-SkyMed-1 satellite is matched to the Sentinel-1B.

Table A.1: Table listing COSMO-SkyMed & Sentinel-1 product pairs over the Egadi region with orbit type (OT) and satellite (SAT) reported.

CSK			SEN		
ID	OT	SAT	ID	OT	SAT
1293433	D	CSK-1	.._DA40	A	S1B
1293433	D	CSK-1	.._8795	A	S1B
1357156	D	CSK-1	.._981C	A	S1B
1357156	D	CSK-1	.._78B8	A	S1B
1388973	D	CSK-1	.._5E57	A	S1B
1388973	D	CSK-1	.._F637	A	S1B
1545679	D	CSK-1	.._3AE1	A	S1B
1545679	D	CSK-1	.._FF3C	A	S1B
1648226	D	CSK-1	.._5F2C	A	S1B
1648226	D	CSK-1	.._B2A1	A	S1B
1672570	D	CSK-2	.._7FDA	A	S1B
1672570	D	CSK-2	.._C828	A	S1B
1762255	D	CSK-1	.._81C7	A	S1B
1762255	D	CSK-1	.._2482	A	S1B
1794761	D	CSK-2	.._8FEA	A	S1B
1794761	D	CSK-2	.._D86B	A	S1B

A.1.2 Adriatic Sea

Concerning the COSMO-SkyMed and Sentinel-1 products, the products matched over the Adriatic scenario are reported in Tables A.2-A.4. As it is possible to observe from Table A.2, also in this scenario the orbit types are opposite. Turning attention to the platforms, the dataset has shown a good variance in this case. Indeed, three out of the four COSMO-SkyMed satellites and both the

Sentinel-1 satellites have been acquired. Regarding the COSMO-SkyMed and SAOCOM products paired, in all the five couples the orbit type is the same, either ascending or descending. This is not in contrast with the unique platforms coupling, i.e. COSMO-SkyMed-1 and SAO1A. Finally, considering the Sentinel-1 and SAOCOM couplings (Table A.4), the orbits are of the same type, and the Sentinel’s platforms are diversified.

Table A.2: Table listing COSMO-SkyMed & Sentinel-1 product pairs over the Adriatic region with orbit type (OT) and satellite (SAT) reported.

CSK			SEN		
ID	OT	SAT	ID	OT	SAT
1266369	D	CSK-1	.._271C	A	S1B
1275943	D	CSK-1	.._BAD2	A	S1A
1280633	D	CSK-1	.._E4C1	A	S1B
1310194	D	CSK-1	.._5BCA	A	S1B
1340348	D	CSK-1	.._60B1	A	S1B
1479132	D	CSK-1	.._8123	A	S1B
1599279	D	CSK-1	.._257C	A	S1B
1730645	D	CSK-1	.._3956	A	S1B
1290589	D	CSK-2	.._E51A	A	S1B
1322026	D	CSK-2	.._3301	A	S1B
1322085	D	CSK-4	.._1F05	A	S1A
1322085	D	CSK-4	.._B23F	A	S1A
1505200	D	CSK-4	.._77DD	A	S1B
1681855	D	CSK-4	.._0BE9	A	S1B
1681855	D	CSK-4	.._E00F	A	S1B

Table A.3: Table listing SAOCOM & Sentinel-1 product pairs over the Adriatic region with orbit type (OT) and satellite (SAT) reported.

SEN			SAO		
ID	OT	SAT	ID	OT	SAT
.._1C60	D	S1A	E...1648365	A	SAO1A
.._1C60	D	S1A	E...1648344	A	SAO1A
.._5DBF	D	S1A	E...1466555	A	SAO1A
.._5DBF	D	S1A	E...1466535	A	SAO1A
.._6F18	D	S1B	E...1324975	A	SAO1A
.._6F18	D	S1B	E...1325195	A	SAO1A
.._4FE1	D	S1A	E...1289028	A	SAO1A
.._4FE1	D	S1A	E...1289039	A	SAO1A
.._E0A7	D	S1B	E...1178505	A	SAO1A
.._E0A7	D	S1B	E...1178729	A	SAO1A
.._2E53	D	S1A	E...1140164	A	SAO1A
.._2E53	D	S1A	E...1140151	A	SAO1A

Table A.4: Table listing COSMO-SkyMed & SAOCOM product pairs over the Adriatic region with orbit type (OT) and satellite (SAT) reported.

CSK			SAO		
ID	OT	SAT	ID	OT	SAT
1529475	D	CSK-1	E...1179846	D	SAO1A
1653365	D	CSK-1	E...1258329	D	SAO1A
1696271	D	CSK-1	E...1383006	D	SAO1A
1653365	D	CSK-1	E...1258316	D	SAO1A
1702876	A	CSK-1	E...1390850	A	SAO1A

A.1.3 Sardinia

In the end, the products matched over the Sardinia scenario are analyzed and reported in Tables A.6-A.8.

The intercorrelations among the orbit types of the coupling of COSMO-SkyMed and SAOCOM products are reported in Table A.5. Also in this case, the orbit types are the same for both the product types. Concerning the platforms, COSMO-SkyMed-1 and SAO1A are the only two satellites that showed a matching. Turning now to the evidence of Tables A.6-A.7, it is possible to state that the orbits in the case of COSMO-SkyMed and Sentinel-1 matches are of the opposite type. Surprisingly, the only Sentinel-1A has found coupled products while the COSMO-SkyMed platforms are many. In the end, from Table A.8 it is clear that even in this case the orbits are of the same kind with a unique platform matching the satellite Sentinel-1A with SAO1A.

Table A.5: Table listing COSMO-SkyMed & SAOCOM product pairs over the Sardinia region with orbit type (OT) and satellite (SAT) reported.

CSK			SAO		
ID	OT	SAT	ID	OT	SAT
1534730	D	CSK-1	E...1198795	D	SAO1A
1534730	D	CSK-1	E...1198827	D	SAO1A
1598374	A	CSK-1	E...1170243	A	SAO1A
1598374	A	CSK-1	E...1169649	A	SAO1A
1643704	D	CSK-1	E...1240108	D	SAO1A
1643704	D	CSK-1	E...1240050	D	SAO1A
1643704	D	CSK-1	E...1240057	D	SAO1A
1643704	D	CSK-1	E...1240059	D	SAO1A
1652334	A	CSK-1	E...1257354	A	SAO1A
1652334	A	CSK-1	E...1257516	A	SAO1A
1652334	A	CSK-1	E...1257235	A	SAO1A
1699257	D	CSK-1	E...1386298	D	SAO1A
1699257	D	CSK-1	E...1386327	D	SAO1A
1699257	D	CSK-1	E...1386386	D	SAO1A
1751759	A	CSK-1	E...1582482	A	SAO1A
1751759	A	CSK-1	E...1582481	A	SAO1A
1751759	A	CSK-1	E...1582518	A	SAO1A
1751759	A	CSK-1	E...1582458	A	SAO1A
1751759	A	CSK-1	E...1582430	A	SAO1A
1756348	D	CSK-1	E...1591762	D	SAO1A
1756348	D	CSK-1	E...1591783	D	SAO1A
1756348	D	CSK-1	E...1592317	D	SAO1A
1756348	D	CSK-1	E...1591582	D	SAO1A

Table A.6: Table listing COSMO-SkyMed (CSK) & Sentinel-1 (SEN) product pairs over the Sardinia region with orbit type (OT) and satellite (SAT) reported. Part 1.

CSK			SEN		
ID	OT	SAT	ID	OT	SAT
1266960	D	CSK-1	.._BC52	A	S1A
1281788	D	CSK-1	.._68EE	A	S1A
1281788	D	CSK-1	.._5D58	A	S1A
1281788	D	CSK-1	.._A65E	A	S1A
1311179	D	CSK-1	.._4E34	A	S1A
1311179	D	CSK-1	.._0E5B	A	S1A
1311179	D	CSK-1	.._69A0	A	S1A
1341805	D	CSK-1	.._CC8B	A	S1A
1341805	D	CSK-1	.._C2FA	A	S1A
1341805	D	CSK-1	.._21A5	A	S1A
1373764	D	CSK-1	.._B8B4	A	S1A
1373764	D	CSK-1	.._9997	A	S1A
1373764	D	CSK-1	.._FA60	A	S1A
1619147	D	CSK-1	.._FA89	A	S1A
1676151	D	CSK-1	.._2ABD	A	S1A
1676151	D	CSK-1	.._C735	A	S1A
1676151	D	CSK-1	.._BBEE	A	S1A
1737846	D	CSK-1	.._957E	A	S1A
1737846	D	CSK-1	.._33CB	A	S1A
1737846	D	CSK-1	.._517C	A	S1A
1800228	D	CSK-1	.._9CF0	A	S1A
1800228	D	CSK-1	.._2266	A	S1A
1800228	D	CSK-1	.._97C1	A	S1A
1271840	D	CSK-2	.._B978	A	S1A
1271840	D	CSK-2	.._5A67	A	S1A
1271840	D	CSK-2	.._2EAB	A	S1A
1295617	D	CSK-2	.._5220	A	S1A
1295617	D	CSK-2	.._433E	A	S1A
1327050	D	CSK-2	.._EE14	A	S1A
1327050	D	CSK-2	.._CEB4	A	S1A
1327050	D	CSK-2	.._2445	A	S1A
1359039	D	CSK-2	.._9FB8	A	S1A

Table A.7: Table listing COSMO-SkyMed (CSK) & Sentinel-1 (SEN) product pairs over the Sardinia region with orbit type (OT) and satellite (SAT) reported. Part 2.

CSK			SEN		
ID	OT	SAT	ID	OT	SAT
1359039	D	CSK-2	.._E316	A	S1A
1392673	D	CSK-2	.._45C6	A	S1A
1392673	D	CSK-2	.._689F	A	S1A
1444983	D	CSK-2	.._E509	A	S1A
1444983	D	CSK-2	.._4826	A	S1A
1444983	D	CSK-2	.._173D	A	S1A
1652352	D	CSK-2	.._53BE	A	S1A
1652352	D	CSK-2	.._84E3	A	S1A
1652352	D	CSK-2	.._37C3	A	S1A
1767344	D	CSK-2	.._29A0	A	S1A
1767344	D	CSK-2	.._0D3C	A	S1A
1767344	D	CSK-2	.._4489	A	S1A
1842293	D	CSK-2	.._3BC6	A	S1B
1288075	D	CSK-4	.._9439	A	S1A
1288075	D	CSK-4	.._0608	A	S1A
1351845	D	CSK-4	.._83D8	A	S1A
1351845	D	CSK-4	.._7C16	A	S1A
1426712	D	CSK-4	.._139B	A	S1A
1426712	D	CSK-4	.._9510	A	S1A
1524061	D	CSK-4	.._F42E	A	S1A
1524061	D	CSK-4	.._33F3	A	S1A
1693039	D	CSK-4	.._4EDC	A	S1A
1693039	D	CSK-4	.._EB97	A	S1A

Table A.8: Table listing SAOCOM & Sentinel-1 product pairs over the Sardinia region with orbit type (OT) and satellite (SAT) reported.

SEN			SAO		
ID	OT	SAT	ID	OT	SAT
.._9E85	A	S1A	E...1719361	D	SAO1A
.._9E85	A	S1A	E...1719372	D	SAO1A
.._5E2E	A	S1A	E...1539550	D	SAO1A
.._5E2E	A	S1A	E...1539549	D	SAO1A
.._5E2E	A	S1A	E...1539785	D	SAO1A
.._ECD9	A	S1A	E...1352271	D	SAO1A
.._ECD9	A	S1A	E...1352377	D	SAO1A
.._9BD8	A	S1A	E...1213291	D	SAO1A
.._9BD8	A	S1A	E...1213557	D	SAO1A
.._9BD8	A	S1A	E...1212985	D	SAO1A